

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D2.9

The CoBraD ethical and regulatory
framework v2

March 2024

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIA	Artificial intelligence Act
C108	Council of Europe convention on automated processing
CIOMS Guidelines	International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans
COCIR	European Coordination Committee of the Radiological and Electromedical and Healthcare IT Industry
CTR	Clinical Trials Regulation
DGA	Data governance Act
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data protection impact assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
Dx.y	Deliverable number y
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention of Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICH GCP	International Conference on Harmonization of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use.
ICT	Information and communications technology
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PUC	Pilot Use Cases
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
WHO GCP	WHO Guidelines for Good Clinical Practice (GCP)
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This executive summary captures the updates and additions that have been incorporated to the second version of the MES-COBraD Ethical and Regulatory framework v1¹.

- › **Section 2:** The Ethical Framework in the MES-CoBRAd project
 - New section 2.3 reports on the follow up of the ethical framework and offers a follow-up on how the project has implemented the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice.
- › **Section 3:** The Regulatory Framework in MES-CoBraD
 - Updated on 3.3.1 Secondary law reflect relevant aspects of newly adopted legislation on data law (Data Governance Act and Data Act). It also includes an introduction to the Cybersecurity Framework and a reference to the AI risk categorisation from the Artificial Intelligence Act.
 - Added New subsection 3.5 introducing the European Union Cybersecurity framework.
 - Added subsection 3.6 on the Medical Device Regulation.
- › **Section 4:** Capita Selecta: Data protection assessment in Mes-CoBrAD.
 - Added a new subsection 4.1.1 on MES-CoBrad methodology for a data protection impact assessment. This section introduces the different phases of the methodology followed during the project.
 - Added a new subsection 4.2 Presentation of CJEU findings with regards to the concept of personal data, identification, and the assessment of pseudonymisation and anonymisation.
 - Updated subsection 4.3 Personal data and health data, following on the findings previously presented. In relation to that, s. 4.3.5 provides an update on the data processed during the project.
 - Updated subsection 4.4 to reflect what has occurred during the project by reference to that recorded in the DMP.
 - Updated subsection 4.5 to reflect the organisational measures adopted by the project with regards to responsibilities on datasets.
 - Updated subsection 4.6 to incorporate the assessment on the de-personalisation module as requested in the midterm review.
 - Updated 4.7 on data principles. Introduced subsection 4.7.6 reporting on key insights form the dpia questionnaires.
 - Added a new section 4.8 aggregating: storage, integrity, confidentiality, and security. Identification or risk. Introduced subsection 4.8.4 reporting on key insights form the dpia questionnaires.
 - Updated subsection 4.9 on the principle of accountability.
 - Updated subsection 4.10 on data protection by design and by default.
 - Updated subsection 4.11 on data subject rights. Introduced subsection 4.11.7 reporting on key insights form the dpia questionnaires.
 - Updated subsection 4.12 on international data transfers
- › **Section 5:** former section 5 on the MDR has been moved to section 3 subsection 3.6..

¹ D2.3 MES-CoBRAd ethical and regulatory framework v1- Submitted in March 2022.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

MES-CoBraD is a scientific project that strongly relies on the processing of data from diverse sources, including data specially protected under the GDPR. Because of the sensitivity of the project's envisaged processing activities, the responsibilities and obligations of the consortium have been assessed side by side with the applicable ethical and normative frameworks. These frameworks have been defined as an "essential supporting structure" establishing the conditions and principles for the project ethical and data protection assessment.²

The second version of the Ethical and Regulatory framework reports describes how the project has dealt with the WP2 Task 2.1 concerning fundamental rights for data protection, as well as the social and functional acceptance of the research activities in MES-CoBraD and the development of MES-CoBraD platform.

More concretely two main objectives have been pursued:

First, offer an update on the normative and ethical framework relevant to the consortium for the performance of its research activities. In that regard, the ethical and normative frameworks have been outlined and updated to help partners assess, anticipate, and mitigate the risks to research participants and their personal data throughout the duration of the whole project. Specific guidance has been provided to the partners in order to conduct the research according to the ethical and data protection principles.

Second, the present document offers practical insights and guidance for the implementation of the principles of data protection by design and by default in the development of the MES-CoBraD platform in a scenario of deployment and exploitation.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE AND UPDATES

The structure and content of the deliverable is built upon VUB's experience and involvement in previous EU funded projects, in particular TenDER³, Nutrishield⁴ and PROTEIN⁵:

The second section introduces the ethical framework in MES-CoBraD. An update on research ethics during the Project has been added.

The third section titled Regulatory framework: Data Protection and Cybersecurity in MESCoBraD, informs the partners on the applicable data protection and cybersecurity laws and applicable to MES-CoBraD research. In this second version a new subsection is incorporated following up on new the so-called new generation of EU data laws. In that regard it offers a legislative update on the recently adopted i) Data Governance Act; ii) Data Act and iii) the Artificial Intelligence Act. In addition, the section also incorporates

² Kloza, Dariusz, Niels van Dijk, Simone Casiraghi, Sergi Vazquez Maymir, Sara Roda, Alessia Tanas and Ioulia Konstantinou (2019) "Towards a method for data protection impact assessment: Making sense of GDPR requirements", d.pia.lab Policy Brief No. 1/2019, VUB: Brussels.

³ P. Quinn, E. Mantovani, A. van Scharen (VUB), PROTEIN, D10.1 Report on security, data protection, privacy, consumer protection, ethics and social acceptance (TARESS Framework) (2019) ("PROTEIN"); Personalised nutrition for healthy living: Protein;

⁴ D.Markopoulou, E. Papakonstantinou (VUB), D6.5 – Data governance and ETL specifications -Preliminary Version, Fact-based personalized nutrition for the young: ("Nutrishield");

⁵ P. Quinn, L. Feirabend (VUB), D1.1 – Fundamental Rights, Ethical and Legal Implications and Assessment AffecTive basEd iNtegrateD carE for betteR Quality of Life: ("TeNDER") Project;

a cybersecurity framework.

The fourth section has been reframed to reflect the focus on the assessment carried through MES-CoBraD. It presents, from a theoretical and practical approach, critical issues to the processing activities envisaged in MES-CoBraD and explains the methodology followed during the project to assess the data protection issues raised in the previous version. In addition, concepts and recommendations have also been updated, taking into account recent developments in the field.

The fifth section considers the MES-CoBraD platform in light of the EU Medical Devices Regulation.

1.3 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES/WPS/TASKS

The conclusions and outputs of the present deliverable are, in general, relevant to all tasks and WPs of the MES-CoBraD project. This said, the following WPs tasks and deliverables are particularly affected by the D2.3 The CoBraD ethical and regulatory frameworks-v1 findings and recommendations:

- › WP2 on Legal, Ethics and Security Frameworks. D2.3 represents the basis for the D.2.9 and the updated version of the MES-CoBraD ethical and regulatory framework-v2; D2.9 also provides inputs to T2.2 The CoBraD PUC legal and ethical assessment and its results in D2.5, Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards-v1 and D2.8 Final Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards -v2.
- › WP3 on Landscape analysis & Methodology. In particular, D2.9 provides the ethical and normative frameworks for T3.6–ETHAI model of AI in healthcare ethics standard development and its results in D3.9.
- › WP5 on Common multi-source research data lake & resource sharing and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular, T5.1 regarding the data integration and harmonisation for heterogeneous data sources; and T5.2 and the development of the security and anonymisation requirements.
- › WP6 on Advanced Analytics and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular, T6.1- and the specifications, requirements, infrastructure design and preparation for Expert System (ES); T6.3 and the implementation of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) knowledge-based system for data analysis and interpretation.
- › WP7 on Integrated Clinical Research Platform and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular, T7.3 will take input from the architectural framework developed in T7.1 and will integrate the software components developed in WP5 and WP6 to form a sound MES-CoBraD platform.
- › WP8 on Pilot RWD Acquisition in CoBraD and its different tasks and deliverables, in particular, T8.1 – Participant recruitment and pre-existing RWD access and T8.3 Secure RWD sharing.

2 THE ETHICAL FRAMEWORK IN THE MES COBRAD PROJECT

2.1 INTRODUCTION RESEARCH ETHICS AND INNOVATION GOVERNANCE IN MES-COBRA D

The proliferation of invocations of ‘ethics,’ especially concerning the recent debate on (the regulation of) Artificial Intelligence (AI), has been referred to as the “ethification” phenomenon. Ethics is often invoked to protect individuals against the disruptive effects of digital technologies on their rights and freedoms and to steer the development of such technologies in a desirable direction. Along this way, it is proposed as an alternative or complement to the law to regulate emerging technologies.⁶

As a synonym for moral philosophy, ethics is a branch of philosophy that deals, generally speaking, with “a rational and practical reflection on what is good or bad and right or wrong”.⁷ While the term morals refer to de facto habits, customs and traditions, ethics refers to a systematic reflection, a philosophical critique and evaluation. In the context of scientific research, classical ethics must also be distinguished from institutional ethics, namely those settings relating to policy, regulation, and research integrity or, more generally, politics.

The research activities performed in MES-CoBraD, involve different practices, actors, and institutions from various locations. In order to better approach the ethical elements of a multidisciplinary project, the ethical framework in MES-CoBraD is structured upon the distinction between “Research ethics” and “Innovation governance ethics.”

On one hand, Research ethics concerns the screening of project proposals or research activities that involve human participants, and it relates to the conduct of researchers themselves. In MES-CoBraD it focuses on the interaction between human participants and medical ethics and the role of informed consent in PUCS.

On the other hand, Innovation governance ethics applies to the research responsible for designing a technological solution. It is a way of governing technological innovation, while not directly based on legally binding norms, it aims to provide an advisory input for developers of the MES-CoBraD platform.

2.2 RESEARCH ETHICS IN MES-COBRA D

2.2.1 THE RESEARCH ETHICS FRAMEWORK AT MES- COBRA D

Research engaging with human participants must abide to medical ethics principles.⁸ Through history the principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice, have been refined and developed by the medical community and codified in our language.⁹ The principles are not absolute and must be balanced in order to strike a compromise between sometimes other competing interests. Normatively

⁶ N. van Dijk, S. Casiraghi, and S. Gutwirth, ‘The “Ethification” of ICT Governance. Artificial Intelligence and Data Protection in the European Union,’ *Computer Law & Security Review* 43 (1 November 2021): 105597,

⁷ Scholars distinguish, within moral philosophy between metaethics, normative ethics and applied ethics. The former deals with metaphysical, epistemological, or psychological pre- suppositions related to moral language, thought, and practice; normative ethics deals with the rational explanation behind the rules that would guide one’s action; applied ethics deals with the practical application of normative theories to concrete cases. Ibid.

⁸ See D2.1 Legal and Ethical helpdesk v1 (2021)

⁹ T. L. Beauchamp, J. F. Childress, *Principles of biomedical ethics*, Oxford University Press, USA, 2001; Walter, Klein eds. *The Story of Bioethics: From seminal works to contemporary explorations*; see also McLean S. *Autonomy, Consent, and the Law*. Routledge, 2010, Paperback, 248 pp

speaking they scattered in several diverse sources both at an international and national level.¹⁰¹¹

Table 1 MES-CoBraD medical ethics principles

Principle of autonomy	Highlights the need to protect the patients and research participant autonomy. In that regard, informed consent constitutes a mechanism how patients and research participants can exercise their autonomy.
Principle of beneficence	The principle of beneficence requires a physician to do good and act in the best interest of the patient.
Principle of non-maleficence	Requires a physician to do no harm and avoid acting against the patient’s interests. It also requires the physician to “weigh the expected harmful effects of any proposed intervention against the intended beneficial effects.”
Principle of justice	The physician’s decisions about resource allocation require equitable distribution of medical goods and services. This principle also implies a prohibition to discriminate and warns the physician against making decisions based on negative stereotypes.

When considering the relevant ethical framework in connection to the MES-CoBraD research with human participants, a distinction should be made between research involving tests of medicinal products on humans and the observation of humans using medical devices.

Insofar MES-CoBraD does not intend to test a medicinal product on human participants, the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR)¹² is not applicable. Nevertheless, references to the provisions therein are considered as guidelines and good practices.¹³

2.2.2 PATIENT RIGHTS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

While the project’s research goal is to not to treat patients, they are acknowledged as the primary source of the RWD used for the research in MES-CoBraD.¹⁴ Their status as patients grants certain rights at the EU level as set out in the EU Directive 2011/24/EU on the application of Patients’ rights in cross border healthcare.¹⁵

Much of the Patients Directive deals with the practical implications of cross-border healthcare, such as reimbursement of treatments and other relevant administrative procedures. However, and in line with data protection rules and the data subject rights, the Patients Directive also requires that healthcare providers give relevant information to help patients make informed decisions and exercise their rights.¹⁶ In this respect, Article 4 (2) identifies a number of obligations for the healthcare service providers, including those based on Information Communication Technologies (ICT) solutions with regards to:

- › provision of clear information regarding the availability, safety, and quality of healthcare,

¹⁰ They have been already introduced in detail at D.2.1 CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk report v1, section 4.1.2 Identification and recruitment procedures Submitted in M6.

¹¹ See TeNDER, D1.1 Fundamental Rights, Ethical and Legal Implications and Assessment; See also p. 18 PROTEIN, Baseline Report on legal and ethical aspects of human participation in research, personal data protection, human tissues and cells, and medical device p. 14.

¹² The Regulation aims to ensure the EU offers an attractive and favourable environment for carrying out clinical research on a large scale, with high standards of public transparency and safety for clinical trial participants. Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC, OJEU L 158 27/05/2014

¹³ See EDPB (2019), Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) (ar 70.1.b)).

¹⁴ See MES-CoBraD, D2.2 Data Management Plan v1.

¹⁵ Directive 2011/24/EU of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients’ rights in cross-border healthcare.

¹⁶ Ibid Article 5(d).

- › the prices,
- › complaint procedures and mechanisms,
- › information on professional liability,
- › measures adopted to protect the patient's personal data.

The Patients Directive further recognises the Member state's obligation to ensure the security of the data subject's fundamental right to privacy by subjecting its scope to the GDPR.¹⁷

2.2.3 INFORMED CONSENT AND PILOT USE CASES (PUCS).

In medical research, the principle of autonomy translates into the requirement of obtaining the patient's permission for intervening on their body.¹⁸ For the consent to be valid, it must be informed.

Based on the judgement of the Nazi war crimes at Nuremberg in 1947, the Nuremberg Code laid down 10 standards to which physicians must conform when carrying out experiments on human subjects.¹⁹ The first requirement was that of "voluntary consent".

More recently the Declaration of Helsinki adopted in 1964 and its subsequent updates, have elaborated on the notion of consent in medical research. In its current version, paragraph 25 and 26 introduces the notion of informed consent, emphasising the information to be provided to a participant in a research activity.^{20 21}

Today it is broadly recognised that the constitutive elements of competent judgement by the patient or participant and thus the source of an informed decision involve the following attributes:²²

- i. the ability to receive, process, and understand information,
- ii. the ability to appreciate the situation and its consequences,
- iii. the ability to weigh benefits, risks, and alternatives, and
- iv. the ability to make and communicate a decision.

The Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine,²³ known as the Oviedo convention is the first international legally binding instrument in the field of bioethics. It provides a framework for the protection of human rights and human dignity by establishing fundamental principles applicable to health care, medical research, transplantation, and genomics²⁴. Jointly with its additional Protocol, they outline the human rights principles in biomedicine through Europe. According to Article 5 of the Oviedo Convention, an intervention in the health field can only be carried out after the person involved has given free and informed consent. By reference to this general principle, Article 16(v) sets out the conditions for

¹⁷ Patients' Rights Directive 2011/21/European Union Article 11 (2) a. Also, and while not strictly applicable to MES-CoBraD research its provisions on the E-health network might of relevance when it comes to deploy the platform (Article 14 (1) Patients' Rights Directive)

¹⁸ Garrett et. al., Health Care Ethics, Prentice Hall, 2nd Edition (1993), See TENDER D1.1, p.18.

¹⁹ British Medical Journal No 7070 Volume 313: Page 1448, 7 December 1996

²⁰ In this sense, the Declaration requires that special attention is given "to the specific information needs of individual potential subjects as well as to the methods used to deliver the information." World Medical Association, Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects (June 1964, and most recently amended October 2013).

²¹ Informed consent in research with human participants has been included in many other instruments, including in the ICCPR, CIOMS Guidelines, the ICH GCP, the WHO GCP, and the UNESCO Declaration.

²² See for instance Guideline 19, CIOMS Guidelines, p. 62; Meulenbroek et al., Informed Consent in Dementia research. Legislation, Theoretical Concepts and How to Assess Capacity to Consent. See also Kosta, E. (2013). Consent in European data protection law. (Nijhoff Studies in European Union Law; No. 3). Martinus Nijhoff. See also Tender p22 European Geriatric Medicine 1 (2010) 58-63 ("Meulenbroek et al."), p. 58. ; TENDER p.22

²³ Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, 4.IV.1997

²⁴ Council of Europe, Bioethics;

conducting research on a person, including that “the necessary consent as provided for under Article 5 has been given expressly, specifically, and is documented. This consent may be freely withdrawn at any time. ’

The Oviedo Additional Protocol deals in more detail with the issue of informed consent in biomedical research requiring in its article 13 that all potential research participants are provided with “adequate information in a comprehensible form” and lists the elements that they should be informed of, including the nature, extent, duration of the study, risks and benefits of participation, the handling of personal data and compensation in case of damage. ²⁵

Article 14 of the protocol then reiterates that “no research on a person may be carried out [...] without the informed, free, express, specific and documented consent of the person” and that “such consent may be freely withdrawn by the person at any phase of the research”. ²⁶

Finally, in the EU pharmaceutical context, the CTR introduces in its article 28 the mandatory requirement of informed consent for the performance of clinical trials. Its article 29 elaborates on the formalities and different elements of informed consent. ²⁷

Importantly, the requirement for consent for a subject to participate in a CTR must be distinguished from the requirements for a lawful processing of personal data under the GDPR. As indicated by the EDPB in its guidelines on clinical trials, the requirement of informed consent by the CTR must not be confused with consent as a legal ground for processing personal data set out in Article 6(1) (a) of the GDPR. Informed consent, in the context of CTR, is a safeguard not a legal basis for data processing. It serves as an ethical standard and procedural obligation. ²⁸

In MES-CoBraD each institution involved in research with humans has used its own consent form and procedures. The following indicates the minimum information requirements of a valid consent to participate research:

Table 2 MES-CoBraD Information requirements for research participants

1.	Research scope and funding of the project;	2.	The right to ask any questions;
3.	The voluntary nature of the participation;	4.	The incidental findings policy detailing what happens if something suspicious is detected;
5.	The fact that personal data will be collected, for which purpose and in which secured form;	6.	The possibility to stop participation at any time;
7.	Expected duration of the participant’s participation;	8.	No advantage or inducement shall be offered;
9.	Possible risks and discomfort (if any);	10.	Ethics approval has been sought
11.	Appropriate contact details of the researchers.		

²⁵ CETS 195 – Human Rights and Biomedicine (Protocol), 25.I.2005 Article 13

²⁶ Ibid Article 14

²⁷ CTR Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 article 28

²⁸ EDPB, (2019), Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) (art. 70.1.b).

2.2.4 COMPETENT ETHICS COMMITTEES

In addition to international norms of conduct, medical research with human subjects is subject to the approval of ethics committees. In general research ethics committee “must be transparent in its functioning, must be independent of the researcher, the sponsor, and any other undue influence and must be duly qualified.”²⁹

The CTR defines an ethics committee as “an independent body established in a Member State in accordance with the law of that Member State and empowered to give opinions for the purposes of this Regulation, taking into account the views of laypersons, in particular patients or patients' organisation.”³⁰

2.3 RESULTS FROM THE MES-COBRA D ETHICAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

The first version of the Ethical and Regulatory framework highlighted certain issues but left some questions open, as it was not possible to completely settle them at the moment the deliverable was written. However, this updated version, nearing the project's completion, benefits from the comprehensive efforts invested in the legal and ethical evaluation of the PUCs (D2.5) and the development of the ETHAI model. As a result, many aspects, particularly concerning the integration of AI within the project, have been clarified. This section aims to address some of the concerns from the D2.3 deliverable, specifically focusing on the ethical considerations surrounding the implementation of AI within the project and its resulting outcomes.

In the initial version of this deliverable, it was established that the adherence to ethical requirements (AI HLEG and WHO) would be verified, and their relevance to the MES-CoBraD project evaluated through various measures. These actions included formulating and disseminating an internal ethics questionnaire, creating an infographic and an ethics guide as a “how to” and aiding in the design process of AI solutions.

The ethics questionnaire was indeed distributed among partners prior to the completion of the D2.5 deliverable, of which it constituted a crucial component, returning informative findings. It was structured into four sections mirroring the ethical principles outlined by the ethical requirements and the four principles of bioethics: “**respect for persons**” (further divided into “autonomy” and “respect”), “**beneficence**”, “**non-maleficence**”, and “**justice**”. The questionnaire was founded on a **set of requirements derived from the frameworks delineated in the D2.1 and D2.3** deliverables, further elaborated upon during the development of the D2.5.

While the focus of the D2.5 assessment primarily revolved around PUCs 1 and 2, encompassing areas such as medical ethics, group composition, real-world data (RWD) gathering, and patients' rights, rather than solely on AI-related matters addressed in the innovation governance section of the D2.3 deliverable, it nonetheless provides valuable insights into clarifying certain unresolved points. In the subsequent subsections, pertinent results from the ethics questionnaire, as well as from the desk assessment and inquiries made during the drafting of the ETHAI model, will be presented where applicable.

Regarding the other two actions, an infographic and a set of FAQs have been incorporated into the second version of the helpdesk deliverable (D2.6). Additionally, the requirements, particularly those pivotal to the development of the ETHAI, have been discussed with partners on multiple occasions, encompassing plenary sessions, face-to-face meetings, and dedicated sessions with partners overseeing the expert system's development.

However, it is important to acknowledge that for meaningful participation (and thereby support) in the

²⁹ Regulation (EU) No 536/2014, on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use (CTR Regulation) (EU), article 29
³⁰ idem Article 2

design process of AI solutions, the approach should have been slightly different, initiating concurrently from the project's outset. In this regard, the forthcoming deliverable dedicated to the ETHAI will delineate an approach aimed at shaping **the design of AI solutions right from the project's inception**, thus circumventing the need for solely post-assessment evaluations and instead embedding ethics into the design and development process.

It is worth mentioning, though, that a preliminary version of the D3.9 deliverable (the ETHAI model) was disseminated relatively early, in M24. Subsequently, it was presented during a face-to-face meeting, followed by two dedicated sessions with scientific and technical partners to discuss the ethical requirements pertaining to the design, implementation, and testing of AI modules outlined in the document. Thus, while a true ethics-by-design process may not have been fully realized, **there existed substantial engagement and collaboration between technical and ethical-legal partners.**

In the following sections, there is a quick review of what has been done with respect to each macro-requirement, to ensure through diverse assessments that the consortium correctly implemented it. Since the assessment framework utilized in D2.5 is structured around the four bioethical principles mentioned earlier, this outline will likewise adhere to the same categorization.

It must be clear though that being MES-CoBraD a project that bridges traditional healthcare themes with artificial intelligence, the choice of starting from the principles of bioethics should not be interpreted as cutting out the questions pertaining to artificial intelligence and exemplified into the HLEG guidelines and in the open issues listed in section 2.6 of the D2.3 deliverable, much of which have indeed been answered in the assessment made in the course of the D2.5 and especially of the ethical self-assessment questionnaire.

2.3.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS.

As mentioned before, for each of the four principles of bioethics (respect for persons, beneficence, non-maleficence, justice) a set of requirements was defined and then the PUCs #1 and #2 have been assessed against them. The first of those requirements regards the **respect of the patient's right to be adequately informed** and is thoroughly assessed in the D2.5 and D2.6 deliverables, where the procedures that are adopted at the project's level to ensure the respect of this requirement (in the D2.5) are described and are listed the actual informed consent procedures and documentation (in the D2.6). The ways fragile or vulnerable patients are protected are also examined and assessed, as well as the absence of any undue pressure or constraints. Also, the possibility for the patients of having a continuous and satisfactory interaction with their doctors is enquired, and positively assessed. Of course, each clinical site has an **incidental findings policy** and **received approval from their respective IRB** (documented in D2.6, except for KCL as they received approval after the deliverable submission).

It is noted that all the aspects related to the **transparency and explainability** have also been assessed, at least in this first round of the PUCs assessment, under this macro-principle. In particular the clinician (but indirectly also the patient) has the right to access the data on the basis of which the expert system delivered a certain output and to know how the algorithm proceeded. One first answer to this issue is already available, as the **human intervention** in the operation of the MES-CoBraD expert system is quite intensive (as the clinician decides which datasets, variables, functions and flowcharts to use) but more questions on transparency and explainability have been asked in the second ethical questionnaire (that will constitute one of the bases for the deliverable D2.8, the v2 of the PUCs evaluation), more focused on the role and impact of artificial intelligence inside the project.

This additional assessment is necessary because compliance with these requirements was initially assessed solely by examining the official project requirements and architecture (along with the first ethics self-assessment questionnaire). However, in the second round of assessment, actual compliance with these requirements can be verified. Notably, the first version of the ethical self-assessment questionnaire

included a direct query on this aspect. Partners responded that, accordingly to the requirement of explainable AI, **the system features a reporting and analytics tool** that can provide accurate results and explain the output of all workflows based on input values. Patients will receive **dedicated time** with a researcher who will explain the system's output to them. However, patients will not have direct access to the system's output.

Most partners also stated that they believe the interaction with the expert system does not impede **clinicians' autonomy**, as **clinicians are always considered responsible and accountable**, even when their decisions are based on the expert system's output. Partners perceive no difference between clinical practice using the MES-CoBraD platform and normal clinical practice regarding transparency; the use of the system does not diminish transparency compared to traditional clinical practice. Nonetheless, this issue will be examined in further detail in the second version of the ethical questionnaire, which is focused more on the artificial intelligence aspects of the project.

It must be considered though that the way the system is designed should reasonably protect the clinicians against the risk of losing their autonomy, because there are many points in which their intervention and their interaction with the system is essential, and in which they take decisions and direct the operations of the system (for instance by deciding which datasets to use, or designing the workflows to be run), so **they are in no way passive users of something that happens out of their control**. Besides, the expert system is conceived simply as a **decision support tool**, but it will never, under any circumstances make autonomous decisions. In this sense, the question about the opportunity of forbidding the usage of the system in certain circumstances also loses its sense, as the clinician will evaluate its utility and applicability case by case.

2.3.2 BENEFICENCE

Similarly, an analogous procedure to the one described above for the principle of respect for persons was established for the principle of beneficence: a set of requirements was outlined and subsequently verified for compliance (refer to deliverables D2.5 and D2.6 for comprehensive results). In medical ethics, the principle of beneficence is primarily understood as ensuring that medical interventions (including participation in clinical research with a scientific component) would be **beneficial for individual participants** or for the same cohort of participants—namely, individuals in similar conditions or suffering from the same ailment—and that **any potential burdens arising from the intervention do not outweigh the benefits**. This aspect was meticulously evaluated in deliverable D2.5, which **delineates how participation in MES-CoBraD research directly or indirectly benefits patients**.

In the second version of the ethical questionnaire, inquiries are more focused on the utilization of the MES-CoBraD expert system in clinical practice. Partners are **asked regarding whether there exists a well-defined process to monitor whether the AI system is meeting the intended goals**, or to ascertain **if the research is aligning with actual patient and stakeholder demands and needs**—rather than, for instance, solely catering to scientific curiosity or solely benefiting clinicians. This represents a more expansive interpretation of the principle of beneficence, one that is particularly crucial to assess when dealing with artificial intelligence in healthcare. The complete set of questions from the two ethical questionnaires (one for technical partners and one for clinical partners), along with partners' responses, will be detailed in deliverable D2.8.

2.3.3 NON-MALEFICENCE

Regarding the respect of the non-maleficence principle, measures have been put in place (see D2.5, D2.6 and Data Management Plan) to:

- Protect the **vulnerable and/or fragile** participants.
- Prevent **data breaches and/or misuses** and protect the system **against cyberattacks**.

- **Prevent incompetent usage** and the potential damages resulting from it (even though this question is furtherly assessed in D2.8 deliverable and in the related ethical questionnaire)
- Guard the patient against the possibility of **algorithmic error** and to **ensure the validation of the ES outputs** (and again, more on this in deliverable D2.8)

Partners also answered affirmatively about the existence of **an incidental findings policy and a risk assessment document** per site.

There exists a **significant risk of intentional misuse of the system**, exemplified by practices like social scoring. This point is examined in greater detail in deliverable D3.9 (ETHAI model), where specific requirements are outlined. However, while the risk exists, **the mitigation should occur at the policy level**, preempting any usage that could lead to such consequences. Implementing limitations on accesses and a establishing a logging system could serve as potential partial solutions. Moreover, as it is stated in D2.5, **MES-CoBraD adopts a de-personalization protocol** regarding data, ensuring that individuals cannot be traced back starting from the data available in MES-CoBraD.

2.3.4 JUSTICE

Justice in this context entails **equitable distribution of benefits and burdens resulting from the research**, ensuring also that no social group is **excluded or disproportionately advantaged** within the MES-CoBraD project. One approach to achieving this outcome is by scrutinising the **group composition** of research participants, which should be balanced and formulated based on purely scientific criteria.

Group composition is in fact a potential source of bias, and **biases on their turn are one of major sources of unfairness** (for a classification of possible biases refer to deliverable D2.3); similarly, the same may happen **if biases are introduced at the algorithmic level**, resulting in systematic error or in results whose reliability is not granted.

These concerns have already been examined in deliverable D2.5, where compliance with KPIs regarding group composition and the implementation of debiasing measures has been assessed. However, conclusive evidence has not been reached during that assessment, given the project's ongoing phase at the time. In deliverable D2.8, these aspects will be further scrutinized, evaluating the attainment of KPIs related to group composition and elucidating the measures taken for **de-biasing** purposes. Additionally, the **reliability and reproducibility of the system** will be considered, with a particular emphasis on automatic reporting of any issues and the reliability (or lack thereof) of system outputs.

Extremely important here is also the effort made to prevent the misuse of MES-CoBraD for prioritizing diagnoses or treatments for specific groups or for purposes diverging from purely clinical objectives. As previously mentioned, such a risk exists, and the possible mitigation measures are stated in D2.5 and will be outlined in D2.8 and D3.9.

3 THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORK IN MES-COBRAD

This section informs the consortium on the applicable laws applicable to MES-CoBraD, both with regards to its activities involving human participants and also in relation to the development and design of the MES-CoBraD platform.

This second version of the deliverable incorporates an update on the applicable secondary law, with specific reference to the recently adopted Data Act, Data Governance Act, and the Artificial Intelligence Act. This section also incorporates a reference to cybersecurity law in the EU. In addition it has also incorporate a section dealing with the Medical Device Regulation.

3.1 PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION AS FUNDAMENTAL RIGHT

The right to privacy and data protection are two different rights but their evolution is closely interlinked. The right to respect private life appeared for the first time in 1948 with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)³¹ and two years later in the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)³².

The legal formulation of the concept of privacy is broadly attributed to the work of the American lawyers Samuel Warren and Louis Brandeis in 1890.³³ In Europe, the typification of a right to privacy is often claimed to appear as a reaction to the abuses of totalitarian states before and during the WWII, thus, as a vertical and negative freedom for citizens against the interferences by the State.

The computerization of society in the 60's and 70's, particularly in the United States, led to the development of a new conceptualization of the right under the notion of informational privacy.³⁴ Based on the US pioneering work, the 1970's turned into a fertile ground for European legislation on how public authorities and private entities dealt with data and computers. Through the years, the expansion of concept has led several authors to develop theoretical frameworks to explain what actually privacy is.³⁵

The German federal Land of Hessen was the first to pass European legislation on data protection (Datenschutz). Not much later, national laws of Sweden (1973), Germany (1977), and France (1978) would follow it, establishing the foundries of what later became EU's right data protection³⁶. In order to harmonize the blossoming number of national laws, the 80's contemplated several supranational and international attempts to shape and control data protection. Of particular interest is the adoption of Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) guidelines in 1980³⁷, followed by the Council of Europe convention on automated processing in 1981(Convention 108)³⁸.

Soon after the Treaty on the European Union was adopted in October 1995³⁹, the European Parliament

³¹ United Nations (UN), Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 10 December 1948;

³² Council of Europe, European Convention on Human Rights, CETS No. 005, 1950..

³³ Samuel D. Warren & Louis D. Brandeis, *The Right to Privacy*, in *Harvard Law Review*, 1890, Vol. 4, No. 5, p 193-220.

³⁴ Alan F. Westin, *Privacy And Freedom*, 25 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 166 (1968).

³⁵ See Alan Westin's Four Privacy States, Roger Clarke's Classification, Anita Allen's "Unpopular Privacy," Finn, Wright, and Friedewald's Types of Privacy and Solove's categorisation of privacy theories. More recently, Bert Jaap Koops synthetised the theoretical production into his "typology of privacy." The two-dimensional model that consists of eight basic types of privacy (1. bodily, 2. intellectual, 3. spatial, 4. decisional, 5. communicational, 6. associational, 7. proprietary, and 8. behavioral privacy), with an overlay of a ninth type (9. informational privacy) overlapping, but not coinciding, with the former eight basic types. Bert-Jaap Koops et al., «A Typology of Privacy», SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 24 March 2016), <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2754043>

³⁶ G. González Fuster, 'The Beginning of EU Data Protection', in *The Emergence of Personal Data Protection as a Fundamental Right of the EU*, ed. Gloria González Fuster, Law, Governance and Technology Series (Cham: Springer International Publishing, .

³⁷ OECD, 1980 Guidelines Governing the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data. An updated version was adopted in 2013.

³⁸ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No. 08, 28 January 1981 ("Convention 108"), Also see TeNDER, p. 43.

³⁹ Treaty on the European Union

and the Council passed the Directive 95/46/EC on Data Protection⁴⁰. The Directive had per objective the harmonisation and protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons in respect of processing activities and to ensure the free flow of personal data between member states.

Through the years, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) case law has discussed, shaped, and clarified many aspects involving data protection. Notably, under the checks and balance formula in article 52(1) the Court has consistently defended that the respect for private life is not an absolute right, but that instead, needs balancing among other competing rights and interests. At the same time, the Court has clarified that the ECHR does not only prohibit interfering with rights, but, in certain circumstances, also actively acts to protect them.

At the EU level, the adoption of the EU Charter in 2000, consecrated in its article 8, the right to data protection as an autonomous fundamental right. In this regard, it should be noted that the notion of fundamental rights is a genuine legal construct of the EU. The founding treaties of the European Communities did not have any reference to them. Originally, human rights, as they were understood in the United Nations or Council of Europe framework were regarded as a strange body to the economic integration and internal market. Today fundamental rights are claimed to be a defining element of the EU evolution into an international organization with its own and unitary legal system.⁴¹ In its permanent evolution, the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU) continues to clarify the scope and normative role of data protection a fundamental right.

The overlapping scopes between the fundamental rights to privacy and the right to data protection are still a matter of debate today. The blurriness of their respective limits has enabled some positions to defend the autonomous character of data protection and others to understand it as an integral part of privacy.⁴²

3.2 COUNCIL OF EUROPE AND DATA PROTECTION

3.2.1 THE EUROPEAN CONVENTION ON HUMAN RIGHTS, ARTICLE 8

At the level of the Council of Europe, the right to personal data, protection falls under the scope of article 8 of the ECHR, which guarantees the right to respect for private and family life, home, and correspondence.

Right to respect for private and family life, home and correspondence Article 8 of the ECHR	1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. 2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified. 3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.
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Paragraph 2 of article 8 lays down those cases when restrictions to the right are permitted. This is the case when an interference with the right occurs “in accordance with the law and is necessary for a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety, or the economic well-being of the country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others (Article 8(2) ECHR).

⁴⁰ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and the free flow of such data.

⁴¹ P. P. Craig and G. De Búrca, eds., *The Evolution of EU Law*, 2nd ed (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 2011).

⁴² S. Rodotà, ‘Data Protection as a Fundamental Right’, in *Reinventing Data Protection?*, ed. Serge Gutwirth et al. (Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2009), 77–82, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9498-9_3.

3.2.2 CONVENTION 108 AND THE MODERNISED CONVENTION 108+

The Convention 108 of 28 January 1981 is the first legally binding international instrument in the data protection field. All forty-seven countries of the Council of Europe are parties. It applies to data processing conducted by both the private and public sectors, including data processing by the judiciary branch and law enforcement authorities.⁴³

The Convention 108 is not subject to the judicial supervision of the ECtHR but has been taken into consideration in the case law of the ECtHR within the context of Article 8 of the ECHR ⁴⁴.

In 2018, the Convention was modernised (Convention 108+)⁴⁵ to respond to the new challenges of the digital era, the globalisation of processing operations, and to allow safer exchanges of personal data. ⁴⁶

3.3 EUROPEAN UNION DATA PROTECTION LAW

EU law is composed by primary law (treaties) and secondary law (Regulations, Directives, and Decisions). The EU constitutional provisions on data protection are provided under the Charter of Fundamental Rights (Charter)⁴⁷ and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)⁴⁸.

Primary Law

The TFEU also known as the treaty of Lisbon, entered into force in 2009 it recognized for the first time that EU policies impacted EU citizens' rights which led to the approval of the Charter of Fundamental Rights in 2000. The text only became legally binding in 2009 as primary law, with the entry into force of the TFEU, and it in its article 16 grants the competence to the EU in order to legislate on data protection matters.⁴⁹

Article 8 of the Charter establishes the right to protect personal data as a separate from the right for respect to private and family life (Article 7 of the Charter):

Article 8 of the Charter	<p>1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.</p> <p>2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.</p> <p>3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.</p>
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Under the EU law, fundamental rights are not absolute, this means that they can be interfered or limited provided if certain conditions are observed. Following the balancing formula set by the ECHR, Article 52(1) of the Charter identifies the conditions under which the right may be limited, namely when:

- i. It is provided for in law,
- ii. Respects the essence of those rights and freedoms,
- iii. It is proportional and necessary, and
- iv. Meets the objective of general interests recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others.

⁴³ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law.

⁴⁴ ECtHR, Zv. Finland, N° 22009/93, 22 February 1997.

⁴⁵ CoE, Convention 108 + Convention for the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data (2018);

⁴⁶ CoE (2018) Brief overview of the Council of Europe standards and activities in the field of data protection

⁴⁷ European Parliament, Council and Commission, Charter on Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 7 December 2000 ("Charter").

⁴⁸ EU, Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, 25 March 1957 (and as amended) ("TFEU"),

⁴⁹ ibid

The connection between the Council of Europe and the EU interpretation of the rights is set in Article 52(3) of the Charter, which establishes that when the Charter contains an equivalent right in the ECHR, “the meaning and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention.”⁵⁰

3.3.1 SECONDARY LAW

The rules governing the processing of personal data in the field of healthcare are not limited to the GDPR but must also be read in line with other pieces of legislation. In that sense the new generation of “data laws”, represented by the Data Governance Act, the Data Act, the first attempt to legislate Artificial Intelligence, the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR), the In Vitro Diagnostic Devices Regulation (IVDR), as well as cybersecurity provisions of the NIS1 and NIS2 Directives, conform altogether, a complex and interrelated new legislative mosaic.

Heated discussions have followed the adoption of the DGA and the Data Act and its use of terminology that seems to be at odds with that established by the GDPR. In that sense both instruments have been said to promote a new alternative to the “rigid” dualism between the regulation of personal and non-personal data set by the GDPR.⁵¹ On this issue doubts have already been raised with regards the use and assessment of mixed datasets, containing both types of data. Similarly, the potential overlap of the newly adopted Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA), with existing legal regimes has raised the questions among stakeholders.⁵² From a data protection perspective, the EDPB⁵³ and more recently the EDPS⁵⁴, have already expressed their concerns with regards to the interplay of certain elements of the AIA and data protection laws. In the case of AI in health, potential conflicts with the Medical Device Regulation have also been identified.⁵⁵ These aspects will need to be closely monitored by providers AI systems before putting the platform into service.

Overall, the future data protection landscape of Healthcare in the EU will need to look beyond the GDPR. As expressed, the Data Governance Act, the Data Act, the AIA, the NIS2 as well as the Medical Device Regulation must be considered. A framework that soon will also include the proposed Health Data Space Regulation⁵⁶.

Requests of further clarity on how the new framework will operate, is needed in particular with regards to cybersecurity, privacy, and safety concerns.⁵⁷ This section has been updated to outline this new scenario and inform on the main features of these instruments.

3.3.1.1 EU: The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the main legal instrument governing the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data and the free flow of such data. The GDPR

⁵⁰ EU Charter article 52: “Any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others. [...]3. In so far as this Charter contains rights that correspond to rights guaranteed by the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the meaning, and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention. This provision shall not prevent Union law from providing more extensive protection.”

⁵¹ ‘The Data Act: A (Slippery) Third Way beyond Personal/Non-Personal Data Dualism?’, European Law Blog (blog), 4 May 2023,

⁵² COCIR (2021), ‘Analysis on AI in Medical Device Legislation’,

⁵³ EDPB-EDPS (2021) Joint Opinion 5/2021 on the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence.

⁵⁴ EDPS (2023) Opinion 44/2023 on the Proposal for Artificial Intelligence Act in the light of legislative developments,

⁵⁵ COCIR (2024) recommendations on the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) ‘s alignment with the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR).

⁵⁶ European Commission, (2022) Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space,

⁵⁷ idem

became fully enforceable in the European Union in May 2018 in replacement of Directive 95/46/EC.⁵⁸

The GDPR applies to the “processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system”.⁵⁹ It applies to processing activities carried out by individuals, companies, or organizations of personal data relating to individuals in the EU. Based on the principle of extraterritoriality, the GDPR applies to the data of EU residents regardless of whether or not the data processing takes place in the EU (Article 3(2) of the GDPR). Importantly, the regulation only covers the processing of personal data, this means that it does not apply to non-personal data or to the processing of personal data of deceased persons or of legal entities nor to data not considered as personal. Also, under the household exemption, its provisions do not apply to data processing by an individual for purely personal reasons or for activities carried out in one’s home provided there is no connection to a professional or commercial activity.

Differently from Directives, Regulations are legal instruments directly applicable to all Member States, however, as indicated in recital 10, the GDPR still needs to be transposed into the national laws, thus offering a certain margin of discretion.⁶⁰ This means that Member States might for instance subject certain aspects of a processing activities to stricter rules in their national laws than those foreseen in the GDPR.⁶¹ This is the case of the processing of health data where further national conditions might exist, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health.⁶²

3.3.1.2 Data Governance Act

The Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance (hereinafter DGA)⁶³ was proposed by the European Commission in November 2020 and it is applicable since September 2023.

The DGA pursues four main goals: 1) lay down conditions for the re-use, within the Union, of categories or data held by public sector bodies. 2) establish a notification and supervisory framework for the provision of data intermediation services; 3) create a framework for voluntary registration of entities collecting, and processing data made available for altruistic purposes and 4) lay down a framework for the establishment of a European Data Innovation Board (Article 1(1) of the DGA).

Under the term “data altruism” the DGA aims to promote the sharing of data among the public sector bodies (Article 2(16) of the DGA). Acknowledging the existence of vast amounts of data protected by third-party rights (such as trade secrets, personal data or intellectual property), the DGA aims to allow the use of “non-personal data” altruistically (i.e. without remuneration) for the purpose of improving public services (Article 25 of the DGA). The DGA encourages the concept of data altruism, where individuals and companies can voluntarily share their data for the common good, including health-related research and innovation, without seeking rewards. This altruistic sharing aims to accelerate medical advancements by

⁵⁸ Directive (EU) 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (“EU Directive 95/46/EC”).

⁵⁹ Article 2(1) of the GDPR.

⁶⁰ Recital 10 of the GDPR. See also European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law,

⁶¹ Art 9(4) of the GDPR means that harmonisation in the area of health data will be limited. In the specific case of genetic data, biometric data, or data concerning health, article 9(4) of the GDPR contemplates the possibility that the Member States maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to their processing. Also, Member States can introduce derogations in the context of processing activities for scientific or historical purposes from data subjects’ rights (Article 89 of the GDPR).

⁶² Article 9(4) of the GDPR

⁶³ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act).

making valuable data more accessible to researchers and healthcare professionals.⁶⁴

The DGA foresees the need to attach stricter conditions to certain types of non-personal data which are identified as “highly sensitive” (Article 5(13) of the DGA. Explicit reference is made to datasets held in the public health system, such as public hospitals. The Act delegates the definition of the conditions to Union Law, with a reference to the future Health Data Space Regulation.

While it does not elaborate further, it mentions that such conditions, should be “proportionate, non-discriminatory and necessary to protect legitimate Union public policy objectives identified, such as the protection of public health, safety, the environment, public morality, consumer protection, privacy and personal data protection” (Recital 24 of the DGA).

The personal scope of the DGA distinguishes between data subjects, data holders and data users and define them as follows:

- › **Data subject:** means data subject as referred to in Article 4, point (1), of Regulation (EU) 2016/679; (Article 2 (7) of the Data Governance Act)
- › **Data holder:** means a legal person, including public sector bodies and international organisations, or a natural person who is not a data subject with respect to the specific data in question, which, in accordance with applicable Union or national law, has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data; (Article 2 (8) of the Data Governance Act)
- › **Data user:** means a natural or legal person who has lawful access to certain personal or non-personal data and has the right, including under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in the case of personal data, to use that data for commercial or non-commercial purposes; (Article 2 (9) of the Data Governance Act)

Finally, a clear focus of the DGA is put on “Data intermediation services” (Article 2(11) of the DGA). These new services seek to establish commercial relationships for the purposes of “data sharing between an undetermined number of data subjects and data holders on the one hand and data users on the other, through technical, legal, or other means, including for the purpose of exercising the rights of data subjects in relation to personal data.

3.3.1.3 The Data Act

The Regulation 2023/2854 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (hereinafter Data Act), was proposed on 23 February 2022 and entered into force on 11 January 2024.⁶⁵ The new regulation seeks to remove “barriers to access to consumer and business data” and promote innovation by business and public authorities.⁶⁶

The scope of the Data Act is broad, it proposes rules governing the making available of a) product data and related service data to the user of the connected product or related service; b) data by data holders to data recipients; c) data by data holders to public sector bodies; as well a d) facilitating switching between data processing services; e) introducing safeguards against unlawful third-party access to non-personal data; and f) the development of interoperability standards for data to be accessed, transferred and used. (Article 1(1) of the Data Act).

The Data Act covers the sharing of **personal and non-personal data** generated by connected products or

⁶⁴ Summary of the Regulation (EU) 2022/868 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act).

⁶⁵ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act)

⁶⁶ *Idem* Recital 4

related services to ensure fairness in data sharing contracts and to allow public sector institutions to use data held by enterprises where an exceptional need arises.⁶⁷ Examples of the data covered are any connected physical product that generates or collects data concerning its use or environment (i.e. IoT products) which includes medical devices and other health devices, such as monitors, wearables, trackers, sensors MRI or X-ray scanners.⁶⁸ In that way, the Data Act expands individuals' data access rights to data generated by connected objects in the hands of private companies.

The Regulation also introduces new rules aimed at facilitating the exchange of cloud services providers and other data processing services and establishes safeguards against illegal international data transfers by these cloud service providers.⁶⁹

With regards to healthcare, the personal scope of the Data Act might apply to the users of medical devices and other health devices, the holders of connected medical devices' and connected health devices' data and the recipients of such data:

- › **Data subject:** means data subject as referred to in Article 4, point (1), of Regulation (EU) 2016/679
- › **User:** means a natural or legal person that owns a connected product or to whom temporary rights to use that connected product have been contractually transferred, or that receives related services; (Article 2 (12) of the Data Act)
- › **Data holder:** means a natural or legal person that has the right or obligation, in accordance with this Regulation, applicable Union law or national legislation adopted in accordance with Union law, to use and make available data, including, where contractually agreed, product data or related service data which it has retrieved or generated during the provision of a related service. (Article 2 (13) of the Data Act)
- › **Data recipient:** means a natural or legal person, acting for purposes which are related to that person's trade, business, craft or profession, other than the user of a connected product or related service, to whom the data holder makes data available, including a third party following a request by the user to the data holder or in accordance with a legal obligation under Union law or national legislation adopted in accordance with Union law (Article 2 (14) of the Data Act)

The concepts of "user" and "data holder" should not be confused with the concepts of "controller", "processor" and "data subject" under the GDPR. In that sense, when processing personal data, data holders can be data controllers (but not necessarily). Similarly "users" does not necessarily equate to "data subject".

3.3.1.4 Proposal for a Health Space Regulation

The European Commission proposed the European Health Data Space (EHDS) in 2022 to enhance care delivery and improve patients' lives by offering all EU citizens control over their personal health data in a private and secure environment. The goal is to eliminate information barriers and establish a single market for digital health services.⁷⁰

More specifically, the EHDS aims to enable EU citizens to provide health professionals throughout the EU

⁶⁷ In this respect the EDPB notes that the use of concepts such as "product" or expressions such as "related services" will require greater precision. See 'EDPB-EDPS (2023) Joint Opinion 03/2022 on the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space'.

⁶⁸ See section 5 below.

⁶⁹ COCIR,(2023) 'Joint Medical Technology Industry Perspective on the Data Act'.

⁷⁰ 'Impact assessment report proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council on the European health data space', 2022.

with access to their personal health data via a digital interface. This system would streamline the use of health data for purposes like research, innovation, policy making, and regulatory tasks, all the while upholding complete adherence to the EU’s data protection standards⁷¹.

Article 2(2) of the proposal defines “personal electronic health data” as data concerning health and genetic data as defined in the GDPR, as well as data referring to determinants of health, or data processed in relation to the provision of healthcare services, processed in an electronic form.

The EDPB-EDPs points out a potential overlap with the reference in recital 35 of the GDPR which includes “information collected in the course of provision of health services”.⁷² More generally civil society has insisted on the need to bring the Commission’s proposal in alignment with data protection principles and fundamental rights.⁷³

3.3.1.5 Guidelines and authorities:

In addition to law, an important source of guidance when implementing data protection law are the opinions and recommendations of the EU independent bodies; the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB).

The EDPS is the EU’s independent data protection authority, entrusted with three main roles: i) supervision of the processing of personal data by EU Institutions and bodies; ii) advisory role for those entities on data protection matters, and iii) monitoring role with regards to new technologies involving data protection issues.

Meanwhile the EDPB is established by the GDPR as “an independent European body, which contributes to the consistent application of data protection rules throughout the European Union and promotes cooperation between the EU’s data protection authorities.”⁷⁴

The following opinions, guidelines, and codes issued by the EDPS and EDPB are relevant to the MES-CoBraD research.

Table 3 MES-CoBraD institutional guidelines and opinions on data protection

OPINIONS	
EDPS, 2020	A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research, Adopted on 6 January 2020
EDPB, 2021	Response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research, Adopted on 2 February 2021
EC, Green paper SWD (2014)	European Commission Green Paper on mobile Health ("mHealth"), Adopted on 10 April 2014.
EDPB, 3/2019	EDPB Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection

⁷¹ Although concerns have been raised about the current iteration of the EHDS proposal, including its potential to exacerbate health inequalities instead of remedying them and potential changes to data-sharing practices, the concept of cybersecurity has received limited attention. See EDRI “Make the European Health Data Space serve patients and research”, 2022.

⁷² ‘EDPB-EDPS (2022) Joint Opinion 03/2022 on the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space’,.

⁷³ ‘Efpia-Ehds-Position on a European Health Data Space’,..2020

⁷⁴ Since the entry into force of the GDPR in 2018, the EDPB has replaced the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. EDPB, About EDPB (website), see https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb_en (last accessed on 20 February 2022).

	regulation (GDPR), Adopted on 23 January 2019.
EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 03/2022	EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 03/2022 on the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space. Adopted on 12 July 2022.
EDPS, 8/2020	Preliminary Opinion 8/2020 on the European Health Data Space
EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 1/2022	EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 1/2022 on the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/953 on a framework for the issuance, verification and acceptance of interoperable COVID-19 vaccination, test, and recovery certificates (EU Digital COVID Certificate) to facilitate free movement during the COVID- 19 pandemic. Adopted on 14 March 2022.
16 June 2020	Statement on the data protection impact of the interoperability of contact tracing apps
EDPB Opinion 2 February 2021	EDPB Document on response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research
EDPB Opinion 5/2019	Opinion 5/2019 on the interplay between the ePrivacy Directive and the GDPR, in particular regarding the competence, tasks and powers of data protection authorities. Adopted on 12 March 2019
EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 5/2021	EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 5/2021 on the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). Adopted on 18 June 2021
GUIDELINES	
17 April 2023	Guidelines 8/2022 on identifying a controller or processor’s lead supervisory authority Replaces previous opinion from 10 October 2022.
17 April 2023	Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights - Right of access
4 April 2023	Guidelines 9/2022 on personal data breach notification under GDPR Replaces previous guidelines from 10 October 2022: what are the main differences with respect to the previous. Explain how it has been dealt in MES-CoBrad and report on this
17 April 2023	Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights - Right of access
EDPB 04/2019,	EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default Adopted on 13 November 2019
EDPB, 1/2019	EDPB Guidelines 1/2019 on Codes of Conduct and Monitoring Bodies under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 12 February 2019
EDPB, 03/2020	EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak, Adopted on 21 April 2020
EDPB, 07/2020	EDPB Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, Adopted on 07 July 2021.

EDPB 01/2021	EDPB Guidelines 01/2021 on Examples regarding Data Breach Notification, Adopted on 19 January 2021.
EDPB 10/2020	EDPB Guidelines 10/2020 on restrictions under Article 23 GDPR, Adopted on 13 October 2021.
EDPB 05/2020	EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 4 May 2020.
WP251	Article 29 Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on October 2017, Endorsed by the EDPB.
WP259	Article WP29 Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 28 November 2017. Endorsed by the EDPB.
EDPB-EDPS, 5/2021	EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 5/2021 on the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). Adopted on 18 June 2021
AEPD-EDPS	10 misunderstandings related to anonymisation, Adopted on 27 April 2021
EDPB 3/2019	EDPB Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR), Adopted on 23 January 2019
RECOMMENDATIONS	
18 June 2021	Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data
Recommendation No. R (97)	Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers, Recommendation No. R (97) 5 on the Protection of Medical Data. Adopted on 13 February 1997.
CM/Rec (2019)2	Council of Europe Recommendation CM/Rec (2019)2 of the Committee of Ministers to member States on the protection of health-related data, Adopted on 27 March 2019
EDBP, R01/2020	Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data (Version 2.0), Adopted on 18 June 2021

3.3.2 MEMBER STATES' AND THIRD COUNTRIES' DATA PROTECTION NORMATIVE FRAMEWORKS

Member States might establish derogations to the provisions in the GDPR by “determining more precisely specific requirements for the processing and other measures to ensure lawful and fair processing”.⁷⁵ As a result, it is necessary to take into account the particularities of applicable national laws in the different MES-CoBraD pilot sites.

The following subsection offers a brief summary of the relevant national legal frameworks given the locations of the parties involved in the project.

3.3.2.1 Spain

The Spanish implementation of the data protection regime is found in the Organic Law 3/2018 on the Protection of Personal Data and the Guarantee of Digital Rights (the Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de Protección

⁷⁵ Article 9(4) of the GDPR.

de Datos y Garantía de los Derechos Digitales), which entered into force in December 2018 ⁷⁶.

Regarding the processing of health data in the context of scientific research, a specific framework is developed in the “Additional Provision 17th (1) (2) of the same Organic Law 3/2018. Derogations to the processing of personal data can be found in sections c), d), f) and g), conditioned to the adoption of safeguards and the adoption of technical and organisational measures:

In addition, the Catalan Code of Conduct for the processing of personal data in the health sector ⁷⁷, applies as far as the MES-CoBraD partner is located in that territory. The code aims to create a common framework and unify the criteria in the implementation of data protection rules in the health sector. It establishes the measures and procedures to be followed by the controller and processors in the field of medical assistance and research activities (Article 112-1).

The data protection supervisory authority in Spain is Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD)⁷⁸. Autonomous territories also have their own supervisory authorities, as is the case of the Catalan Authority of Data Protection.⁷⁹

3.3.2.2 Italy

The Italian implementation of the data protection regime is found in the Legislative Decree no. 101 of 10 August 2018 (“The Decree”) and which entered into force in September 2018 ⁸⁰. There are a number of derogations from the GDPR included in the relevant Italian law, including with respect to processing of special categories of data ⁸¹. With regards to health data the Italian law in its article 2-septies (m) provides that the processing of genetic, biometric, and health data shall be carried out only if both the processing complies with Article 9(2) GDPR and certain security measures, such as encryption, pseudonymisation, and minimisation are implemented. The decree further allows personal data to be processed, stored, and transferred to another controller after the normal period for processing and even after the termination of the main processing if carried out for scientific, historical, or statistical purposes as well as archiving in the public interest. Guidance will be issued for the processing of personal data for this purpose, aiming to identify adequate guarantees for the rights and freedoms of the data subject in accordance with Article 89 GDPR ⁸².

The Data Protection Authority in Italy is the Garante per la protezione dei dati personali ⁸³.

Further guidance on the security measures on the processing of special categories of data will be to be indicated by the Garante every two years. Since the GDPR, the Garante has not adopted new safeguards. Until now, the Garante has updated the General Authorisation No. 8/2016 on processing of genetic data (section 5.7) and issued further several guidelines and opinions on the processing of data concerning health, biometric and genetic data.⁸⁴

3.3.2.3 Greece

In Greece, the national implementation of the GDPR, the Greek Data Protection Act (Greek DPA)⁸⁵, applies

⁷⁶ See Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Spain) (“GDPR Tracker Spain”)

⁷⁷ Codi de Conducta per al tractament de dades personals en l'àmbit sanitari

⁷⁸ Agencia Española protección de Datos <https://www.aepd.es/es>

⁷⁹ Autoritat Catalana Protecció de Dades

⁸⁰ The Decree did not repeal the Italian Data Protection Act but rather amended any provisions of the act conflicting with the GDPR .See Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Italy) (“GDPR Tracker Italy”)

⁸¹ *ibid*

⁸² *ibid*

⁸³ Garante; <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/> (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

⁸⁴ IDPA, General Application Order Concerning Biometrics as of November, 2014,

⁸⁵ Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDP), measures for implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data, and

to the processing of healthcare data, with important foundations for the processing of personal data in the context of healthcare and medical research in the Code of Medical Ethics.⁸⁶ The Code describes the patients' right to receive all necessary information regarding their health status as well as their right not to know.

All patients' personal data are protected under the obligation of medical confidentiality, and those which must be processed for health-related purposes such as the age, sex, address, and medical history of patients are extensively described in the Code.

The processing of health-related data for scientific research purposes is permitted under the condition of existing safeguards, including DPO appointment, encryption of data, and restriction on data-by-data controllers and processors and requires the data subject's explicit consent.

As an exemption to the general rule of informed consent, Art. 9(1) GDPR, the data controller may further process Health data for research purposes if the controller can prove its competing interest in processing such data against the interest of the data subjects in not having their data processed. In the latter case, the data controller must take appropriate and specific measures (Art. 30(1) Law 4624/ 2019)⁸⁷. This appears as the only possibility for an exemption to process special data categories based on other legal grounds than consent for scientific research purposes. In all cases, the research carried by the partner must be approved by the competent scientific council and the bioethics committee (Art. 24(2)(d) Law 3418/2005 and Art. 23 Law 4521/2018)⁸⁸.

The Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa) is a constitutionally consolidated independent Authority ⁸⁹.

3.3.2.4 Sweden

The Sweden's Personal Data Act (1998:204) was repealed in May 2018 and replaced by the Swedish Data Protection Act (2018:218) and the Swedish Data Protection Regulation (2018:219) to govern alongside the EU's GDPR.⁹⁰

The data privacy legislation regulates data protection principles, the legal bases for processing personal data, rules around special category data, and transparency requirements.

The Personal Data Act paragraph 3(7) indicates that sensitive personal data can be processed according to the GDPR Art. 9(2)(j) if the processing is necessary for statistical purposes and the public interest, for the statistics project for which the processing takes place, clearly outweighs the risk for unfair infringement of the individuals' integrity that the processing may cause.⁹¹ There is specific legislation with regards to patient data, the Patient Data Act (2008:355) which provides further conditions for the processing of personal data in health care. ⁹²

transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, and other provisions, Law 4624/2019 (Government Gazette, Series A, Issue N 137, p. 3379).

⁸⁶ Code of Medical Deontology, Law 3418/2005 (Government Gazette, Series A, Issue N. 287, p. 5391).

⁸⁷ Law No. 4624 Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa), measures for implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data, and transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, and other provisions.

⁸⁸ Supra

⁸⁹ Hellenic Data Protection authority.

⁹⁰ See Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Italy) ("GDPR Tracker Sweden")

⁹¹ GDPR Tracker Sweden

⁹² Patient Data Act 2008,

3.3.3 THIRD COUNTRIES

3.3.3.1 UK

The UK's data protection framework is currently regulated by the Data Protection Act 2018, which incorporates the EU GDPR and supplements its provisions.⁹³ The Data Protection Act 2018 focuses significantly on data subject rights, "special category" personal data, data protection fees, data protection offenses, consent from children, and enforcement. While the UK is no longer be an EU member state as of March 29, 2019, to this day there has been no update with regard to its existing data privacy laws.

Furthermore, as a signatory to the Convention 108 of the Council of Europe, the exception provided for in Article 2(8)(1) of the aforementioned regulations, which allows cross-border transfers, would continue to apply to the UK.⁹⁴

The Medical Research Council is responsible for co-coordinating and funding medical research in the UK. With regards to the legal basis for processing special categories of data, it has advised against the use of consent as an adequate legal basis arguing⁹⁵ that the 'GDPR's consent requirements do not often apply to research.⁹⁶

3.3.3.2 Israel

Data protection in Israel is governed primarily by the Protection of Privacy Law, 5741-1981 ('the Privacy Law')⁹⁷ and the Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty, 5752-1992⁹⁸. The latter sets out the fundamental rights of privacy whereas the former focuses on the protection of personal data and information.⁹⁹

Guidelines on data protection issues are provided by the Israeli regulator, the Privacy Protection Authority ('PPA') (formerly known as the Israel Law, Information, and Technology Authority ("ILITA"))¹⁰⁰. With regards to data referring to a patient's physical or mental health, or data about his\her medical treatment, these are not defined in the Privacy Law, but in the Patient's Rights Law, 5756-1996.¹⁰¹

In terms of privacy protection regulation relating to the transfer of personal information to databases outside State Borders, 5761-2001 sets out the conditions for data retention and use applying to a database located in Israel (section 2(4) of the Regulation).

3.4 EUROPEAN UNION CYBERSECURITY

Today the term cybersecurity is colloquially defined as "the state of being protected against the criminal or unauthorized use of electronic data, or the measures taken to achieve this" or as the "measures taken

⁹³ EDPB (2021) Opinion 14/2021 regarding the European Commission Draft Implementing Decision pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the adequate protection of personal data in the United Kingdom, section 2.1.

⁹⁴ See Opinion regarding the continuation of cross-border transfers of personal data, from Israeli based organizations to UK based organizations post Brexit, available at https://www.gov.il/en/departments/publications/reports/gb_personaldata (Last accessed 18 January 2022)

⁹⁵ This is supported by the UK Medical Research Council, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): Consent in Research and Confidentiality: Guidance Note 3 (March 2018, updated May 2018).

⁹⁶ UK Medical Research Council, GDPR and Data Protection Act 2018: Key Facts for Research (13 June 2018),

⁹⁷ Protection of Privacy Law, 5741-1981- unofficial translation

⁹⁸ Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty, 5752-1992,)

⁹⁹ See ICLG, Digital health laws and regulations 2022,

¹⁰⁰ Privacy Protection Authority, available https://www.gov.il/he/Departments/the_privacy_protection_authority, (last accessed 21 March 2022)

¹⁰¹ Available in Hebrew: https://www.health.gov.il/LegislationLibrary/Zchuyot_01.pdf (last accessed 21 March 2022)

to protect a computer or computer system (as on the Internet) against unauthorized access or attack”.¹⁰²

From a technical perspective, in 2008, the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) defined cybersecurity as “The collection of tools, policies, security concepts, security safeguards, guidelines, risk management approaches, actions, training, best practices, assurance and technologies that can be used to protect the cyber environment and organization and user’s assets”.¹⁰³

In 2012, the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) together with the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), founded a Joint Technical Committee and defined it as the “Preservation of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information in the Cyberspace”, where cyberspace was conceptualised as “the complex environment resulting from the interaction of people, software and services on the Internet by means of technology devices and networks connected to it, which does not exist in any physical form”.¹⁰⁴

The same ISO/IEC would two years later develop the different components of its definition as follows:

- Information security: Preservation of confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information
 - Confidentiality: Property that information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorized individuals, entities, or processes
 - Integrity: Property of accuracy and completeness
 - Availability: Property of being accessible and usable upon demand by an authorized entity
- cybersecurity

In 2015 the European Union Agency for Cyber Security (ENISA) in an attempt to capture a definition of the term, ended up concluding that “ cybersecurity is an enveloping term and it is not possible to make a definition to cover the extent of the things Cybersecurity covers”.¹⁰⁵ Ultimately ENISA presented a collection of the most used conceptualisations and recommended stakeholders and policymakers to choose the most appropriate definition based on their needs and context.

The following subsections present the legislation most relevant to the MES-CoBraD platform with regards to cybersecurity.

3.4.1 NIS1

The Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union (hereinafter: NIS Directive) was adopted on 16 July 2016.¹⁰⁶

The NIS Directive represented an important milestone for the EU cybersecurity policy in three main ways. First it required Member States to adapt their national laws to EU cybersecurity agenda, recognizing the cross-border nature of cybersecurity and establishing coordination and cooperation mechanisms across the EU. Second it increased cooperation between Member States at Union level by setting up various fora facilitating the exchange of strategic and operational information. Third, improved “cyber-resilience” of public and private entities in seven sectors, that due to their importance need are regarded as essential: 1) energy; 2) transport; 3) banking; 4) financial market infrastructures; 5) healthcare; 6) drinking water supplies and distribution and 7) digital infrastructures.

¹⁰² Merriam Webster dictionary, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/cybersecurity>

¹⁰³ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (EU body or agency) et al., *Definition of Cybersecurity: Gaps and Overlaps in Standardisation* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2015),

¹⁰⁴ ISO/IEC 27032:2012

¹⁰⁵ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (EU body or agency) et al., *Definition of Cybersecurity: Gaps and Overlaps in Standardisation* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2015),

¹⁰⁶ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union [2016] OJ L194/1 (hereinafter: NIS Directive).

In terms of scope, and as its title otherwise indicates, the NIS Directive lays down measures with a view to achieving a high common level of security of network and information systems within the Union, so as to improve the functioning of the internal market (Article 1(1) of the NIS Directive). However, the national transposition turned to be less uniform than expected, resulting in an irregular framework that evidenced the lack of readiness from those entities the Directive aimed to regulate.

Finally, it was considered that NIS did not adequately cover this increased interconnection and interdependence between sectors. The assessment of new threats and challenges, significantly stressed during the Covid-pandemic, resulted in the “general understanding” that the Directive was insufficient to face the new “cyber challenges” and that a repeal and replacement was needed.¹⁰⁷

3.4.2 NIS2

The Directive 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, (hereinafter the NIS2 Directive), was adopted on 14 December 2022, entering into force 20 days later. The deadline for its transposition is set for 17 October 2024, the moment at which measures in the Directive will be fully applicable and the NIS 1 Directive will be effectively repealed (Article 40 of the NIS2 Directive).

With a view of “ensuring a high common level of cybersecurity within the Union”, the NIS2 Directive lays down obligations on: a) Member States to adopt national cybersecurity strategies, designate competent national authorities, single points of contact and computer security incident response teams (CSIRTs); b) cybersecurity risk management and reporting obligations for entities of a type referred to as essential entities in Annex I and important entities in Annex II; c) obligations on cybersecurity information sharing. (Article 1(1) of the NIS2 Directive).

In terms of scope the difference between the NIS1 and NIS2 relies fundamentally in their conceptualization of “cybersecurity”. In that sense while the NIS1 focuses on the “security of network and information systems” the NIS2 understands it as “the activities necessary to protect network and information systems, the users of such systems, and other persons affected by cyber threats”.¹⁰⁸ As a result the objective is not only to protect networks but also “the users”.¹⁰⁹ The Directive applies to entities of any size insofar they belong to the sectors identified in Annex I and II (Article 2(1) of the NIS2 Directive). The fact that the Directive establishes a list of entities is a major change when compared to the directionality given to Member States in the NIS1.¹¹⁰

With regards to healthcare, the NIS2 considers as highly critical - in addition to clinics/hospitals - basic pharmaceutical product manufacturers, EU reference laboratories, critical medical device manufacturers, and R&D entities.

Article 21(2) identifies a non-exhaustive list cybersecurity risk management measure to be adopted by the entities under scope of the NIS2 including:

- a. policies on risk analysis and information system security.
- b. incident handling.
- c. business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management.
- d. supply chain security, including security-related aspects concerning the relationships between

¹⁰⁷ European Commission, ‘Impact Assessment Report Accompanying the document Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 – part 1’ SWD (2020) 345 final,13

¹⁰⁸ Article 32(1) of the Cybersecurity Act.

¹⁰⁹ Niels Vandezande, ‘Cybersecurity in the EU: How the NIS2-Directive Stacks up against Its Predecessor’, *Computer Law & Security Review* 52 (April 2024): 105890,

¹¹⁰ idem

- each entity and its direct suppliers or service providers.
- e. security in network and information systems acquisition, development, and maintenance, including vulnerability handling and disclosure.
 - f. policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures;
 - (g) basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training.
 - g. policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and, where appropriate, encryption.
 - h. human resources security, access control policies and asset management.
 - i. the use of multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, where appropriate.

As it can be observed from its provisions, the NIS2 stresses the need to limit the impact of incidents on users and not only on the provider of the service.¹¹¹ At the same time the NIS2 also emphasizes the accountability requirements of the targeted entities, requiring demonstration in their level of cybersecurity preparedness¹¹². This includes the need to exert due diligence in explaining the “entity’s supply chain of security” including their suppliers and IT service providers.¹¹³

Regarding incident notification, article 23 establishes an exhaustive list of guidelines according to which 'essential and important' entities must be notified with undue delay to national management bodies or the competent authority of any incident that has a significant impact on the provision of their services. In this respect, an incident shall be considered significant if (Article 23(3) of the NIS2 Directive):

- (a) it has caused or is capable of causing severe operational disruption of the services or financial loss for the entity concerned.
- (b) it has affected or is capable of affecting other natural or legal persons by causing considerable material or nonmaterial damage.

There are still doubts on how these reporting duties will interact with the reporting requirements set by the GDPR.¹¹⁴ Despite the NIS2 and the GDPR providing for different requirements with different objectives, certain overlap under both frameworks continue to occur. This is particularly relevant when it comes to reporting data breach incidents. Reporting obligations might present significant challenges, particularly in relation to early public disclosure of security breaches and their repercussions on incident response.¹¹⁵

In that regard, Schmitz-Berndt argues that concurrent application of Article 23 NIS2 and 33-34 GDPR could lead to premature public disclosure of significant incidents. Alternatively, Markopoulou, Papakonstantinou, and de Hert assert that concerns over the double reporting frameworks might be overstated, and that, if a conflict were to arise, it should be solved by reference to the different nature of

¹¹¹ Idem. See also Donald David Stewart Ferguson, ‘The outcome efficacy of the entity risk management requirements of the NIS 2 Directive’ [2023] *International Cybersecurity Law Review* 6

¹¹² Article 21 states that “Member States shall ensure that essential and important entities take appropriate and proportionate technical, operational and organisational measures to manage the risks posed to the security of network and information systems which those entities use for their operations or for the provision of their services, and to prevent or minimise the impact of incidents on recipients of their services and on other services”(Article 21 (1) of the NIS2 Directive). Also, the NIS2 Directive places a novel and heavy responsibility upon the CSIRT (national management bodies), including the obligation to approve risk-management measures or provide relevant training upon risk of being held liable for infringement (Article 20 of the NIS2 Directive).

¹¹³ Elisabetta Biasin, Erik Kamenja, ‘Cybersecurity of medical devices: new challenges arising from the AI Act and NIS 2 Directive proposals’ (2022) 3 *Int. Cybersecur. Law Rev.*166;

¹¹⁴ European Data Protection Supervisor, ‘Opinion 5/2021 on the Cybersecurity Strategy and the NIS 2.0 Directive’ (EDPS, 11 March 2021)

¹¹⁵ Sandra Schmitz and Stefan Schiffner, ‘Don’t tell them now (or at all) – responsible disclosure of security incidents under NIS Directive and GDPR’ (2021) 35:2 *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology* 101, 106-111

NIS2 and GDPR as legal instruments and their different protection goals.¹¹⁶

3.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT

The Regulation laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (hereinafter AIA), was proposed in April 2021 and adopted on the 13 March 2024.¹¹⁷ The AIA represents the first attempt to enact “horizontal regulation “over Artificial Intelligence in the EU. Adopting a risk-based approach, it lays down a classification for AI systems to which different requirements and obligations are associated.

According to the AIA, an AI system is “a machine-based system designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy, that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments” (Article 3(1) of the AIA).

Where risk is defined as “the combination of the probability of an occurrence of harm and the severity of harm (Article 3(2) of the AIA), the risk classification system requires that all AI systems are inventoried and assessed according one of the **three risk categories**:

Table 4 AI act risk categories

Prohibited AI practices- Unacceptable risk (Article 5 of the AI Act):

AI Systems posing an unacceptable risk to people’s safety, security, and fundamental rights. This AI systems are prohibited. Examples of prohibited AI systems are :

- a) AI systems that deploy **subliminal techniques** beyond a person’s consciousness or purposefully manipulative or deceptive techniques, with the objective, or the effect of , materially distorting the behaviour of a person or group of persons by appreciably impairing their ability to make an informed decision, thereby causing a person to take a decision that that person would not have otherwise taken in a manner that causes or is likely to cause that person, another person or group of persons significant harm.
- b) AI systems that **exploit vulnerabilities** of a person or a specific group of persons due to their age, disability or a specific social or economic situation, with the objective or the effect of, materially distorting the behaviour of that person, in a manner that causes or is reasonably likely to cause that person or another person significant harm.
- c) AI systems aimed at the **evaluation or classification of natural persons** or group of persons over certain period of time **based on their social behaviour** or known, inferred or predicted personal or personality characteristics, with the social score leading to : i) detrimental or unfavourable treatment in social context that are unrelated to the context which the data was originally collected; ii) detrimental or unfavourable treatment of certain natural persons that is unjustified or disproportionate to their social behaviour or its gravity.
- d) AI systems for making **risk assessments of natural persons** in order to assess or predict the likelihood of a natural person **committing a criminal offence**, based solely on the profiling of a natural person (..).
- e) AI systems that create or expand facial recognition databases through the **untargeted scrapping of facial images from the internet or CCTV footage**.
- f) AI Systems to **infer emotions of a natural person** in the areas of workplace

¹¹⁶ Dimitra Markopoulou, Vagelis Papanonstantinou and Paul de Hert, ‘The new EU cybersecurity framework: The NIS Directive, ENISA’s role and the General Data Protection Regulation’ (2019) 35 Computer Law & Security Review,

¹¹⁷ Note that at the time of writing the final text of then AI Act is still subject to a final lawyer-linguist check and is expected to be finally adopted before the end of the legislature (through the so-called corrigendum procedure). The law also needs to be formally endorsed by the Council. European Parliament 13 March 2024,

	<p>and education institutions, except in the case of medical or safety reasons.</p> <p>g) AI systems used to categorise individuals based on their biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinion, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs, sex life or sexual orientation. This prohibition does not cover labelling or filtering of lawfully acquired biometric datasets or categorizing of biometric data in the area of law enforcement.</p> <p>h) AI systems used for real time remote biometric identification systems in publicly available spaces for the purposes of law enforcement.</p>
<p>High-risk AI systems (Article 6-27 of the AI Act):</p>	<p>AI systems are considered to be high-risk where both of the following conditions are fulfilled: a) Fall under the scope of EU harmonising legislation under Annex I and/or Annex III of the AI Act.; b) The product, is required to undergo a third-party conformity assessment, with a view to the placing on the market or the putting into service of that product pursuant to the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex I.</p> <p>In line with a risk-based approach, those high-risk AI systems might be permitted on the European market subject to compliance with certain mandatory requirements and an ex-ante conformity assessment.:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Risk management system (Art 9 of the AI Act) 2) Data and data governance (Art 10 of the AI Act) 3) Technical documentation (Art 11 of the AI Act) 4) Record keeping (Art 12 of the AI Act) 5) Transparency and provision of information to deployers (Article 13 of the AI Act) 6) Human oversight (Article 14 of the AI Act) 7) Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity (Article 15 of the AI Act). <p>The classification of an AI system as high-risk is based on the intended purpose of the AI system, in line with existing product safety legislation. Therefore, the classification as high-risk does not only depend on the function performed by the AI system, but also on the specific purpose and modalities for which that system is used.¹¹⁸</p>
<p>Limited risks: (Recital 53 of the AI Act)</p>	<p>AI systems that pose a limited risk are those that do not lead to a significant risk of harm to the legal interest protected because they do not materially influence the decision-making or do not harm those interests substantially.</p> <p>This would be the case of AI systems that “do not have an impact on the substance, and thereby the outcome, of decision-making, whether human or automated”. To fall under such description recital 53 establishes four conditions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The AI system is intended to perform a narrow procedural task: Examples are transformation of unstructured data into structured data, classification of incoming documents into categories, or detection of duplicates. 2) The task performed by the AI system is intended to improve the result of a previously completed human activity that may be relevant for the purposes of that list. The AI system only provides an additional layer to a human activity with consequently lowered risk: Examples are AI systems aimed at improving language used in drafted documents. 3) The AI system is intended to detection-decision making patterns or deviations from prior decision-making patterns. In this case the risk is lowered because the use of the AI system follows a previously completed human assessment which is not meant to replace or influence, without proper human review. Examples are AI systems designed to flag inconsistencies or anomalies in grading patterns.

¹¹⁸ Explanatory memorandum AI Act.

- 4) The AI system is intended to perform a task that is only preparatory to an assessment relevant for the purposes of the AI system, listed in the annexes of the AI Act., thus making the possible impact of the output very low in terms of representing a risk for the assessment to follow. Examples are smart solutions for file handling, AI systems used for translations, processing or linking data to other data sources.

The AI act is detailed and exhaustive when explaining what are to be considered Prohibited AI systems. Alternatively, it is more flexible when it comes to High-risk systems. To begin with it defines two ways how an AI system might qualify as high risk, either automatically because a) it is covered in one of the AI systems listed in Annex III or b) it meets the two conditions listed in article 6(1), namely 1) it is regulated under Union Harmonisation legislation and 2) it is subject to a third-party conformity assessment pursuant to relevant Union harmonisation legislation.

Medical devices are one of the manufactured products subject to EU harmonisation law, as it is provided in Annex I (11) of the AI Act. Furthermore, under the MRD certain medical devices need to undergo a conformity assessment. The majority of medical device software require such assessment and thus the involvement of a notified body. It follows that in the context of MES-CoBraD, it seems relevant to at least provide a preliminary assessment over the qualification of the platform as medical device under the Medical Device Regulation. The next section further elaborate on this question.

3.6 THE MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION (MDR)

The main instrument of the EU framework regarding medical devices, is the EU Medical Devices Regulation (MD Regulation), which entered into force in 2017, and is applicable since 26 May 2020.¹¹⁹

The MD Regulation aims to harmonise the rules and procedures related to medical devices. Considering the MES-CoBraD project's utilisation of various existing technologies as well as the development of the MES-CoBraD platform itself, the EU Medical Devices Regulation is relevant.¹²⁰

The MD Regulation defines a medical device as: "(...) any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material, or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes:

- › diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment, or alleviation of disease,
- › diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability,
- › investigation, replacement, or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state,
- › providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood, and tissue donations."¹²¹

Software is clearly mentioned in the definition. However, to qualify as a medical device, it is important that the manufacturer intended the software to be used for one of those medical purposes, for example: monitoring diagnostic and/or therapeutic purposes. In contrast, a device that *de facto* performs an activity that falls within the letter of the definition but is not intended to be used for medical purposes by its manufacturer, is not a medical device. Consequently, a safety certification as a medical device cannot be required.

¹¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices.

¹²⁰ TENDER D1.1 section 5

¹²¹ Article 2 of the Regulation (EU) 2017/745

In the *Brain Products GmbH v BioSemi VOF and Other cases*,¹²² the CJEU has sustained that a medical device must satisfy the essential requirements of the (replaced) directive and bear the CE marking, only if its manufacturer expressly intended to market it for medical purposes.

The recently updated Manual on Borderline and Classification in the Community Regulatory Framework for medical devices, attempts to provide some clarification when the assessment of a solution as a medical device is unclear.¹²³

It is important to underline that these guidance documents are not legally binding.

3.6.1 MES-COBRAD AS A MEDICAL DEVICE

Not all software used within healthcare qualifies as a medical device, for instance, software aimed to have library functions, such as facilitating retrieval of records through metadata matching would not qualify. Alternatively, software designed to “process, analyse, create or modify medical information can be qualified as a medical device if the creation and modification of that information is governed by a medical intended purpose”.¹²⁴

The MDCG puts the example of software that changes the data representation for medical purposes as an example that would qualify as medical device software. In contrast, altering the representation of data for embellishment/cosmetic or compatibility purposes does not readily qualify the software as a medical device software.¹²⁵ Another example that would not fall under the MDR is general software intended for non-medical purposes such as invoicing or planning staff. Based on the European Commission guidance on the qualification and classification of software as a medical device, the following decision steps have to be performed in order to determine the qualification of software as a medical device.

Table 5 MES-CoBraD Medical Device decision tree

<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Is the product 'software' according to the definition of the guidance note?<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Yes: next stepb. No: not covered by the guidance.2. Is the software a 'MDR annex XVI device' or an 'Accessory for Medical Device according to Art. 2(2) of the MDR or 'software driving or influencing the use of a (hardware) Medical Device?<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Yes : Covered by the MDRb. No: next step3. Is the software performing an action on data different from storage, archival, communication, or simple search?<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Yes: next stepb. No: not covered by the MDR4. Is the action for the benefit of individual patients?<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Yes: Next stepb. No: not covered by the MDR5. Is the software a Medical Device Software (MDSW) according to the definition of this guide?<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Yes: covered by the MDRb. No: not covered by the MDR
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¹²² CJEU Judgment of 22 November 2012 *Brain Products GmbH v BioSemi VOF and Others*, C-219/11 - *Brain Products*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:742

¹²³ Manual on Borderline and Classification in the Community Regulatory Framework for medical devices, version 1.18.

¹²⁴ European Commission (2019) 'MDCG 2019-11 Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – MDR and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 – IVDR'.

¹²⁵ *Idem* p.6

The MES-CoBraD project develops a platform that fuses RWD data collected from various sources to diagnose and ultimately treat complex brain disorders. From the information at hand, we can infer that the MES-CoBraD Platform is not merely intended to store data but to exploit it for an assessment. As such, it will allow the utilisation of data beyond storage and for the medical benefit of the patient, therefore it follows that different elements of the MES-CoBraD platform might qualify as medical software components:

- **Decision support software:** computer-based tools that combine general medical information databases and algorithms with patient-specific data. They are intended to provide healthcare professionals and/or users with recommendations for diagnosis, prognosis, monitoring, and treatment of individual patients. (i.e. Radiotherapy treatment planning systems; Drug planning systems; Computer-assisted detection systems).
- **Information systems:** Information systems that are intended only to transfer, store, convert, format, or archive data are not qualified as medical devices in themselves. However, they may be used with additional modules which maybe qualified in their own right as medical devices (MDSW).

Taking into account the above, we can conclude that at least certain components of MES-CoBraD will qualify as medical device and thus require compliance with the MDR. In that respect, and as explained in the EC guidelines, some medical device software may be segregated into a number of applications where each of these applications is correlated with a module. Some of these modules have a medical purpose, others not.¹²⁶ Accordingly, those modules which qualify as medical device software following the MDCG guidance, described above, would need comply with the requirements of imposed by the MDR including carrying out the CE Marking. Alternatively, the non-medical device modules would not be subject to the requirements for medical devices.

3.6.2 THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE MDR

Once the platform is functional, the consortium will need to identify the different components/modules within the MES-CoBraD platform individually to determine their qualification. Regardless of a more precise assessment, it can be concluded that the MDR is of application to MES-CoBraD, and thus its rules and safety controls will need to be considered. Based on the report provided by the European Coordination Committee of the Radiological and Electromedical and Healthcare IT Industry (**COCIR**) this section presents some of the legal requirements relevant to Artificial Intelligence solutions might need to adjust to comply with the MDR.¹²⁷

3.6.2.1 Design features required by the MDR.

Performance	Manufactures must describe in the instructions for use, if applicable, the intended purpose with a clear specification of indications, contraindications, patient target group or groups, intended users, and operating parameters and limitations of their device.
Minimise bias	Obligation for manufacturers to minimise bias. To that end manufacturers have to carry out an assessment AI for bias and ensure that bias has been minimised if considered harmful.
Repeatability	Devices that incorporate electronic programmable systems, devices that include software or software that are devices in themselves, needs to be repeatable.
Reliability	Devices that include software or are software devices in themselves need to be

¹²⁶ MDCG 2019-11 Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) , p 17

¹²⁷ COCIR (2021) Analysis on AI in medical Device Legislation,

	reliable.
Safety and security	Manufacturers need to establish, implement, document, and maintain a risk management system, including security and cybersecurity risks. This system must be a continuous iterative process throughout the lifecycle of a device. ¹²⁸
Eliminate or reduce the risk of use error	Elimination or reduction of the risk of use error. Inappropriate levels of trust in automation may cause suboptimal performance.

3.6.2.2 Compliance and enforcement under the MDR

Risk based:	Classification of devices by means of risk-based classification rules. ¹²⁹
Oversight and transparency	Requirement for an ex-ante and ex post controls on the safety and performance of medical devices, i.e., from device conception to retirement
Governance	The EU MDR has an elaborate governance system, checking on distributors, importers and manufacturers.
Notified bodies:	Depending on the type of device, the manufacturer must follow a compliance assessment procedure that involves the notification of a third-party, independent body with the description of the device, the management system to be applied, technical documentation, and documentation on clinical evaluation plan and risk management. In the EU, such an organisation is called a Notified Body. ¹³⁰
Addresses	Provide addresses of manufacturers and economic operators
Keeping of records and data	IEC 82304-1 General requirements for product safety of health software therefore require manufacturers to provide all information necessary for the user or the responsible organisation to safely decommission and dispose of the health software, including personal and health-related data.

3.6.2.3 Transparency and accountability

Transparency	The EU MDR does not require devices to explain or render transparent their decisions to the user, nor does it preclude manufacturers from placing ‘inexplicable’ devices on the market. Instead, it requires demonstration that the safety and performance of their devices reaches state-of-the-art for their intended use. Transparency under the MDR should not be confused with transparency as per the GDPR articles 12-14.
Accountability	Accountability in healthcare means answerability, it is closely related to transparency and can be divided into the following categories: financial, performance, and political / democratic accountability.

¹²⁸ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on medical devices (MDR), Annex I General Safety Performance Requirements

¹²⁹ The EU MDR contains 22 classification rules.

¹³⁰ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on medical devices (MDR), Annex IX Conformity assessment based on quality management and on assessment of technical documentation.

4 CAPITA SELECTA: DATA PROTECTION ASSESSMENT IN MES-COBRA D

4.1 MES-COBRA D METHODOLOGY FOR A DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The European Union’s (EU) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) imposes on data controllers, *inter alia*, an obligation to conduct, if there is a likelihood of a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, a process of data protection impact assessment (DPIA) (Article 35(1)).

The methodology of DPIA applied in MES-CoBraD is based on VUB’s *d.pia.lab Policy Brief*.¹³¹ The assessment in MES-CoBraD has been adapted to the needs of an international project that includes different partners, jurisdictions, as well as multiple processing operations and types of datasets.

The updated version of this section mobilises the framework identified in the first version of the ethical and regulatory framework and incorporates the assessment performed during the project. In this sense, this section establishes the core elements for an assessment of the activities carried out by the entities involved in the project.

Based on the data protection guidelines and the CJEU case law, the concepts of personal data, processing, controller, processors, and joint controllership are introduced and considered in light of the MES-CoBraD research activities.

The assessment methodology followed in MES-CoBraD has made use of the different 'tools' available in WP2, in particular the D2.2 MES-CoBraD Data Management Plan, the D2.1 and D2.6 CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk (v1-v2).¹³²

Particularly the DMP, has functioned as a living document, collecting and periodically updating information regarding the processing activities of the project.

In addition, the analysis on the different aspects herein discussed are also based on the findings produced by the Project, in particular those regarding the Data Integration, harmonisation, sharing and security from WP5.¹³³

Accordingly, when necessary, this section will refer to the relevant deliverables.

Table 6 MES-CoBraD DPIA methodology

The MES-CoBraD assessment methodology is structured in the following four phases:

4.1.1 PHASE I: PLANNING AND PREPARATION

The objective of this first phase was to determine if the DPIA process was required in MES-CoBraD in the first place. To that end, we checked whether one or more of the criteria set forth by law or other relevant

¹³¹ Dariusz Kloza et al., 'Data Protection Impact Assessment in the European Union: Developing a Template for a Report from the Assessment Process', *D.Pia.Lab Policy Brief* 2020 (11 September 2020): 1–52,.

¹³² D2.6 CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk v2.

¹³³ ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final (v1.0). (2023).

regulatory requirements were met or, alternatively, an exemption applied.

Following the general description of the project provided in the GA, MES-CoBraD is “a medical research project aimed at the development of a platform offering medical practitioners an efficient tool for the diagnosis of complex brain disorders. The project seeks to improve the diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes of complex brain disorders, such as epilepsy, dementia, and sleep disorders”.¹³⁴

The MES-CoBraD platform is composed of 1) an **edge module** installed at the medical partner’s premises and a 2) **cloud platform** integrated by a i) data lake, ii) security components, iii) data harmonisation tools, and iv) the expert system. The cloud platform is in Italy, at the premises of the technical partner ENG.

MES-CoBraD relies on the processing of retrospective and prospective real-world data (RWD) concerning health, to populate the platform and train its predictive algorithms / machine learning capacities. In particular, MES-CoBraD uses the following datasets:

With this in mind, WP2 concluded that it was necessary to assess the data protection risks generated by the project and identified the following preliminary elements:

- The sensitiveness of the scope and purpose of the project. Considering in particular the research in the field of healthcare.
- The potential processing of personal data, special categories of data and data concerning health.
- The potential existence of international data transfers to consortium partners outside the EU.
- The reliance on anonymisation for its processing activities.

A second step in this phase was to **define the scope** of the assessment. In that respect, we distinguished **two MES-CoBraD scenarios**.

1. On the one hand, the processing activities that take place during the research performed in MES-CoBraD.
2. On the other hand, potential processing activities that take place in a hypothetical deployment scenario.

In this respect, it is important to note that, while certain aspects of the assessment might be applicable upon deployment, this should not be taken for granted. This is consistent with the conclusions raised in D2.3 Legal and Ethical Framework v1, where it was recommended that “(u)pon conclusion of the project and prior its deployment for exploitation, (...) a data protection impact assessment is conducted to assess the potential impact of the MES-CoBraD processing operations on the protection of personal data”.¹³⁵ Certainly, we consider that it could not be another way as many aspects of the platform are yet unknown or might be subject to future modification. In conclusion, the evaluation performed in this document, including the inputs of the monitoring and actions adopted through the DMP, should be understood to refer to the processing activities performed during research.

From an organisational point of view, because the assessment of a research project requires flexibility as well as a capacity to react upon those assessments, it was decided to use of the D2.2 Data Management Plan as living document [M6]. Accordingly, the D2.2 DMP would be used to:

- i) Set the FAIR data management policy of the project,
- ii) Report on the main data protection elements:
- iii) Act as a mean to enforce data protection compliance.

¹³⁴ Mes CoBraD Grant agreement.

¹³⁵ D2.3 The CoBraD Ethical and Regulatory Framework. (2022)

In that way, the DMP has become the enabling tool for the assessment of data protection in MES-CoBraD. The use of research dataset templates (hereinafter RDT) was considered the most practical way to keep track of the data generated by the project as well as its use. Structured in 5 sections, the RDT has been designed to facilitate both complying with FAIR requirements and also gathering crucial information from an ethics and data protection perspective.¹³⁶

Additionally, the assessment has been complemented by D2.3 Legal and Ethical Frameworks (M12) which aimed to capture the Ethical and Regulatory framework of MES-CoBraD, and by D2.1 the CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk (M12-) aimed to provide a fast, precise, and organised response to the ethical and legal questions of the project partners. The document gathered the relevant ethical documentation for ethical compliance with the research activities of the project, such as: IRB approvals, incidental finding policies, and consent forms.

4.1.2 PHASE II: ASSESSMENT AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The goal of this second phase was to expand the preliminary description of the processing and describe the envisaged processing operations both contextually and technically. Such a description was aimed to be operational and suggest measures to address the risks of processing operations identified in order to protect individuals and to demonstrate compliance with law during the project. This task was carried based on D2.3 and D2.1.

D2.3 presented contextual aspects of the envisaged processing operations. The document identified the applicable legislation for the project and presented a number of recommendations to address the potential risks. Those recommendations had to be mobilised by the partners during the remaining duration of the project.

As stated above, D2.3 first informed partners about the applicable data protection laws and national derogations applicable to the MES-CoBraD research. Paying special paid to European Union (EU) law on personal data protection and the opinions and guidance notes from EU independent bodies (s.2 and s3). Second, it presented from both a theoretical and practical approach, a number of critical issues to the processing activities envisaged in MES-CoBraD. The first version of the normative framework will focus on the following points:

- (1) The concept of personal data:
- (2) Data Processing Operations in MES-Cobrad
- (3) Anonymisation and pseudonymisation
- (4) Controllership
- (5) Principles related to personal data under the GDPR.
- (6) Security of processing activities
- (7) Rights of the data subject
- (8) International data transfers in MES-CoBraD

Based on the research carried out by the partners and the legal developments that have taken place since the publication of D2.3, Section 4. provides an updated assessment of these aspects in the context of MES-CoBraD.

4.1.3 PHASE III: MOBILISATION AND COMPLIANCE

The submission of D2.3 to M12 resulted in a number of recommendations; the following table presents the measures adopted during the project to comply with those recommendations.¹³⁷

¹³⁶ RDT sections are: 1) Data summary; 2) Fair Data principles; 3) Storage and Security and 5) Ethics.

¹³⁷ Further information can be found in s3 of the DMP.

Table 7 MES-CoBrad Organisational measures

DOCUMENT	DESCRIPTION
<p>Nomination of DPO ethical contact point and compliance declaration- May 2021</p>	<p>In May 2021, a month after the official launch of the project, all members of MES-CoBraD were requested to provide the details of their nominated Data Protection Officer (DPO) or contact point for legal and ethical matters of MES-CoBraD. Furthermore, all partners were also requested to sign an acknowledgement statement concerning their obligations towards national and EU legislation, including, but not limited to, compliance with the GDPR.</p> <p>All partners in MES-CoBraD have signed a “Declaration of compliance regarding the processing of personal data” declaring that “the collection and processing of personal data in the project, within the activities involving the [relevant partner], is or will be carried out according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the General Data Protection Regulation), and the national law of the country where the partner organisation is established”.¹³⁸</p> <p>Therefore, it is acknowledged that partners acting as data controllers and processors have taken all necessary measures for their internal GDPR compliance and safeguarded all personal data. This is particularly relevant with regard to the role of medical partners and the processing activities on health data that take place at their premises. The individual responsibilities of each partner do not free up the MES-CoBraD from the obligation to comply with its obligations as a research project.</p>
<p>Opinions and approvals by ethics committees, incidental findings, and consent forms October 20, 2022</p>	<p>D2.6 Cobrad Ethical and Legal Helpdesk report collected the existing documentation, sent by the consortium partners, certifying compliance with the ethical and legal principles of the project, and described in this deliverable (see section 3). In particular, the partners provided the following documentations: i) IRB approvals; ii) The consent forms given to patients; iii) The inclusion and exclusion criteria adopted to select participants; iv) The Incidental Finding Policies.</p>
<p>Records on processing activities (living doc)</p>	<p>A diagram of the 1) data processing lifecycle within the project and the 2) description of the processing operations envisaged in MES-CoBrad was added to the DMP (s 3.1.5). In both cases, the description has been subject to changes as the project and its assessment have progressed.</p>
<p>MES-CoBRaD Protocol for handling data subject requests May 20, 2022</p>	<p>Each party shall handle Data Subject requests (Articles 15-22 of the GDPR) raised in connection with the data collected and provided to the MES-CoBraD platform, in accordance with their internal policies and applicable data protection requirements.</p> <p>All Partners shall cooperate and, when requested, provide each other with swift and efficient assistance in handling any Data Subject requests in accordance with the following step.</p>

¹³⁸ Idem

<p>MES-CoBraD Data Processing policy September 2022</p>	<p>According to the controller’s obligation (Article 4 (7) and Article 26 of the GDPR) and the principles of transparency and accountability (Article 5 (1) and 5 (2) of the GDPR), the consortium has decided to adopt a data processing policy to better identify and reflect the roles of each partner with respect to the data stored at the MES-CoBraD platform, particularly with respect to the exercise of the rights of the Data Subject (Article 15 of the GDPR) and their respective duties to provide them with information (Article 14 of the GDPR).</p>
<p>Data Breach Protocol March 20, 2023</p>	<p>Parties establish the protocol to be followed in the event of a personal data breach within the project, taking into account the applicable legislation, in particular the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 (hereinafter "the GDPR"). The European Data Protection Board Guidelines 9/2022 on personal data breach notification under the GDPR are also considered.</p>

4.1.4 PHASE IV: ONGOING STEPS

The goal of this ongoing step has been to consult and maintain a direct line of information with the MES-CoBRAD partners, particularly with regard to the processing operations taking place throughout the entire project.

All partners generating data have been requested to fill their respective Research Data set Templates (RDT), by themselves and upload them to the relevant SharePoint folder. This has ensured the flow of information between the different partners of the project and facilitated an assessment that would otherwise have been extremely complex.

Additionally, based on the findings reported in D2.3 Ethical and Regulatory Framework, three questionnaires were distributed among partners.

- › **Part I:** Lawfulness Fairness and Transparency 19/10/2023 until 2/11/2023.
- › **Part II:** Data Protection Principles: purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy (2/11/2023 until 16/11/2023)
- › **Part III:** Storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality (16/11/2023 until 30 /11/2023)

The questionnaires had twofold purpose: First, to foster discussions on data protection principles among technical partners during the design stage of the project. Second, monitor the compliance of the project and facilitate the assessment on how MES-CoBraD complied with its data protection obligations.

Although all partners were invited to contribute to the questionnaires, the documents targeted WP leaders who, when necessary, could redirect to relevant partners to those specific questions that fall under their expertise. Partners were also requested to identify the module of the platform to which an answer referred, as well as the WP, task, or deliverable where an explanation to a question can be found. To maintain the collaborative approach and avoid the creation of files with a single answer, all partners were invited to contribute to the same document stored on Project SharePoint. At the same time, to foster participation, it was agreed that the answers would not be made public.

However, many of these answers are reported directly through different items in this section; key insights concerning 1) Data protection principles; 2) Storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality; 3) Data subject rights have been identified.

4.2 JURISPRUDENTIAL UPDATE ON THE CONCEPT OF PERSONAL DATA BY THE CJEU

Since March 2022, the date when the first version of this deliverable (D2.3) was submitted, the debate over the concept of personal data has been recurrent for academia, courts, and data protection bodies.¹³⁹ During this period, the CJEU has been providing guidance on how to interpret the meaning of “personal data” in the GDPR, elaborating on the controversial aspect of identifiability expressed in recital 26 of the GDPR. Three cases require special attention, 1) the **Case T-557/20 (SRB)** from March 2023; 2) the case **C-319/22 (Gesamtervand)** from on November 2023 and 3) the **Case C-479/22 P (OC)** March 2024. The following section provides an overview on the three cases, presents their main findings, and concludes with an assessment on how they can apply to the questions posed in MES-CoBraD.

All of these cases rely to a great extent on the Breyer case of 2016¹⁴⁰. There, the CJEU elaborated on the notion of personal data by means of the test of identifiability. The Court argued that, in the definition of personal data, the use of the word 'indirectly' suggested an intention of the Legislator to go beyond the information held by one party when it came to determine identifiability; The Court then elaborated on the limits of the 'reasonable likelihood of identifiability', stating that 'a means is not reasonably likely to be used to identify the subject of the data where the identification of that person is prohibited by law or impossible in practice, because it requires a disproportionate effort in terms of time, cost and labour, so that the risk of identification appears in reality to be insignificant.¹⁴¹ Based on these arguments, the CJEU found that a dynamic IP address in the hands of a website publisher had to be regarded as a piece of personal data for that publisher if the publisher had legal means enabling it to identify the visitor. This has been interpreted as the CJEU’s “objective criterion” to identifiability.¹⁴²

Following Breyer, two main positions have been observed with regards to the concept of personal data and related elements such as pseudonymisation, anonymisation, or identifiability.

On the one hand, advocates of the **static or objective approach** prominently represented by the EDPS and the EDPB, sustain that the nature of data as personal or not, depends on the abstract possibility of the individual reidentification. This follows a broad understanding of what ‘identified or identifiable’ means. According to this view, 'identified' refers to a person who is known or distinguished in a group, and 'identifiable' is a person who is not yet identified, but whose identification is possible. From this perspective, neither an actual identification nor even the intention of identifying the subject in the future is required.¹⁴³ Moreover, it is not even necessary that the data is kept by the same person who processes the “information”.¹⁴⁴ This is based on an interpretation of recital 26 according to which, only when reidentification is not possible for any entity, information can be regarded as not being personal. In other words, even when identification is theoretically possible only for the controller but not for the processor, the processing activities performed by the processor are still regarded as personal data.

On the other hand, proponents of the dynamic or '**relative approach**' argue that the qualification of data as personal must be assessed contextually, requiring a particular assessment of who holds the data set (the controller or the subsequent recipient) as well as the technical and legal means available to the

¹³⁹ See for instance Alexandre Lodie, 'Are Personal Data Always Personal? Case T-557/20 SRB v. EDPS or When the Qualification of Data Depends on Who Holds Them', n.d.; Stephanie Rossello and Pierre Dewitte, 'Exploring the Limits of Joint Control: The Case of COVID-19 Digital Proximity Tracing Solutions', 2021.

¹⁴⁰ CJEU, judgment of 19 October 2016, *Breyer*, C-582/14, EU:C:2016:779

¹⁴¹ *Idem*, paragraph 46.

¹⁴² Frederik Zuiderveen Borgesius, 'Breyer Case of the Court of Justice of the European Union: IP Addresses and the Personal Data Definition (Case Note)', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY, 6 June 2017),.

¹⁴³ EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 04/2020 on the use of location data and contact tracing tools in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak; See also EDPB, 15 December 2020, Response to Professor Dr. Katja Becker regarding the impacts of the GDPR on Research

¹⁴⁴ CJEU, judgment of 19 October 2016, *Breyer*, C-582/14, EU:C:2016:779, paragraph 46).

recipient to succeed in the reidentification of datasets.¹⁴⁵ As will be observed, from the recent case law on the matter discussed below, the relative approach appears to have been consistently established as the interpretation adopted by the CJEU.

4.2.1 SRB vs EDPS

A bit more than seven years after the Breyer case, the General Court shook what, until then, was considered an unshakeable principle of data protection. In the *Single Resolution Board v EDPS* case, the Single Resolution Board (SRB) acting as the Union banking authority, invited the Banco Popular shareholders to comment on their eligibility for compensation during the process of resolution scheme. Those comments were filtered, categorised, and aggregated, when identical, and then associated with an alphanumeric code, a 33-digit globally unique identifier randomly generated at the time the responses to the form were received.¹⁴⁶

Some of these comments were later shared with an independent evaluator (Deloitte) to complete the assessment. SRB retained a decoding table which allowed linking the identifiers back to the original commenters. However, neither the independent evaluator nor the SRB staff working with the comments had access to the 'decoding table'.

Five shareholders filed a complaint before the EDPS, arguing that they had not been informed about their personal data being transferred to a third party (the independent evaluator). Without looking too much at the specificities of the case, EDPS (rather dogmatically) concluded that sharing the alphanumeric code represented a processing of 'pseudonymous' data, and therefore personal data. As a result, the EDPS found a data protection breach resulting from the SRB failure to inform data subjects that their personal data had been shared with third parties.

The decision was appealed by SRB and referred to the General Court. The appellant (SRB) opposed the EDPS interpretation, arguing that the comments remained anonymous to recipient (Deloitte) because information allowing re-identification were not shared with them, The General Court endorsed this approach by stating that "qualification of data as pseudonymised and/or anonymised cannot be asserted in an abstract fashion".¹⁴⁷ It follows that whether in the specific case the recipient has the means reasonably likely carry out the re-identification of the data irrespective of whether the data could be considered as "pseudonymised" by nature needs to be examined case by case.¹⁴⁸

The Court thus adopted what some scholars have referred as to a relative approach on the concept of personal data in contraposition to the EDPS objective approach.¹⁴⁹ In the particular case the Court phrased this approach as follows: "since the EDPS did not investigate whether Deloitte had legal means available to it that could, in practice, enable it to access the additional information necessary to re-identify the authors of the comments, the EDPS could not conclude that the information transmitted to Deloitte constituted information related to an 'identifiable natural person (...)'.¹⁵⁰

According to the General Court, the EDPS had failed to assess whether the recipient of pseudonymised

¹⁴⁵ Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon and Alison Knight, 'Anonymous Data v. Personal Data – A False Debate: An EU Perspective on Anonymization, Pseudonymization and Personal Data', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY, 6 March 2017),.

¹⁴⁶ CJEU Judgment of 26 April 2023, *SRB v. EDPS*, C- T-557/20, ECLI:EU:T:2023:219

¹⁴⁷ *Idem* paragraph 103

¹⁴⁸ *idem*

¹⁴⁹ Michèle Finck and Frank Pallas, 'They Who Must Not Be Identified - Distinguishing Personal from Non-Personal Data Under the GDPR', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY, 1 October 2019), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3462948>. See also Frederik J. Zuiderveen Borgesius, 'Singling out People without Knowing Their Names – Behavioural Targeting, Pseudonymous Data, and the New Data Protection Regulation', *Computer Law & Security Review* 32, no. 2 (1 April 2016): 256–71, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2015.12.013>. Alexandre Lodie, 'Are Personal Data Always Personal? Case T-557/20 SRB v. EDPS or When the Qualification of Data Depends on Who Holds Them', n.d.

¹⁵⁰ CJEU Judgment of 26 April 2023, *SRB v. EDPS*, C- T-557/20, ECLI:EU:T:2023:219, paragraph 105

data (the independent evaluator) had any reasonable means (technical and legal) to obtain the additional information held by SRB and necessary to re-identify the data subjects from the data received. In that sense the Court argued that EDPS had only taken into consideration, the controller's perspective (SRB) and not of the recipient.¹⁵¹

As a result, the Court considered that even when data is pseudonymed, one has to check whether the recipient of the data has the means to re-identify the data subjects, in the negative, pseudonymised data cannot be regarded as personal data.

4.2.2 AUTOTEILE-HANDEL EV V SCANIA (VINS DECISION)

The case concerns the dispute between a manufacturer of commercial vehicles (Scania) and a trade association of independent wholesalers of vehicle parts (Gesamtverband Autoteile-Handel). In the view of the trade association, based on article 6(1) of the Regulation [2018/858, Scania was obliged to provide all independent operators with access to a list of the vehicles' unique identifying numbers (VINS) in order to ensure competition in the motor vehicle aftermarket.¹⁵²

The interest from a data protection perspective lies on the views maintained by the parties regarding the nature of VINS as personal data and its capacity to reidentify individuals. The manufacturer (Scania) opposed to the disclosure of information arguing that VINS constituted personal data, while the trade association (Gesamtverband) argued that VINS were not personal data based on their incapacity to reidentify individuals.

The Court considered that to answer the question posed in the proceedings, it was necessary to first examine whether the VIN fell within the concept of 'personal data' set in Article 4(1) of the GDPR.¹⁵³ For this reason, the Court explained that information is personal data 'where, due to its content, purpose, and effect, the information in question is related to a particular natural person.' Then focusing on the issue of identifiability the Court referred to the 2016 Breyer case and stated that "(i)n order to determine whether a natural person is identifiable, directly or indirectly, account should be taken of all the means likely reasonably to be used either by the controller, within the meaning of Article 4(7) of the GDPR, or by any other person, to identify that person, without, however, requiring that all the information enabling that person to be identified should be in the hands of a single entity"¹⁵⁴

The Court noted that VINS, understood as an alphanumeric code assigned to the vehicle by its manufacturer (...) were not as such 'personal'—but that the same could become personal "as regards someone who reasonably has means enabling that datum to be associated with a specific person".¹⁵⁵ The Court went on to note that VINS held information on the registration certificate for a vehicle, including the name and address of the holder of that certificate. In those circumstances, the VIN constituted personal data, within the meaning of Article 4(1) of the GDPR, in so far as the person who had access to it had means enabling the reidentification of the owner of a vehicle with the person in the certificate.

To conclude, the Court established that "where independent operators may reasonably have at their disposal the means enabling them to link a VIN to an identified or identifiable natural person, which it is

¹⁵¹ idem para.103

¹⁵² According to Article 61(1) of Regulation 2018/858 requires "vehicle manufacturers to provide independent operators with unrestricted, standardised and non-discriminatory access, inter alia, to 'vehicle repair and maintenance information (...)'. When raising the case to the CJEU for preliminary ruling, the Landgericht Köln (Regional Court, Cologne) asked whether "Article 61(1) of Regulation [2018/858] constituted, for vehicle manufacturers, a legal obligation within the meaning of Article 6(1)(c) of the GDPR which justifies the disclosure of VINs or information linked to VINs to independent operators as other controllers within the meaning of point 7 of Article 4 of the GDPR?". The question inferred an assumption that, if such an obligation were to exist, compliance with it would necessitate the processing of personal data.

¹⁵³ General Court Judgment of 26 April 2023, SRB v. EDPS, C- T-557/20, ECLI:EU:T:2023:219, paragraph 44

¹⁵⁴ CJEU, Judgment of 19 October 2016, Breyer, C-582/14, EU:C:2016:779, paragraphs 42 and 43

¹⁵⁵ Idem paragraph 46.

for the referring court to determine that the VIN constitutes personal data for them, within the meaning of Article 4(1) of the GDPR, and, indirectly, for the vehicle manufacturers making it available, even if the VIN is not, in itself, personal data for them, and is not personal data for them in particular where the vehicle to which the VIN has been assigned does not belong to a natural person.” (para 49).

The Court therefore took a relative approach on “identifiability” by conditioning the nature of VINS as personal data to the perspective of the recipient perspective.¹⁵⁶

4.2.3 OC v COMMISSION (OLAF PRESS RELEASE)

The case dealt with the claim of a Greek researcher, who had been under investigation by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) for fraud in the use of research funds.¹⁵⁷ The claimant argued that the Agency unlawfully disclosed personal data after publishing a press release on the case. Adopting a questionable position, the General Court rejected the claimant's view, arguing that the press release could not be considered personal data despite an investigative journalist having indeed reidentified the researcher.

Applying the identification test of identification from recital 26 of the GDPR, the Court sustained that investigative journalists could not be seen as “average or likely readers” of the information discussed, and that as result, the press release remained non personal to all who, in contrast to the journalist, did not possess the means enabling re-identification.

On appeal, the researcher argued that the General Court “had legally misinterpreted the concept of an ‘identifiable natural person’” based on two main points: First, identifiability does not depend on an “average reader” criterion but on whether a specific individual holds “additional factors necessary for identification”.¹⁵⁸ The Court had made an erroneous interpretation of identifiability criteria. Second, the Court misjudged recital’s 26 test on the “means reasonably likely” to re-identify a data subject.

Indeed, the ECJ held that the General Court had wrongly applied the test of identifiability shrined in recital 26. Interpreting the arguments raised in Breyer, it noted that despite additional information might allow the identification of a data subject, that would not automatically turn the data to be classified as personal.

The ECJ also rejected the General Court’s use of an ‘average reader test” as a valid recourse to conclude that certain data are not personal.

Finally, the ECJ noted that the press release contained enough information to enable the identification of the researcher (including gender, nationality, father’s occupation, geographic location of the hosting entity etc). Applying the “reasonable means “test the ECJ determined that identification could occur without a disproportionate effort in terms of time, cost, and labour. Therefore, the Court had failed in finding that the claimant was not identifiable from the press release, and to state that the information therein included was not personal.¹⁵⁹

4.3 PERSONAL DATA AND HEALTH DATA

In EU and European data protection law, only personal data is subject to data protection rules. Therefore, as a preliminary step to determine the legal obligations and responsibilities of the consortium toward data protection, it is necessary to first identify which types of data are processed.

¹⁵⁶ See also a critique to Courts assumption over the assessment of identifiability from the data holder perspective. ‘C-319/22 Gesamtverband Autoteile-Handel eV v. Scania: How to Solve the “Indirect Personal Data” Riddle?’, *European Law Blog* (blog), 6 February 2024.

¹⁵⁷ General Court Judgment of 4 May 2022, OC v Commission Case T-384/20. ECLI:EU:T:2022:273

¹⁵⁸ General Court, Judgement of 14 July 2022; T-384/20; Case C-479/22 P, Appeal. ECLI:EU:T:2022:273

¹⁵⁹Idem, paragraph 61

4.3.1 WHAT IS PERSONAL DATA?

Personal data Article 4(1) of the GDPR Recital 30 of the GDPR	Personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;
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Personal data is a key concept of data protection; it is only on personal data that the GDPR applies. It follows that determining whether a controller is processing personal data represents an integral aspect of the controller's evaluation of its data protection responsibilities. This exercise should be carried out by the controller 'at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of processing itself' so that the controller adopts the appropriate measures and safeguards to protect the principles of data protection and the rights of the data subject rights.¹⁶⁰

The definition of personal data in the GDPR is worded in a purposely vague fashion, arguably a sign of the legislator's desire to enable, flexibility, and adaptability to future technological developments. From the wording of article 4 (1), three elements help constitute personal data is: 1) information (relating to) 2) identified or identifiable, and 3) natural person. Neither the content (public or private) nor the format (digital or analogue) through which personal data is stored or used is relevant to the applicability of the data protection law.¹⁶¹

In practice, any piece of 'information' is personal data, insofar as it relates to 'an identified or identifiable' natural person.¹⁶² Data would relate to a natural person when from it someone can be identified directly or indirectly when using additional information. The fact that personal data refer exclusively to 'natural' person excludes legal persons and deceased persons (Recital 27).¹⁶³ Despite not being explicitly mentioned or defined by the GDPR, the contrary of personal data is non personal data.

The Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 on the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data in the EU offers a *contrario* definition of the concept by referring to anything not considered personal data as per article 4(1) of the GDPR. Therefore, by opposition non-personal data should be understood as information that does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, either because it does not contain human identifiers or because those have been removed, for instance, as a result of an anonymisation processing.

As a novelty, beyond the said duality, the GDPR introduces two new categories, pseudonymisation and anonymisation. These are always the result of the processing of personal data, namely 1) personal data that has undergone pseudonymisation or 2) personal data that have undergone anonymisation.

4.3.2 IDENTIFIED OR IDENTIFIABLE?

The test of	To ascertain whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the 1)
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¹⁶⁰ See EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.v2.0

¹⁶¹ The case of cell samples is specifically dealt in Article 4 (13) of the GDPR) as information that relates to the "individual's inherited or acquired genetic characteristics, provide unique information about their health or physiology and result from an analysis of a biological sample of this person".

¹⁶² The notion of information has been interpreted by the CJEU in the Nowak v Data Protection commissioner case. There the CJEU interpreted that "(t)he use of the expression 'any information' in the definition of the concept of 'personal data', (...), reflects the aim of the EU legislature to assign a wide scope to that concept, which is not restricted to information that is sensitive or private, but potentially encompasses all kinds of information, not only objective but also subjective, in the form of opinions and assessments, provided that it 'relates' to the data subject. See CJEU Judgement of 20, December 2016, C-434/16, Nowak v Data Protection Commissioner, ECLI:EU:C:2017:994, paragraph 34.

¹⁶³ In the case of a deceased person Member States are entrusted the possibility to legislate specific.

reasonable likelihood of identification <i>Recital 26 of the GDPR</i>	means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, 2) by the controller or another person to identify the natural person 3) directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used, account should be taken of 4) all objective factors, such as i) the costs of and ii) the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration iii) the available technology at the time of the processing and iv) technological developments.
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In order to be considered personal data, information must necessarily relate to a natural person. This means that even when it contains personal identifiers, data might be regarded as nonpersonal when the same cannot lead to a natural person identification.

The concept of Identifiability embodies the so called “risk-based approach” and promotes a risk management attitude towards the processing of information under a principle of reasonableness.¹⁶⁴

This formula leaves open the question as to what or which threshold could lead to ascertain when a person is 'identified or can be identifiable' based on a piece of information. As an example, article 4(1) provides a number of identifiers, some of which are as straightforward, such as the individual’s name or identification number, but then the definition opens up to less explicit factors that could allow the present and future identification of an individual by themselves or in the future when combined with other data. The advances in computational processing methods have led to acknowledge that information a priori aseptic in terms of identifies might eventually qualify as personal data.

To assess “identifiability recital 26 introduces a test of a reasonable likelihood for the identification. The test must contemplate the means “likely to be used” not only by the controllers but also for “any other person” willing to attempt reidentification. (see section 4.2 above). Regarding the concept “of means”, recital 26 includes relative values concerning costs and time. It is also important to note that the assessment has a future-oriented nature and thus must be periodically conducted to embrace technological developments.

For this reason, when considering whether we are discussing about the existence of personal data or not, a “tailored, context- specific” analysis is required.¹⁶⁵

4.3.3 SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

There are special categories of personal data that are considered particularly sensitive in relation to the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Its processing is deemed riskier and thus worth of an enhanced protection.¹⁶⁶ Whereas the processing of special categories of data is a priori forbidden, and there is only a limited number of cases where its processing is lawful. Processing data relating to medical diagnosis, scientific research is one of those cases.¹⁶⁷

Within the GDPR (Article 9), the following categories are considered special categories of data:

- i. personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin.
- ii. personal data revealing political opinions, religious or other beliefs, including philosophical beliefs.
- iii. personal data revealing trade union membership.
- iv. genetic data and biometric data processed for the purpose of identifying a person.
- v. personal data concerning health, sexual life, or sexual orientation.

¹⁶⁴ R.Gellert, The Risk-Based Approach to Data Protection (Oxford University Press, (2020)

¹⁶⁵ N. Purtova, ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law,’ Law, Innovation, and Technology 10(1) (2018).

¹⁶⁶ Recital 51 of the GDPR

¹⁶⁷ See article 9 (2) of the GDPR.

Special attention should be given to categories of data that do not fall under the generic definition of personal data mentioned above, but to a specific group of special types of data.

4.3.4 DATA CONCERNING HEALTH

Data concerning health. Article 4(15) of the GDPR See also recital 35	'Data concerning health' means personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status;
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Health data include all data pertaining to the health status of a data subject, which reveals information relating to the past, current, or future physical or mental health status of the data subject. Examples of health data are:

- i. Information about the natural person collected in the course of the registration for, or the provision of, health care services as referred to in Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council to that natural person.
- ii. A number, symbol, or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes.
- iii. Information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples.
- iv. Any information on, for example, a disease, disability, disease risk, medical history, clinical treatment, or the physiological or biomedical state of the data subject independent of its source, for example from a physician or other health professional, a hospital, a medical device, or an in vitro diagnostic test.

Health data is considered a special category of data, and as such, its processing is a priori forbidden. Member States are allowed to keep or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data, or data concerning health. See below section on Member States derogations.

4.3.5 WHAT DATA IS PROCESSED DURING THE PROJECT MES-COBRA D

The project MES-CoBraD uses retrospective and prospective RWD concerning health to populate the MES-CoBraD platform and train the predictive algorithms. The datasets collected and used in MES-CoBraD for research purposes, have been carefully curated and motivated on a scientific basis and aim to achieve the scientific goals of the project. Information on each dataset, including its purpose and legal basis, is reported in the Data Management Plan. A more detailed description of the research datasets used in MES-CoBraD as well as their justification from a scientific point of view can be found at D3.2 Project Manual.¹⁶⁸

In MES-COBraD four medical partners: **NIA, UU, KCL, RMC-C&E**, have agreed to incorporate participant data to the project.¹⁶⁹ Personal data that are obtained and processed at the clinical sites and other clinical settings are governed by the medical partners own laws, regulations, and procedure independent to MES-CoBraD. In addition, the RWD used for research purposes is bound to the data management policy of the consortium, as a result of it, it is not included in any disseminated material.

¹⁶⁸ MES- CoBraD D3.2 Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation – v2, September 2021. For further information on the RWD description, please check v2 of the MES-CoBraD Project Manual (p.26) and the Data Management Plan (D2.2)

¹⁶⁹ IR-HSCSP. D8.5 Participant recruitment, Preexisting RWD access, Prospective RWD acquisition and secure storage –v3 (v1.0), (2023).

As it will be further detailed below, the processing of personal data in MES-CoBraD is limited to the collection and preparation of the data for its de-personalisation. In that respect, the MES-CoBraD platform incorporates in its edge module, installed at each of the medical partners premises, a de-personalisation module configurable according to each type of RWD.¹⁷⁰

The data outcome obtained from the module might be either fully anonymised data or pseudonymised data. If a dataset is successfully anonymised at the depersonalisation module, the data uploaded will no longer be personal data and as a result, no processing of personal data will take place within the MES-CoBraD platform.

Figure 1 - Basic de-personalisation flow.¹⁷¹

Alternatively, if the data remain capable of identifying the data subject, the data within the platform will continue to be considered personal data, and as a result the data protection framework will continue to apply.

A more detailed description on the data processing activities taking place during the project is fundamental to establish whether the processing of personal data takes place at a platform level.

4.4 DATA PROCESSING

4.4.1 DEFINING A DATA PROCESSING ACTIVITY

<p>Processing- Article 4(2) of the GDPR ¹⁷²</p>	<p>'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction;</p>
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Data processing refers to any operation on personal data using automated means (i.e., computers, mobile devices) as well as manual ones, when the personal data is contained or aimed to be contained in a file.¹⁷³ In practice, the processing of data might group different activities or operations that precede and follow one another. From collecting the data until it is destroyed, the data can be used in many ways.

4.4.2 THE DATA PROCESSING LIFECYCLE IN MES-CoBRAD

Describing the processing activities in MES-CoBraD requires the identification of the dataset processing

¹⁷⁰ ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final (2023).

¹⁷¹ idem

¹⁷² The concept is shared and in Art. 2 (b). of the Council of Europe Modernised Convention (2018) for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data,

¹⁷³ In its recital 15 the GDPR defines file as “any structured set of personal data accessible according to determined criteria, whether this set is centralized, decentralized or distributed functionally or geographically”. The files or sets of files not structured according to specific criteria, do not fall within the scope of the Regulation.

lifecycles. In MES-CoBraD medical partners process two types of data sets: 1) retrospective data and 2) prospective data.

From a research perspective, the purposes of the processing activities that take place in the Project are aimed at: 1) diagnostics (image recognition, system checkers and decision support, risk stratification); 2) knowledge generation (pattern recognition, greater knowledge of rare diseases, greater understanding of causality); 3) system efficiency (optimisation of care pathways, prediction of do not attends, identification of staffing requirements).

Associated processing activities to the mentioned purposes involve the collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure, by transmission, dissemination, or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, reassure or destruction.

The creation of the datasets refers to the moment when the data are collected. With regards to retrospective data, that moment took place at the time when the partner first collected it. With regard to new or prospective data, the data set is created when the data is generated or collected by the clinical partner.¹⁷⁴

Figure 2 – The processing of datasets in MES-CoBraD

¹⁷⁴ The MES-CoBraD Data flow(s) are further explained in ENG. D5.2 - Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security, (2023).

The processing of RWD collected by medical partners passes through the edge module, which is the link between the clinical site and the MES-CoBraD platform. Only after undergoing depersonalisation through edge module, data is uploaded to the MES-CoBraD platform.

Processing activities performed at the clinical site are carried out on the original dataset, while processing activities performed at a platform level, solely involves de-personalised datasets.

The processing of personal data pre-anonymisation only occurs at the clinical site, so the only processing activity that takes place on the datasets at the edge module, is the de-personalisation itself (pseudonymisation/anonymisation). The restriction of the personal data availability only within the clinical Local Area Network ensures that not even clinical partners are enabled to process personal data at a platform level.

The CJEU has addressed the debate over the use of data for the purposes of training AI tools in the case *Nacionalinis visuomenės v. Valstybinė duomenų*.¹⁷⁵ In this case the CJEU addressed the question on whether personal data used for the purposes of IT testing would qualify or not as a processing activity. In that respect the CJEU concluded that the key aspect is not the purpose of the processing but the nature of the data. As a result, if the data used can re-identify an individual then the activities would be considered processing under the GDPR. It follows that when qualifying the existence of a processing activity at a cloud level, we need to refer to the assessment of the data resulting from the MES-CoBraD depersonalization module.¹⁷⁶

4.5 CONTROLLERS, PROCESSORS AND RECIPIENTS

4.5.1 WHO IS A CONTROLLER?

Controller	controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law
Article 4 (7) of the GDPR	

The definitory aspect of controllership is the capacity to determine or influence the purposes and means of the processing. Whether this power derives from a legal designation or from factual circumstances must be decided on a case-by-case basis.

A controller can be linked to either a single activity within the processing lifecycle of a dataset or to several sets of operations. In practice, this means that the control exercised by a particular entity may extend to the entirety of processing at issue but may also be limited to a particular stage in the processing.¹⁷⁷

Jurisdictionally, the representative of the controller must be established “in one of the Member States where the data subjects, whose personal data are processed in relation to the offering of goods and services to them, or whose behaviour is monitored” (Article 27 of the GDPR).¹⁷⁸ If no representative is designated, legal action can still be initiated against the controller or the processor themselves.¹⁷⁹

¹⁷⁵ CJEU (Grand Chamber), judgment of 5 December 2023, Case C 683/21, *Nacionalinis visuomenės v. Valstybinė duomenų*; ECLI:EU:C:2023:949

¹⁷⁶ See section 4.6 of this document and section 3.3 of the D2.2 Data Management Plan.

¹⁷⁷ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 07/2020 p 40; See also Explanatory Report of Modernised Convention 108, para. 22.

¹⁷⁸ General Data Protection Regulation, Art. 27 (1).

¹⁷⁹ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 07/2020, p 40

4.5.2 WHAT IS A PROCESSOR?

Processor Article 4 (8) of the GDPR ¹⁸⁰	'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;
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The processor is a separate entity of the controller, who is entrusted with the execution of certain tasks for the benefit of the controller. The commands might be general or specific, what truly defines the role of the processor is its influence on the decision-making process. Accordingly, the processor cannot process data without the permission of the controller and its instructions. A processor will infringe the GDPR if it ignores or exceeds the controller's instructions. In the event of surpassing its mandate, the processor would be considered a controller for that processing. Furthermore, ignoring the controller's instructions can lead to sanctions for infringing the GDPR.¹⁸¹

The qualification of processor and controller is always restricted to specific processing activities. This means that processors and controllers can have distinct roles with respect to different personal data sets and their respective processing lifecycles.

4.5.3 WHAT IS A JOINT CONTROLLERSHIP?

Joint controller Article 26 of the GDPR ¹⁸²	Where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they shall be joint controllers. They shall in a transparent manner determine their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under this Regulation, in particular as regards the exercising of the rights of the data subject and their respective duties to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14, by means of an arrangement between them unless, and in so far as, the respective responsibilities of the controllers are determined by Union or Member State law to which the controllers are subject. The arrangement may designate a contact point for data subjects.
	2. The arrangement referred to in paragraph 1 shall duly reflect the respective roles and relationships of the joint controllers vis-à-vis the data subjects. The essence of the arrangement shall be made available to the data subject.
	3. Irrespective of the terms of the arrangement referred to in paragraph 1, the data subject may exercise his or her rights under this Regulation in respect of and against each of the controllers.

In the event there are two or more actors jointly determining the purpose and means of a processing activity, they are to be considered joint controllers.¹⁸³ In practice, "jointly" must be interpreted as meaning "together with" or "not alone." As in the case of controllers and processors, joint controllership must be assessed on a factual and not theoretical basis. The criteria for joint controllership and the extent to which two or more actors jointly exercise control over a data processing activity may take different forms and they do not necessarily need to carry equal responsibilities. In this respect, the EDPB distinguishes between two types of joint participation by two or more entities:¹⁸⁴

- › Common decisions: when the decision the process is taken jointly with the more common understanding of the term jointly.

¹⁸⁰ A definition that is also shared by the Modernised Convention 108 (Article 2 (f)).

¹⁸¹ Article 28(10) of the GDPR.

¹⁸² A definition shared in the modernised convention 108 (Article 2 (f) of the Modernised Convention 108

¹⁸³ Similarly, the Explanatory Report of Modernised Convention 108 states that multiple controllers or co-controllership is also possible within the CoE framework.

¹⁸⁴ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 07/2020

- › Converging decisions: when decisions over the purpose and means of the processing complement each other and are necessary for the processing to take place in such manner that they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means of processing. Convergence is found in those cases where ‘processing’ would not be possible insofar that the processing carried by each party is inextricably linked.

The joint controller’s regime on the basis of converging decisions differs from a controller-processor relationship insofar the processor does not process the data for its own purposes but conducts the processing on behalf of the controller.

4.5.4 DATA PROCESSING RESPONSIBILITY

The following sections assess the different elements forming the concept of the controller, following the EDPB’s deconstruction on the concept and applying to the particular case of MES-CoBraD: 1) “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body” 2) “who determines” 3) “alone or jointly with others” 4) the “purposes and means” of the processing of personal data.

4.5.4.1 Processing entities in MES-CoBraD

There are three separate groups of entities participating in the MES-CoBraD joint research project. According to their role, they can be separated in 1. Medical Partners; 2. Technical Partners; and 3. Supporting Partners.

As explained, the medical partners lead the collection and exploitation of RWD, and, jointly with technical partners, decide on the components and functioning of the MES-CoBraD platform. Additionally, the consortium is completed by the third category of entities leading legal, dissemination and administrative activities.

While all partners decide jointly to undertake and participate in the scientific research, not all partners are equally responsible for all data processing activities taking place during the project.

4.5.4.2 What does “determining” mean?

The influence of an actor over a data processing activity is defined by the exercise of decision-making power in its means and purposes. In that way, the controller appears as the entity deciding certain key elements about the processing. When defining the controllership of certain processing, it is necessary to look at the specific processing operations in question and understand who participates in their definition and execution.

The concept of controller is “functional” and based on a factual assessment of the processing activities. In practice, this means that what determines the controllership is not the type of entity but its influence over the activities in the data processing lifecycle.¹⁸⁵

The entity(ies) exerting a decision-making power over the purposes and means of the processing will be considered controller(s). This does not exclude that the processor who only acts on command, might in certain occasions, also be able to make some decisions in relation to the processing.¹⁸⁶

4.5.4.3 What does “purpose and means” mean?

The principle of purpose limitation, states that “data must be collected for specified, explicit and

¹⁸⁵ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 07/2020. pp 11, and 13

¹⁸⁶ The EDPB has recognised the need for further guidance when it comes to borderline cases between controllers and processors. In those cases, answering the “why” and the “how”, should entail the qualification of an entity as a controller and to what extent a processor may make decisions of its own.

legitimate purposes and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes”¹⁸⁷. The concepts of purpose and means appear to address such key aspects:

The purpose anticipates an intended outcome for which data processing operations occurs. In other words, the purpose of processing answers” why” the processing takes place. In MES-CoBraD, the purpose of the processing activities is determined by the consortium compromise to collaborate in scientific research in order to develop the MES-CoBraD platform.

The means determine the methods how a result is obtained, or an end is achieved. Considering the flexibility recognised by the EDPB, what must be clarified is which decisions on the means should lead controllership and which ones can be left at the discretion of the processor.¹⁸⁸ From this a distinction is drawn between essential and non-essential means.

On the one hand, “essential means” are considered traditionally and inherently reserved to the controller. Together with the purpose of processing, the essential means are also intricately linked to the question of whether the processing is lawful, necessary, and proportionate:¹⁸⁹

- › Which data shall be processed?
- › Whose personal data are being processed?
- › For how long shall they be processed?
- › Who shall have access to them?

On the other hand, the processor can also determine ‘non-essential means’. Non-essential means concern more practical aspects of implementation, such as the choice for a particular type of hardware or software, the detailed security measures, which may be left to the processor to decide on.

4.5.5 CONTROLLERSHIP: ROLE AND OBLIGATIONS IN MES-COBRA D

The MES-CoBraD platform is governed by the **MES-CoBraD Grant Agreement**, and the **MES-CoBraD Consortium Agreement**. Clinical Partners processing datasets in MES-CoBraD are solely responsible for the collection and further processing of the datasets they decide to share with the consortium. As part of their obligations as controllers, partners in MES-CoBraD need to choose a legal basis linked to the datasets depersonalised and later uploaded to the platform.

Due to the special sensitivity of the personal data involved and in line with the principle of transparency and accountability, it was proposed that the consortium entered into a data processing arrangement to clearly identify and allocate the relevant responsibilities of each partner. In that sense **the MES-CoBraD Data Processing Policy** was adopted and incorporated in the Data Management Plan (D2.2. section 3).

Moreover, the consortium operates based on a **Compliance statement (s3.1.5)**;¹⁹⁰ based on this medical partners, Healthcare Organisations, and the medical professionals in particular, as well as technical partners, commit themselves to comply with all international and national applicable laws and protocols regarding the processing of the datasets used during the research.¹⁹¹

As explained in Section 3.3 of the DMP and further detailed in section 4.6 below, the data stored by the medical partners at the clinical site are not accessible to other organisations or individuals. Only data that

¹⁸⁷ Article 5 (b) of the GDPR

¹⁸⁸ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 07/2020 pp. 15.

¹⁸⁹ These aspects are defined in the D3.2 Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation – v2. Information concerning the storage rules of the data processed in the MES-CoBraD platform and the access to the same is also provided in D2.2 Data Management Plan -v1 project.

¹⁹⁰ See D2.2 Data Management Plan section 3.1.5 Nomination of Data Protection Officer and declaration of compliance.

¹⁹¹ The signed statements are documented in the D2.1 CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk report v1

has undergone depersonalisation process is uploaded and shared with partners. As a result, when determining controllership, a distinction must be made between the data stored by each medical partner in their own premises and the “depersonalized” data stored in the data lake.

With regards to depersonalized data stored at a platform level, all partners, accessing depersonalized datasets have expressly committed to not attempt the reidentification of the data subjects from whom the depersonalized information might refer to.¹⁹² Only the partner who possesses the pseudonym key is capable and allowed to identify the data subject, and therefore remains the sole controller of the data.¹⁹³ It follows that for partners other than the controller of the original dataset, accessing depersonalized datasets means accessing non personal data. As a result, no controllership obligations are derived.

4.6 DEPERSONALISATION OF PERSONAL DATA

This section elaborates on the notions of anonymization and pseudonymization under the GDPR and its relation to the research in MES-CoBraD. First, it offers a theoretical introduction to the concepts of anonymization and pseudonymisation. Second, it assesses the de-personalisation module envisaged for the MES-CoBraD platform level and its implications from a data protection perspective.

4.6.1 WHAT DOES ANONYMISATION MEAN?

Anonymisation is not defined in the GDPR. Nevertheless, anonymisation is regarded as a processing activity the outcome of which is the elimination of all identifying elements from a set of personal data. This means that for data to be anonymous, no element may be left in information which could be, by exercising reasonable effort, serve to re-identify the person(s) from which a piece of data is originally related. When data have been successfully anonymised, they are no longer personal data and data protection legislation no longer applies.

From an objective approach, once the technique/combination of techniques has been applied, the anonymization process should make any processing of personal data impossible. The EDPB and the EDPS suggest that data “only lose its qualification as personal data if the anonymity is absolute and no longer any means reasonably likely to be implemented allows us to go back to break anonymity”.¹⁹⁴

As it has been explained, this static or objective approach to identifiability contradicts the recent CJEU interpretations over the concept of personal data, which is based on the context, and involves an assessment based on the data, but also, the recipient(s), the technical and legal means available and the infrastructure where the data are stored.¹⁹⁵

As explained above (see Section 4.2), CJEU’s reliance on the relative approach enables a more flexible understanding of anonymisation. In practice, this means that a dataset might be assessed differently depending on who and how a recipient has access to it. Whenever the technical and organisational means applied to a data set makes it “reasonably impossible” for a recipient to re-identify a natural person, that data set would remain anonymous for that recipient. At the same time, the controller will remain responsible for the observation of its data protection obligations towards the data subject insofar those same safeguards do not prevent it from carrying out a re-identification.

¹⁹² See D2.2 Data Management Plan, section 3.1.7 MES-CoBraD Data Processing Policy (C-4)

¹⁹³ See ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final (2023).

¹⁹⁴ EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 04/2020 on the use of location data and contact tracing tools in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak on 15 December 2020.

¹⁹⁵ Stalla-Bourdillon and Knight, ‘Anonymous Data v. Personal Data – A False Debate’.

4.6.2 ANONYMISATION TECHNIQUES

There is no single anonymisation formula applicable to all cases. This means that finding an optimal technique or combination of techniques for the anonymisation of personal data should be decided on a case-by-case basis. The EDPB identifies two main families of anonymization techniques, randomization and generalization of data and warns that both techniques “have gaps, even if each of them may be appropriate, depending on the circumstances and the context.”¹⁹⁶ When choosing to apply a given technique, three key anonymization risks must be considered:

3. Individualization, which is the ability to isolate some or all of the records identifying an individual from the data set.
4. Correlation, which consists of the ability to link together, at least, two records relating to the same data subject or to a group of data subjects (either in the same database or in two different databases).
5. Inference, which is the possibility of inferring, with a high degree of probability, the value of an attribute from the values of a set of other attributes.¹⁹⁷

A successful anonymization process that meets the three aforementioned criteria would resist identification attempts using the means most likely to be reasonably implemented by the data controller or third parties. Where one of the criteria is not fulfilled, a thorough assessment of the identified risks should be carried out and, where appropriate, a combination of techniques should be used to enhance the reliability of the result.¹⁹⁸ The anonymization of data can take place in several steps depending on the case, what matters is the ultimate result. Whenever anonymisation is not possible, proper pseudonymisation should be the number one safety measure to implement.

4.6.3 WHAT DOES PSEUDONYMISATION MEAN?

Pseudonymization Article 4(5) of the GDPR ¹⁹⁹	<i>the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person;</i>
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Pseudonymisation is a processing activity aimed at mitigating the risks towards the data subject by making its identification impossible without the use of additional information. Differently from anonymization, it does not aim to prevent a data subject from being identifiable. In that sense, it is regarded an appropriate technical measure for enhancing data protection and is explicitly mentioned for the design and security of its data processing.

As a safeguard and a security measure for controllers and processors, pseudonymisation represents a practical implementation of some main data protection principles, particularly, purpose limitation, data minimisation, and data protection by default and by design.²⁰⁰ Due to its value in reducing risks for data

¹⁹⁶ See EDPB former Article 29 Working Party (2016), Opinion on Anonymisation Techniques, 0829/14/EN WP216, p.11.

¹⁹⁷ Ibid., p. 13.

¹⁹⁸ Ibid. pp. 26-27.

¹⁹⁹ Pseudonymization is not explicitly mentioned in the legal definition of the CoE Modernized Convention 108. However, the Explanatory Report of Modernized Convention 108 clearly states that “the use of a pseudonym or of any digital identifier/ digital identity does not lead to anonymization of the data as the data subject can still be identifiable or individualized”. Therefore, “[p]seudonymous data is [...] to be considered a personal data [...]” covered by Council of Europe, (2018) Modernized Convention 108.

²⁰⁰ Article 6(4) of the GDPR

subjects, it should also be considered decisive with regard to access management policies.”²⁰¹

In practice, pseudonymisation may involve removing unique identifiers such as names, social security numbers, and dates of birth, which can be interpreted as enabling the processing of anonymous data when the recipient of a pseudonymised dataset cannot under a test of reasonable likelihood access to the pseudonymous keys.²⁰²

4.6.4 THE ASSESSMENT OF THE MES-COBRA D “DE PERSONALISATION” METHOD

A fundamental element of the project is enabling a secure re-utilisation of datasets. The de-personalisation module has been developed and installed at each clinical site, to ensure that the processing at the MES-CoBraD platform by partners other than the clinical partner holding the original dataset, is performed exclusively on de-personalised data.

In MES-CoBraD the process allowing the use of RWD in anonymous manner at the platform level is addressed by leveraging static (i.e. removal of identifiers such as birthdate, name or address)) and dynamic approaches (i.e. randomisation of data within the datasets), paying attention to several aspects related to issues such as the reidentification risk and to the quality and utility of the final anonymised dataset. Based on balancing the scientific needs in the field of healthcare and the objective of the platform to only store anonymised data for its recipients, datasets are abstracted in order to avoid impacting their value from a research perspective.²⁰³

Depersonalisation in MES-CoBraD operates in five steps, combining both automatic and manual processes. Whether the module will render the personal data anonymous or pseudonymous cannot be concluded beforehand, and it depends on the result obtained after an adequate execution of each of the five depersonalisation steps.

Table 8 MES-CoBraD depersonalization steps

	Description
Step 1- Patient’s data collection and preparation	Scientists and Clinicians preliminarily prepare patients’ data to be submitted to the depersonalisation module. In MES-CoBraD, this is done by the medical partners at their premises.
Step 2- De personnalisation module configuration	Scientists and clinicians install the depersonalisation module. In MES-CoBraD. The depersonalisation module will contemplate different plugins for each type of RWD. Depending on the dataset the process of depersonalisation might involve the pseudonymisation or anonymisation of data. ²⁰⁴
Step 3- Data de-personalisation through the module	Having selected the different datasets that need de-personalisation, identifiers are removed from the dataset and uploaded to the data lake. Certain types of RWD will also have biometrically identifiable

²⁰¹ G. Verhenneman et al., ‘How GDPR Enhances Transparency and Fosters Pseudonymisation in Academic Medical Research’, *European Journal of Health Law* 27, no. 1 (4 March 2020): 35–57,

²⁰² S. Lusignan, ‘Effective pseudonymisation and explicit statements of public interest to ensure the benefits of sharing health data for research, quality improvement and health service management outweigh the risks,’ *Informatics in Primary Care* 21(2) (2014) 61-63.

²⁰³ MES-CoBraD Grant Agreement, p.47; What this entails in practice has been further elaborated by the technical Consortium partners responsible for overseeing the creation and curation of the common database and encryption protocols (WP5).

²⁰⁴ See D5.2 Section 8.2.1 pseudonymisation plugins

	<p>features removed (e.g., defacing of dicom [MRI] images) through edge module tools.</p>
<p>Step 4- Manual verification of the de-personalised dataset</p>	<p>Once an output is obtained, a notification alert is displayed to the user requesting confirmation on whether the data identifiers have been effectively removed.</p> <p>For the purposes of the MES-CoBraD project, only the medical partners will be in charge of verifying that the data has been successfully de-personalised as intended. If the de-personalisation has not been completely successful, the clinician or scientist will be able to remove the relevant data manually.</p> <p>A risk of potential data breaches when partners upload information containing personal data has been identified. At the time of writing the following safeguards have been adopted to mitigate risks:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incorporation of a verification messages to the user uploading data. 2. In the pop-up the clinician will see the dataset twice: one de-personalised another clean. 3. Encourage the clinicians to check whether the data they had uploaded has adequately removed its identifiers. 4. Possibility to refine the plugging to avoid submitting personal data to the cloud. <p>Based on the reliance on the human factor it has been recommended that the efficiency of the de-personalisation plugins should be periodically audited and the clinician checks upon upload should be recorded by the platform.</p>
<p>Step 5- Verified data submission</p>	<p>After revision and confirmation, the data is automatically uploaded into the platform. For the duration of the MES-CoBraD project, this data will only be available on a need-to-know basis, including, when necessary, to those partners involved in the development of certain MES-CoBraD tools.</p> <p>Only after its de-personalisation the RWD obtained by clinical partners is stored at the MES-CoBraD central storage. Once de-personalised and securely stored at the Platform, the information is accessible to Consortium partners on a need-to-know basis.</p>

Pursuant to these five steps, once the data is uploaded to the data lake, only the medical partner uploading the data can re-identify the data uploaded with the original dataset stored at the clinical site. The uploaded data remains anonymous to the rest of the partners who access the de-personalized

dataset. Data are instantly de-personalised, which means that the edge module only retains temporary memory of the data pre-depersonalisation.²⁰⁵

If the processing at the depersonalization module successfully renders the dataset anonymous for the potential recipients of the dataset, the data uploaded is no longer personal data, and therefore those recipients do not process personal data at the MES-CoBraD platform. Alternatively, if it is considered “reasonably likely” for the potential recipients to re-identify the individuals from whom the depersonalized datasets come from, then the data remain personal data and the GDPR will continue to apply to those processing activities performed on the dataset uploaded into the platform.

During the project, the risk of reidentification of the data has been assessed by means of “test of reasonable likelihood of identification” recital 26 of the GDPR. To that end an individual assessment is performed on each type of dataset of RWD processed in MES-CoBraD taking into account its applicable “depersonalization” technique. The test must take into account “the time, effort or resource needed in light of the nature of the data, the context of their use, the available re-identification technologies and related costs” (recital 26 of the GDPR). Therefore, to operationalize Recital 26 we must ask:

Q1- Whether reidentification is technically possible.

Q2- Whether the reidentification is legally possible.

For the assessment of depersonalization in MES-CoBraD, **five objective** criteria have been identified to motivate the “reasonable likelihood of reidentification”.²⁰⁶

- 1- The Recipient of the depersonalised data: partners on a need-to-know basis.
- 2- The information in the data uploaded into the platform and made available to recipients: de-personalised datasets.
- 3- The legal means at disposal of recipients of depersonalised datasets to attempt re-identification of data subjects.: none. Joint agreement not to reidentify.
- 4- The technical means of a “motivated intruder” to reidentify a data subject: unreasonable.
- 5- Effectiveness of the de-personalisation module.

Based on the technical insights provided by the partners, it has been considered that technical safeguards have been put in place to prevent the identification of the uploaded datasets. In addition, it is observed that partners do not have the legal means to access the controllers pseudonymized database. Furthermore, all partners have explicitly committed to not attempt the re-identification pursuant to the MES-CoBraD data processing policy.²⁰⁷

To conclude, considering the information examined in this deliverable and that reported in the MES-CoBraD DMP, it can be confirmed that uploaded datasets are depersonalised in a manner that ensures that, during the project, no recipient of datasets processes personal data at the MES- COBRaD platform.

By design, the processing of personal data at the MES-CoBRaD platform can only take place from the edge module installed at the clinical site of the clinical partner, who is the controller of the original dataset.

4.7 DATA PROTECTION PRINCIPLES IN MES-COBRAD

The main effect of data protection frameworks is the obligation of controllers and processors to observe

²⁰⁵ ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final (2023), section 5.2.2 and s8.2

²⁰⁶ See D2.2 Data Management Plan section 3.3.5.

²⁰⁷ Data Processing policy C4

and comply with its principles. Since the first version of the CoBraD ethical and legal Framework was submitted, this section has been used to raise awareness on the need to comply with certain data protection requirements, but equally important, it has also sought to promote a data protection conscience in the design of the platform.

In that sense, the project’s compliance with its data protection obligations relies greatly on the design of the MEs-CoBraD platform itself. The separation between **edge module** at clinical site and the cloud platform effectively mitigates the likeliness of risks on personal data processed during the project.

As it has been explained, the fact that clinical sites are isolated via the edge module guarantees that personal data is exclusively available only within the clinical Local Area Network.²⁰⁸ This facilitates the compliance with data protection principles, in particular those of purpose limitation, data minimisation and security. At the heart of this is the depersonalisation module located at the edge module

Another fundamental aspect of the MES-CoBraD data protection by design approach, is the project’s emphasis on depersonalisation of personal data. This represents a tangible example on how technical partners have operationalised data minimisation and purpose limitation principles into the processing architecture of the platform.

4.7.1 DEROGATIONS UNDER THE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH REGIME

The GDPR understands that the processing of personal data, including special categories of data, for the purpose of scientific research is a desirable and a priori compatible with its provisions. To that end it grants a special regime with derogations from data protection principles. This regime is conditioned by the controller’s adoption of adequate technical and organisational safeguards ensuring data minimisation as well as other principles.²⁰⁹

The GDPR’s defines scientific research in its article 89, clarifying its scope in its recital 159 as follow: “the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be interpreted in a broad manner including, for example, technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research”.²¹⁰

<p>Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes</p> <p>Article 89 GDPR</p>	<p>1. Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing, which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.</p> <p>2. Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far</p>
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²⁰⁸ ENG. (2023). D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final

²⁰⁹ The EDPS has recognised the value of coupling information from registries in medical research and social sciences. However it alerts on the risks of understanding this regime in a way that “ the essence of the right to data protection is emptied out, and this includes data subject rights, appropriate organisational and technical measures against accidental or unlawful destruction, loss or alteration, and the supervision of an independent authority”. EDPS, Assessing the necessity of measures that limit the fundamental right to the protection of personal data: A Toolkit, 11 April 2017, and discussion (footnote 8) of CJEU judgments in Schrems, CJEU Joined Cases C-293/12 and C-594/12 Digital Rights Ireland 8 April 2014 and Tele2 Sverige AB

²¹⁰The EDPB in its endorsed opinion on consent 17/EN WP259 , has narrowed it down arguing that its scope should not be stretched beyond its common meaning and interpreted as a research project set up in accordance with relevant sector-related methodological and ethical standards, in conformity with good practice.

See also Relevant recitals 156, 157, 158, and 159	as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.
	3. Where personal data are processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.
	4. Where processing referred to in paragraphs 2 and 3 serves at the same time another purpose, the derogations shall apply only to processing for the purposes referred to in those paragraphs.

4.7.2 LAWFULNESS OF PROCESSING

Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency (Art. 5(1) (a) of the GDPR)	Personal data shall be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject
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The definition of lawfulness in the context of a data processing activity includes three elements, the legal basis, fairness, and its transparency. During the project, these aspects must be assessed at two levels: i) at the clinical site level and ii) at a platform level: where the data is stored after being de-personalised and uploaded.

4.7.2.1 Legal basis to process MES CoBraD RWD: consent, public interest, or legitimate interest

According to the principle of lawfulness, all processing of personal data shall be based on one or multiple grounds set out in Article 6(1) of the GDPR:

- (a) the data subject has given free, voluntary, and specific consent.
- (b) performance of a contract to which data subject is a party.
- (c) compliance with a legal obligation of the controller.
- (d) protection the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person.
- (e) the activity carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority.
- (f) legitimate interests pursued by the controller or third party, as long as it is not overridden by fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject.

Among these, explicit consent, public interest, and legitimate interest are the three preferred options for the EDPB.²¹¹ The decision to rely on one or the other will need to consider several aspects of the RWD, including its type, level of sensitiveness and the adequacy towards purpose compatibility.

Explicit consent: (Article 6(1)(a) + Article 9(2)(a)), + Article 89 (1)

Consent to participate in research activity (i.e. clinical trial or test) must be distinguished from the consent as a legal basis for the processing of personal data. Under the GDPR, a valid consent must be freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous, and explicit. In the event the controller wishes to rely on consent for the processing of sensitive data in the course of a research activity, the data controllers should duly consider the WP29 Guidelines on consent, and check if all the conditions are met.²¹²

²¹¹ EDPB, (2020), Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak.

²¹² WP29, (2018), Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article 29 Working-Party, WP259 rev.01, 17EN, page 27 (endorsed by the EDPB).

Due to the complexities in reaching and maintaining all the requirements of explicit consent through the various stages of a research project, the EDPB has warned data controllers about the risks of relying exclusively on individuals' consent as a legal basis. Alternatively, to consent the EDPB suggests the lawful grounds of processing provided under public interest or legitimate interest are more appropriate.²¹³

Public interest: (Article 6(1)(e)) + Article 9(2)(i)), + Article 89 (1)

The processing of personal data by data controllers could be considered “necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest” pursuant to Article 6(1)(e) GDPR. Article 6(3) GDPR further provides that this basis shall be laid down by Union or Member State law and that the purpose of the processing shall be laid down in that legal basis.²¹⁴

The processing of personal data could be considered as necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest when the conduct of clinical trials or tests directly falls within the mandate, missions, and tasks vested in a public or private body by national law. If applicable, the relevant medical partner will need to assess this considering its own national legislation.

Legitimate interests of the controller: (Article 6(1)(f)) + Article 9(2)(i) or (j)+ Article 89 (1)

The legitimate interests for the processing of special categories of data will apply only when Article 9 GDPR provides for a specific derogation from the general prohibition to process special categories of data. In the case of MES-CoBraD for “scientific purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law” (Article 9(2)(j)).²¹⁵ The GDPR allows for the processing of sensitive data for medical research if it is authorised by law, it adheres to the principle of proportionality, respects the essence of the right to protection of personal data, and provides specific safeguards for the protection of individuals' fundamental rights and interests (Article 9(1)(j) of GDPR). As recognised by the EDPB, reliance on legitimate interest as the legal ground, is considered advisable for the processing of sensitive data when conducting general medical research.²¹⁶

The national laws regulating the derogations concerning the processing of personal data concerning health for the purposes of scientific research have not been fully unified within the EU.

Legal basis at MES-CoBraD

At the time of collection, the relevant medical partner identifies the adequate legal basis according to EU and its national law. It will need to ensure that they have a legal basis for the processing of RWD, and that its further processing during MES-CoBraD is not incompatible with its original purpose.²¹⁷ In light of the principle of purpose limitation, further processing and purpose compatibility will need to be evaluated taking into account the technical and organisational measures adopted by the controller.²¹⁸

4.7.2.1.1 *Lawfulness by design and by default*

Lawfulness-Key design and default elements

²¹³ *ibid*

²¹⁴ Recital (54) of the GDPR states that “the processing of special categories of personal data may be necessary for reasons of public interest in the areas of public health without consent of the data subject. Such processing should be subject to suitable and specific measures so as to protect the rights and freedoms of natural persons.”

²¹⁵ As indicated by the EDPB, the processing operations purely related to research activities cannot be derived from a legal obligation, namely a contract.

²¹⁶ EDPB, 21 April, 2020, Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak.

²¹⁷ In the case of existing or retrospective data, the purpose and the legal basis that enabled its storage and subsequent processing based on its national legislation will need to be identified. For new or prospective data, the purpose and the legal basis will have to be chosen at the time of collection based on the relevant national law. See MES-CoBraD D2.2 Data Management Plan-v1; see also upcoming iterations of the present deliverable.

²¹⁸ Article 89 of the GDPR

1.	Relevance	The controller of the dataset should be responsible for applying the correct legal basis to the processing, prior to the upload into the platform.
2.	Differentiation	There is a need to differentiate between the legal basis used for processing activities for medical or healthcare purposes and those aimed at scientific research.
3.	Specified purpose	The appropriate legal basis must be clearly connected to the specific purpose of processing.
4.	Necessary	Processing must be necessary for the purpose to be lawful. It is an objective test that involves an accurate assessment of realistic alternatives for achieving the purpose.
5.	Autonomy	The data subject should be granted the highest degree of autonomy as possible with respect to control over personal data.
6.	Consent Withdrawal	In the event consent is the chosen legal basis, the processing shall facilitate withdrawal of consent. Withdrawal shall be as easy as giving consent. If not, any given consent is not valid.
7.	Balancing of interests	Where legitimate interests are the legal basis, the controller must carry out an objectively weighted balancing of interests. There shall be measures and safeguards to mitigate the negative impact on the data subjects, and the controller should disclose their assessment of the balancing of interests.
8.	Predetermination	The legal basis shall be established before the processing takes place.
9.	Cessation	If the legal basis ceases to apply, the processing shall cease accordingly. Only the medical partner as controller of the data can adequately comply with this responsibility.
10.	Adjust	If there is a valid change of legal basis for the processing, the actual processing must be adjusted in accordance with the new legal basis.
11.	Default configurations	Processing must be limited to what the legal basis strictly gives grounds for.
12.	Allocation of responsibility	Whenever joint controllership is envisaged, the parties must apportion in a clear and transparent way their respective responsibilities vis-à-vis the data subject.

4.7.2.2 Fairness

Fair processing governs primarily the relationship between the controller and the data subject.²¹⁹ Controllers should notify data subjects and the general public that they will process data in a lawful and transparent manner and must be able to proactively demonstrate the compliance of processing operations with the GDPR. When required, data subjects should be aware of potential risks.²²⁰

4.7.2.2.1 Fairness by design and by default

Fairness-Key design and default elements		
13.	Autonomy	Data subjects shall be granted the highest degree of autonomy possible with respect to control over their personal data. With regards to the data processing at MES-CoBraD platform, the derogations in the special regime of article 89 will be considered.
14.	Interaction	Data subjects must be able to communicate and exercise their rights with the

²¹⁹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe (FRA), (2018), Handbook on Data European Protection Law, p. 118

²²⁰ Ibid.

		controller. Regarding the data processing at MES-CoBraD platform, the derogations in the special regime of article 89 will need to be considered.
15.	Expectation	Processing should correspond with data subjects' expectations.
16.	Non-discrimination	Controllers must not discriminate against data subjects. At a development level, this should be considered when defining the exploitation capabilities of the MES-CoBraD platform.
17.	Non-exploitation	The controller shall not exploit the needs or vulnerabilities of data subjects. At a development level, this should be considered when defining the exploitation capabilities of the MES-CoBraD platform.
18.	Consumer choice	The controller should not "lock in" their users. Whenever a service or a good is personalized or proprietary, it may create a lock-in to the service or good. If it is difficult for the data subject to change controllers due to this, which may not be fair.
19.	Power balance	Asymmetric power balances shall be avoided or mitigated when possible. Controllers should not transfer the risks of the enterprise to the data subjects.
20.	Respect to the rights and freedoms	The controller must respect the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects and implement appropriate measures and safeguards to not violate these rights and freedoms.

4.7.2.3 Transparency

The requirement of transparency establishes an obligation for the controller to adopt appropriate measures for keeping the data subjects informed, in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, about how their data are being used ²²¹.

The principle of transparency requires that any information and communication relating to the processing of those personal data be easily accessible and easy to understand, and that clear and plain language be used. Those principal concerns, in particular, information to the data subjects on the identity of the controller and the purposes of the processing and further information to ensure fair and transparent processing in respect of the natural persons concerns and their right to obtain confirmation and communication of personal data concerning them which are being processed.

Natural persons should be made aware of risks, rules, safeguards, and rights in relation to the processing of personal data and how to exercise their rights in relation to such processing. In particular, the specific purposes for which personal data are processed should be explicit and legitimate and determined at the time of the collection of the personal data.²²²

The principle of transparency is closely related with the right to information observed in article 13 and 14 of the GDPR. In the context of the project, activities the derogations foreseen in the special regime must be contemplated.

4.7.2.3.1 Transparency by design and by default

Transparency-Key design and default elements		
21.	Clarity	Information shall be in clear and plain language, concise and intelligible.
22.	Semantics	Communication shall have a clear meaning to the audience in question.
23.	Accessibility	Information shall be easily accessible for the data subject.

²²¹ Article 12(1), GDPR. Also see European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law, p. 120.

²²² Recital 39 of the GDPR.

24.	Contextual	Information shall be provided at the relevant time and in the appropriate form.
25.	Relevance	Information shall be relevant and applicable to the specific data subject.
26.	Universal design	Information shall be accessible to all, this includes use of machine readable languages to facilitate and automate readability and clarity.
27.	Comprehensible	Data subjects shall have a fair understanding of what they can expect with regards to the processing of their personal data, particularly when the data subjects are children or other vulnerable groups.
28.	Multi Chanel	Information should be provided in different channels and media, beyond the textual, to increase the probability for the information to effectively reach the data subject

4.7.3 PURPOSE LIMITATION: FURTHER PROCESSING AND THE PRESUMPTION OF COMPATIBILITY

Purpose limitation Article 5(1) (b) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');
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The principle of purpose limitation requires the identification of a specified explicit and legitimate purpose prior a processing begins²²³. With regards to retrospective data as well as for prospective data collected for a purpose different from scientific research, the processing in MES-CoBraD of data will need to satisfy the requirement of purpose compatibility. This might present problems in those cases where the controller relies on consent as a legal basis for processing data.²²⁴

Further processing is allowed when it is done for archiving, public interest, scientific, historical, statistical or research purposes, as soon as technical and organisational measures are adopted.²²⁵ In that sense, under the special regime, the controller is able to further process the data without the need for a new legal basis.

This said, it should be noted that, even when the presumption of compatibility applies, the scientific research making use of “re-purposed data,” will need to be conducted in compliance with all other relevant applicable provisions of data protection.

4.7.3.1 Purpose limitation by design and by default

Purpose Limitation- Key design and default elements		
29.	Predetermination	The legitimate purposes must be determined before the design of the processing.
30.	Specificity	The purposes must be specific to the processing and make it explicitly clear why personal data is being processed.
31.	Purpose orientation	The purpose of processing should guide the design of the processing and set processing boundaries.

²²³ Article 5.1(b) of the GDPR

²²⁴ For more on consent and issues associated with the secondary use of data see: P. Boddington, L. Curren, J. Kaye, N. Kanellopoulou, K. Melham, H. Gowansa and N. Hawkinsa, ‘Consent Forms in Genomics: The Difference between Law and Practice,’ *The European Journal of Health Law* 18 (2011) 491-519.; See also Kosta, E. (2013). *Consent in European data protection law.* (Nijhoff Studies in European Union Law; No. 3). Martinus Nijhoff.

²²⁵ Article 89(1) of the GDPR

32.	Necessity	The purpose determines what personal data is necessary for the processing.
33.	Compatibility	Any new purpose must be compatible with the original purpose for which the data was collected and guide relevant changes in design.
34.	Limit further processing	The controller should not connect datasets or perform any further processing for new incompatible purposes.
35.	Review	The controller must regularly review whether the processing is necessary for the purposes for which the data was collected and evaluate the design against purpose limitation.
36.	Technical limitations of reuse	The controller should use technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.

4.7.4 DATA MINIMISATION

Data minimisation Article 5 (1) (c) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
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The principle of data minimisation aims to “minimise” the data processed in a way that only the data that is adequate, relevant, and strictly necessary for the purpose is processed. As such, it represents a practical implementation of the principle of necessity.

The minimisation of data can also refer to the degree of identification of a data subject²²⁶. It follows that whenever it is not necessary to identify, the data should be de-personalised as much as possible. Anonymisation fulfils, to best extent possible, the principle of data minimisation. Alternatively, and while it does not render the data anonymous, pseudonymisation is considered an appropriate technical measure for enhancing data protection pursuant to the data minimisation principle.

The de-personalisation module at the MES-CoBraD platform aims to, at least, pseudonymise the personal data uploaded in it.

4.7.4.1 Data minimisation by design and by default

Data minimisation-Key design and default elements		
37.	Data avoidance	Avoid processing personal data altogether when this is possible for the relevant purpose.
38.	Relevance	Personal data shall be relevant to the processing in question, and the controller shall be able to demonstrate this relevance
39.	Necessity	Each personal data element shall be necessary for the specified purposes and should only be processed if it is not possible to fulfil the purpose by other means.
40.	Limitation	Limit the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the purpose
41.	Aggregation	Use aggregated data when possible
42.	Pseudonymisation	Pseudonymize personal data as soon as it is no longer necessary to have

²²⁶EDPB, (2019), Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default, pp.19

		directly identifiable personal data, and store identification keys separately
43.	Anonymisation and deletion	Where personal data is not, or no longer necessary for the purpose, personal data shall be anonymized or deleted
44.	Data flow	The data flow shall be made efficient enough to not create more copies, or entry points for data collection than necessary
45.	State of the art	The controller should apply available and suitable technologies for data avoidance and minimisation.

4.7.5 ACCURACY

Data accuracy Article 5 (1) (d) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, regarding to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased, or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
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The personal data processed during MES-CoBraD project only aims at facilitating the development of the platform, no decision or diagnosis will be carried based on it that might affect a data subject. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the data stored at the platform remains relevant in order to fulfil with the project's data management obligations, for instance actin upon an eventual data subject request. Also, the principle of accuracy remains fundamental for medical partners with regards to the data stored at their premises, in order to address any potential request from data subject.

4.7.5.1 Accuracy by design and by default

Accuracy- Key design and default elements		
46.	Data Source	Data sources should be dependable in terms of data accuracy
47.	Degree of accuracy	Each personal data element shall be as accurate as necessary for the specified purposes.
48.	Measurably accurate	Reduce the number of false positives/negatives.
49.	Verification	Depending on the nature of the data, in relation to how often it may change, the controller should verify the correctness of personal data with the data subject before and at various stages of the processing.
50.	Erasure/rectification	The controller must erase or rectify inaccurate data without delay.
51.	Accumulated errors	Controllers must mitigate the effect of an accumulated error in the processing chain.
52.	Access	Data subjects should be given an overview and easy access to personal data in order to control accuracy and rectify as needed.
53.	Continued accuracy	Personal data should be accurate at all stages of the processing, tests of accuracy should be conducted at critical steps
54.	Up to date	Personal data shall be updated if necessary for the purpose.
55.	Data design	Use of technological and organisational design features to decrease inaccuracy, e.g. drop-down lists with limited values, internal policies, and legal criteria.

4.7.6 KEY INSIGHTS ON DATA PROTECTION PRINCIPLES FROM THE DPIA QUESTIONNAIRES

- › The processing of personal data for research in MES-CoBraD is based on the approvals obtained by the Ethics Boards/Committees of the clinical partners.
- › The lawfulness of the processing of personal data obtained by the clinical sites and other clinical settings are governed by their own laws, regulations and procedure.
- › Information concerning the processing of a dataset is provided in the relevant Research dataset template (RDT) at the D2.2 Data management plan. This includes details on the Data collection, documentation and curation, analysis, training of AI algorithms, disclosure to partners, destruction.
- › Datasets are removed of identifiers and do not enable the re-identification of individuals to any partner except the controller of the original dataset.²²⁷
- › For the duration of the MES-CoBraD project research activities, the purpose of the datasets uploaded into the MES-CoBraD platform is solely to carry out scientific research. This means that no diagnostic or medicine-oriented use has been carried out based on those datasets.
- › With regards to the principle of accuracy of data, a test of accuracy is envisaged at the different steps of the MES-CoBraD processing lifecycle. This is part of the scientific process with the aim to prove the project’s accuracy through hypothesis testing and other statistical analysis tools.
- › Nevertheless, data is not necessarily updated during MES-CoBraD because their purpose is not that of providing a diagnostic to a specific patient. Insofar uploaded datasets are de-personalised, checking whether dataset is up to date is not necessary unless they introduce errors in the analyses.
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4.8 STORAGE, INTEGRITY, CONFIDENTIALITY AND SECURITY

4.8.1 STORAGE LIMITATION

<p>Storage limitation</p> <p>Article 5 (1) (e) of the GDPR</p>	<p>Personal data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1), subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject ('storage limitation');</p>
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The principle of storage limitation aims to technically ensure that data is not processed longer than necessary. The measures and safeguards adopted are instrumental to the effectiveness of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects, specifically, the right to erasure, the right to object and profiling.

4.8.1.1 Storage limitation by design and by default

Storage limitation-Key design and default elements		
56.	Deletion	Avoid processing personal data altogether when this is possible for the relevant purpose.

²²⁷ See section 4.6 on de-personalisation.

57.	Automation	Personal data shall be relevant to the processing in question, and the controller shall be able to demonstrate this relevance
58.	Storage criteria	Each personal data element shall be necessary for the specified purposes and should only be processed if it is not possible to fulfil the purpose by other means.
59.	Enforcement of retention policies	Limit the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the purpose
60.	Effectiveness of anonymization/deletion	Use aggregated data when possible
61.	Disclose rationale	Pseudonymize personal data as soon as it is no longer necessary to have directly identifiable personal data, and store identification keys separately
62.	Data flow	Controllers must beware of and seek to limit “temporary” storage of personal data
63.	Backups/logs	Controllers must determine which personal data and length of storage is necessary for back-ups and logs

4.8.2 INTEGRITY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

<p>Integrity and Confidentiality Article 5 (1) (f) of the GDPR</p>	<p>Personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction, or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures</p>
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Researchers processing personal data have the ethical and legal obligation to ensure that participant’s information is properly protected ²²⁸. Under data protection law, the security of processing is regulated in section 2 of the GDPR, articles 32 to 34.

The principle of security embraces the security properties of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA), aimed at reinforcing the resilience of data processing activities.

- › Confidentiality is the protection of information from unauthorized access or disclosure.
- › Integrity is the protection of information from unauthorized modification.
- › Availability ensures the timely and reliable access to and use of information and systems.

The objective is twofold, from one hand prevent data breach incidents and from the other, facilitate the proper execution of data processing tasks, the observance of data protection principles and data subject rights in a seamless manner. Along with other data protection by design and by default measures, Recital 78 suggests a responsibility on the controllers to continually assess whether they are always using the appropriate means of processing and to assess whether the chosen measures actually counter the existing vulnerabilities. In that sense, the project should conduct regular reviews of the information security measures implemented to check their efficiency.

²²⁸ European Commission, (2018) Ethics and data protection

4.8.2.1 Integrity and confidentiality by design and by default

Integrity and confidentiality -Key design and default elements		
64.	Information security management system (ISMS)	Have an operative means of managing policies and procedures for information security. For some controllers, this may be possible with the help of an ISMS.
65.	Risk Analysis	Assess the risks against the security of personal data and counter identified risks
66.	Resilience	The processing should be robust enough to withstand changes, regulatory demands, incidents, and cyber attacks
67.	Access management	Only authorized personnel shall have access to the data necessary for their processing tasks
68.	Aggregation	Use aggregated data when possible
69.	Secure transfers	Transfers shall be secured against unauthorized access and changes
70.	Secure storage	Where personal data is not, or no longer necessary for the purpose, personal data shall be anonymized or deleted
71.	Backups/logs	The data flow shall be made efficient enough to not create more copies, or entry points for data collection than necessary
72.	Special protection	The controller should apply available and suitable technologies for data avoidance and minimisation.
73.	Pseudonymization	Personal data and back-ups/logs should be pseudonymized as a security measure to minimize risks of potential data breaches, for example using hashing or encryption
74.	Security incident response management	Have in place routines and procedures to detect, handle, report, and learn from data breaches
75.	Personal data breach handling	Integrate management of notification (to the supervisory authority) and information (to data subjects) obligations in the event of a data breach into security incident management procedures
76.	Maintenance and development	Regular review and test software to uncover vulnerabilities of the systems supporting the processing

4.8.3 SECURITY OF THE PROCESSING IN MES-COBRAD

Researchers processing personal data have the ethical and legal obligation to ensure that participant information is properly protected. According to GDPR data protection law, the security of processing is regulated in articles 32 to 34 of the GDPR. This section focusses on the principle of security during MES-CoBraD research for the data stored on the platform. The technical and organisational measures implemented by the medical partners therein are beyond the scope of this section.

Security of processing Article 32 of the GDPR	<p>1. Taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context, and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, including inter alia as appropriate:</p> <p>(a) the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data.</p>
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See also Recital 83 of the GDPR	(b) the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services.
	(c) the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident.
	(d) a process for regularly testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.
	2. In assessing the appropriate level of security account shall be taken of the risks that are presented by processing, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed.
	3. Adherence to an approved code of conduct as referred to in Article 40 or an approved certification mechanism as referred to in Article 42 may be used as an element by which to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in paragraph 1 of this article.
	4. The controller and processor shall take steps to ensure that any natural person acting under the authority of the controller or the processor who has access to personal data does not process them except on instructions from the controller unless he or she is required to do so by Union or Member State law.

Processing taking place on the MES-CoBraD platform must comply with the obligations provided by the GDPR, including observing the security of obligations. Considering that the assessment of MES-CoBraD processing activities is strongly dependant on its capacity to minimise risks towards re-identification, the obligation to ensure security is the most important.

The following tables enumerate the security measures implemented during the project: ²²⁹

Table 9 MES-CoBraD Technical measures

Technical measures	Description
Depersonalisation module	Technical measures have been adopted to prevent the re-identification of personal data. For an in deep description of the measures adopted see D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – final (v1.0). (2023). The system anonymises or pseudonymises private and/or confidential data based on types of RWD.
Encryption	Encryption is a reliable way to protect sensitive data from data breaches because it protects data throughout its lifecycle. There are numerous encryption algorithms in use, including RSA, DES, AES, and many others.
Secure access platform	Adopt technical and measures that prevent the access by nonauthorized third parties.
Audit module	Develop a process for regular testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of that processing. Provide support documentation and history for security and operational actions, providing proof of data origin and integrity.

Table 10 MES-CoBraD Organisational measures

²²⁹ MES-Cobrad Grant Agreement, Part B, p.16

Organisational measures	Description
Transparency	The Data Management Plan explains how the personal data is processed during the MES-CoBraD research.
Distribution of responsibilities and Data Processing arrangement.	In order to ensure a clear distribution of responsibilities in the processing of data under the MES-CoBraD project, a Data Processing Arrangement has been adopted. ²³⁰
Establish user-access protocols	Access to stored personal data is restricted to the MES-CoBraD consortium on a need-to-know basis.
Confidentiality and reidentification commitments	Partners in MES- CoBraD research have formally stated their agreement on not pursuing the reidentification of the pseudonymised personal data stored at the platform. ²³¹

4.8.3.1 Data processing risks

European institutions, bodies and agencies have released several guides and law on the concept of risk management.²³² At EU level the Network Information Security Directive 2016/1148 (NIS Directive)²³³ harmonised the concept of risk in the context of the security of ICT infrastructure.

In its article 4(9) the NIS Directive defines ‘risk’ as any reasonably identifiable circumstance or event having a potential adverse effect on the security of network and information systems. Examples of such risks might be i) the accidental or unlawful destruction, ii) loss, iii) alteration, iv) unauthorised disclosure, or v) the access to processed personal data. In the context of data protection, the GDPR contemplates risk management and the assessment of security measures as being inherently connected to the risks the controllers are responsible for. They include physical, material, or non-material damages foreseen during a processing activity.²³⁴

The risks that could impact the personal data processed during the project have been monitored and addressed technically and organisationally. In that respect, and as it has been already pointed out, because of its repercussions from a data protection perspective, the reidentification of datasets has been our main focus. The measures adopted and presented in Section 3 of the D2.2 DMP, have aimed to reduce that risk as much as possible.²³⁵

The possibility that the MES-CoBraD Platform could be used for discriminating purposes (i.e job applications, insurance policy, financial products) has been taken into consideration. Indeed, it is recognised that, from a technical point of view, the tools developed in MES-CoBraD could be used for discriminatory purposes. During MES-CoBraD the controllers of the datasets remain clinical partners, who have agreed to sign a declaration of compliance with their institutional and national laws.

In a hypothetical scenario of deployment, the technical and organisational measures adopted during the

²³⁰ The agreement should include the roles and responsibilities of the partners, the subject matter, duration, and nature of the processing, the types of personal data concerned, the categories of data subjects concerned, obligations and rights of controllers and processors.

²³¹ All partners accessing de-personalized datasets expressly commit to not attempt the re-identification of the data subjects from whom the de-personalized information might refer to. See s3.1.7 D2.2 Data Management Plan

²³² ENISA, (2022), Risk Management Standards 2022;

²³³ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union (NIS Directive).

²³⁴ Recital 85 of the GDPR

²³⁵ See ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security- final (2023),

Project would need to be revisited and adjusted to reflect the new level of risks, particularly the nature of its stakeholders and its commercial relations. Another important aspect especially concerns cybersecurity and the adjustment of the platform to the NIS2 Directive as well as relevant industry standards. ²³⁶

4.8.3.2 Data breach, assessment, and notification duty

Personal data breach Article 4(12)	Personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed
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A data breach occurs when the data subject suffers a loss of control over their personal data, a limitation of their rights, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, pecuniary loss, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, damage to reputation, and loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy. It also includes any other significant economic or social disadvantage to those individuals.²³⁷ In its Opinion 03/2014 on breach notification²³⁸ and in its Guidelines WP 250²³⁹, the WP29 categorised data breaches following the CIA information security principles, as follows: ²⁴⁰

- › Confidentiality breach: where there is an unauthorised or accidental disclosure of, or access to, personal data.
- › Integrity breach where there is an unauthorised or accidental alteration of personal data.
- › Availability breach: where there is an accidental or unauthorised loss of access to, or destruction of, personal data.

In the event of a data breach the GDPR requires the controller to:

- i. Document the breach, including the facts relating to the breach, its effects and remedial action taken.²⁴¹
- ii. Notify the personal data breach to the supervisory authority, unless the data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.²⁴² As soon as a controller becomes aware of a data breach, the controller should notify it to the supervisory authority without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it. Only when the controller is able to demonstrate, in accordance with the accountability principle, that the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, no notification is required.²⁴³ The notification to the supervisory authority must at least contain the following details:
 - a. describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned, and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned.
 - b. communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained.

²³⁶ See D2.11 MES-COBRA D IPR protection and standardisation.

²³⁷ Ibid p.6

²³⁸ G29 WP213, 25 March 2014, Opinion 03/2014 on Personal Data Breach Notification, p. 5,

²³⁹ G29 WP250 rev.1, 6 February 2018, Guidelines on Personal data breach notification under Regulation 2016/679 - endorsed by the EDPB,

²⁴⁰ More recently the EDPB has issued new guidelines aimed at helping data controllers handling data breaches as well as their risk assessment See EDPB, 14 December 2021, Guidelines 01/2021 on Examples regarding Personal Data Breach Notification Version 2.0.

²⁴¹ Article 33 (5). Of the GDPR.

²⁴² Article 33(1) of the GDPR

²⁴³ Recital 85 of the GDPR

- c. describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach.
 - d. describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.
 - iii. Communicate the personal data breach to the data subject when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.²⁴⁴ The obligation to inform the data subject must be done without undue delay when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. The communications need to be clear and in plain language, include the nature of the personal data breach and at least the same information provided to the supervisory authority. The same article 34 indicates an exhaustive exempts the controller's obligation to inform the data subject when:
 - a. The controller has implemented appropriate technical and organisational measures.
 - b. The controller has taken subsequent measures ensuring that the high risk to the rights and freedoms will not materialise.
 - c. Informing to the data subjects would imply a disproportionate effort.

Following the explicit recommendation in D2.3 the project has adopted the data breach notification protocol. The same can be found in s3.1.8 of the D2.2 MES-CoBraD data management plan.

4.8.4 KEY INSIGHTS ON STORAGE, INTEGRITY, CONFIDENTIALITY AND SECURITY, FROM THE DPIA QUESTIONNAIRES

- › The data uploaded into the platform will remain personal data for the controller insofar it can, with the help of additional information, re-identify the data subject.
- › Clinical sites participating in MES-CoBRaD are certified under ISO 27001 and ISO 27799 have operative means of managing policies and procedures for information security. Based on their obligations from GDPR, the NIS Directive, and several national laws and regulations, clinical sites implement several controls, policies and procedures from the ISO 27001 standard. At the same time, during the project the platform has been deployed in organisations that are certified under ISO 27001.
- › The processing that takes place at the MES-CoBraD platform is robust and can withstand changes in terms of regulatory demands, incidents and cyberattacks. The compartmentalisation of types of datasets resulting from the edge module depersonalisation, ensures that data stored at a platform level cannot be used to re-identify data subjects. With regards to the data stored at clinical site, this remains under the clinical sites' scope, thus the responsibility for any identifiable personal data resides with the clinical site. Security is being addressed using multiple controls in the platform, including VPN connections, cryptography and access control features.
- › The platform has been designed to incorporate a data processing records as per Article 30 of the GDPR. Further information on this point can be found in D5.2 - Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security. In addition, the DMP and the research dataset templates have facilitated the record keeping of the data being processed during the project.
- › The metadata manager explains where the metadata catalogue of the MES-CoBraD datasets is described. The different sources of the RWD are detailed per dataset and incorporated using the FAIR

²⁴⁴ Article 34 (1) of the GDPR

templates to the D.2.2 DMP.

- › Verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the AI system's reliability and reproducibility, have been developed as part of the validation of the training of AI algorithms and are being deployed per case as part of the workflow component.
- › The re-purposing of processing activities is not possible during the MES-CoBraD project (i.e. from research to healthcare, commercial exploitation, etc). There is an express commitment by the partners included in the project Data Processing Policy to only process personal data in the context of MES-CoBraD for the research purposes identified. including data analysis, training of AI algorithms, scientific research etc. It covers all possible uses of open research data. See Section 3 of the D2.2 Data Management Plan.

4.9 THE PRINCIPLE OF ACCOUNTABILITY

Accountability Article 5(2) of the GDPR	The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, paragraph 1 ('accountability').
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Partners participating in the MES-CoBraD research should be able to proactively demonstrate compliance with the GDPR. Regarding medical partners, they should always apply the necessary measures within their organizations in order to be able to explain, both to the individuals concerned and to any future controls by the Data Protection Authorities, that the data protection legislation has been duly observed.

Indicatively, all members have an appointed DPO or given the details of a contact point for addressing legal and ethical matters. In addition, and prior to the submission of the first version of this deliverable, all partners have signed a declaration of compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation), and the national law of the country where the partner organisation is established²⁴⁵

Then following up on the midterm review and the recommendations raised by the first version of the MES-CoBraD Ethical and regulatory framework, a number of organisational measures have been adopted to promote the project's culture toward accountability.²⁴⁶

- Opinions and approvals by ethics committees
- Data processing records
- Data processing policy
- Data subject request protocols
- Data breach protocols

4.10 DATA PROTECTION BY DESIGN AND BY DEFAULT AT MES-COBRA D.

Data Protection by design and by default Article 25 of the GDPR	1. Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing, as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, the controller shall, both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself, implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimisation, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects.
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²⁴⁵ MES-CoBRaD D2.2 Data Management Plan-v1

²⁴⁶ MES-CoBRaD D2.2 Data Mangament Plan- v2 section3.

See also Recital 78	2. The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed. That obligation applies to the amount of personal data collected, the extent of their processing, the period of their storage and their accessibility. In particular, such measures shall ensure that by default personal data are not made accessible without the individual's intervention to an indefinite number of natural persons.
	3. An approved certification mechanism pursuant to Article 42 may be used as an element to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in paragraphs 1 and 2 of this Article.

The principles of data protection by design and by default suppose the controller’s obligation to implement data protection principles and data subject’s rights as a design and as a default property of systems and services.

By definition, the principle of data protection by design must be implemented “at the time of determining the means” of a processing activity or service. It is then that controller must think and introduce the measures and safeguards to effectively implement the data protection principles.²⁴⁷ Nevertheless, controllers must also review the effectiveness of the measures and safeguards, during the processing. The objective is to prevent risks from ever occurring prior and while the processing activity takes place.

Pursuant to article 25(1), the controller has to 1) implement appropriate technical and organisational measures and 2) integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing so that GDPR requirements and data subject rights are observed during the processing.

There is a variety of technical or organizational measures that might serve the purpose of the principles. As long as the measures are appropriate for implementing the data protection principles effectively and proportionately against potential risks. Data protection by default aims that, by default, no more than the necessary personal data for each specific purpose of the processing is processed in compliance with the law and transparently notified to the individuals concerned. In that sense the “default settings” of the platform must be designed with data protection in mind.²⁴⁸

Since the submission of v1 of the Ethical and Regulatory Framework, key design and default features have been incorporated into the MES-CoBraD platform²⁴⁹. WP2 has worked to promote, in the technical discussions on the development of the platform, the consideration of data protection principles. The inputs provided in this deliverable as well as the DMP are proof of the MES-CoBraD commitment to adhere to data protection laws.

4.11 DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS UNDER THE GDPR

The rights of the data subjects are listed in articles 13-21 of the GDPR:

- a. The right to information
- b. The right to access the data.
- c. The right to rectification
- d. The right to erasure (the right to be forgotten)
- e. The right to restriction of processing

²⁴⁷ Ibid

²⁴⁸ The EDPS has expressed that “while it can be argued that this obligation is already implicit in the purpose limitation” and “data minimisation” principles in both the design and operation phases, the explicit rule stresses the importance of taking technical measures to meet the expectations of the individuals whose data are processed, not to have their data processed for other purposes than what the product and service is basically and strictly meant to do, leaving by default any further use turned off, for instance through configuration settings”.

²⁴⁹ See ENG. D5.2 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security- final (2023),

- f. The right to data portability
- g. The right to object

Again, it is necessary to distinguish between the different responsibilities and processing activities that are in place at MES-CoBraD. Medical partners remain individual controllers for the personal data stored at their premises, and thus are fully responsible for the observance of data subject rights in light of EU and national laws. On the other hand, the derogations provided in the special regime apply to the processing of personal data on the platform, taking into consideration the distribution of responsibilities between partners.

The following sections provide an overview on data subject rights in the context of MES-CoBraD.

4.11.1 THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION

The right to information is observed in two articles, Articles 13 and 14. of the GDPR. Article 13 regulates the case where personal data is collected directly from the data subject, while Article 14 applies in those cases where data come from other sources. In the case of data processing from patient records or the processing of data from other countries, article 14 applies.

The disclosure of information to data subjects on processing activities represents a practical consequence of the principles of fair and transparent processing. It implies a fundamental prerequisite for compliance with the controller's data protection obligation, as it enables data subjects to invoke their data subject rights should they wish to do so.²⁵⁰

In light of the right to information, at the time of collection, the controller is obliged to provide the data subject the following details regarding the processing:

Right to information - information to be provided. Article 13(1) and 14 (1) of the GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the identity and the contact details of the controller and, where applicable, of the controller's representative. (b) the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable. (c) the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing. (d) where the processing is based on point (f) of Article 6(1), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party. (e) the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any. (f) where applicable, the fact that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a third country or international organisation and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in Article 46 or 47, or the second subparagraph of Article 49(1), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means by which to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available.
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Further additional information the controller will need to present to the data subject upon collecting his or her personal data when that is needed to ensure transparency and fairness:

Right to information - further information to be provided. Article 13(2) and 14 (2) of the GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period. (b) the existence of the right to request from the controller access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing concerning the data subject or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability. (c) where the processing is based on point (a) of Article 6(1) or point (a) of Article 9(2), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. (d) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.
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²⁵⁰ Due to its enabling nature, the applicability of exemptions on the right to information for the data stored in the MES-CoBraD platform, have a direct impact on the exercise of data subject's rights.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (e) whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data, and of the possible consequences of failure to provide such data. (f) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.
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At the time of collection, medical partners inform the data subject about the further processing that will take place according to their national laws and applicable codes. At least in the case of prospective data, the data subject should be provided, prior to that further processing takes place, with information on that other purpose and with any additional information.²⁵¹

With regards to depersonalised data processed at a platform level, partners might be exempted to fulfil information request they receive, based in the impossibility or disproportionate effort that such request would involve to them.²⁵²

4.11.2 THE RIGHT TO ACCESS THE DATA

The right of access, provided in article 15 of the GDPR has the objective of facilitating data subjects' verification of the lawfulness of a processing activity using his or her personal data. As the right to information, the right of access has also an instrumental nature when it comes to exercising other data subject's rights such as the rectification, erasure or blocking of personal data²⁵³. Pursuant the right of access, the data subject will have the right to obtain the following information:

<p>Right of access</p> <p>Article 15 of the GDPR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the purposes of the processing. (b) the categories of personal data concerned. (c) the recipients or categories of recipient to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed, in particular recipients in third countries or international organisations. (d) where possible, the envisaged period for which the personal data will be stored, or, if not possible, the criteria used to determine that period. (e) the existence of the right to request from the controller rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing of personal data concerning the data subject or to object to such processing. (f) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority. (g) where the personal data is not collected from the data subject, any available information as to their source. (h) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.
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In terms of limitations, the right of access is expressly delineated by the rights and freedoms of others. Despite the fact that data subjects are not obliged to give reasons or to justify their request, the same can be restricted when a request is manifestly unfounded or excessive.²⁵⁴ However and without prejudice to the existence of national rules on specific areas (i.e. law enforcement or health data), as long as the

²⁵¹ Article 13(3) and 14(4) of the GDPR

²⁵² (Article 14(5) b of the GDPR: Proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort". See EDPB 03/2020 p. 9 See also reference to See the Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article-29 Working-Party (2018), WP260 rev.01, 17/EN, page 29 (endorsed by the EDPB).

²⁵³ CJEU, Judgement of 2014, Joined Cases C-141/12 and C-372/12, YS, and Others. ECLI:EU:C:2014:2081

²⁵⁴ Article 12 (5) of the GDPR

requirements of Article 15 of the GDPR are met, the purposes behind the request should be regarded as irrelevant.

4.11.3 THE RIGHT TO ERASURE (RIGHT TO BE FORGOTTEN)

The right to erasure, alternatively known as the right to be forgotten is provided in Article 17 of the GDPR. The right to erasure grants individuals the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay where one of the following grounds applies:

<p>The right to erasure</p> <p>Article 17 of the GDPR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">(a) the personal data are no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were collected or otherwise processed.(b) the data subject withdraws consent on which the processing is based according to point (a) of Article 6(1), or point (a) of Article 9(2), and where there is no other legal ground for the processing.(c) the data subject objects to the processing pursuant to Article 21(1) and there are no overriding legitimate grounds for the processing, or the data subject objects to the processing pursuant to Article 21(2).(d) the personal data have been unlawfully processed.(e) the personal data have to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject.(f) the personal data have been collected in relation to the offer of information society services referred to in Article 8(1).
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The right to erasure is not absolute, and in the context of scientific research, derogations are observed in article 17 (3) of the GDPR. The data subject's right is limited in those cases where its enforcement would be likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement the research objectives. This is particularly relevant for that personal data unlawfully processed or no longer necessary in relation to the purpose for which they were collected, or when the data subject has withdrawn his/her consent.

Only the relevant medical partner remains capable of re-identifying a data subject whose data is at MES-CoBraD platform, based on the data stored at its premisses. Insofar that data at the clinical site is deleted, the pseudonymised information at the MES-CoBraD platform is anonymous for its users.

4.11.4 THE RIGHT TO RESTRICTION OF THE PROCESSING

Based on Article 18 of the GDPR, the data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller restriction of processing where one of the following applies:

- (a) the accuracy of the personal data is contested by the data subject, for a period enabling the controller to verify the accuracy of the personal data.
- (b) the processing is unlawful, and the data subject opposes the erasure of the personal data and requests the restriction of their use instead.
- (c) the controller no longer needs the personal data for the purposes of the processing, but they are required by the data subject for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims.
- (d) the data subject has objected to processing pursuant to Article 21(1) pending the verification whether the legitimate grounds of the controller override those of the data subject.

The term "restriction" is not defined in the GDPR. The scope of this right is the limitation of the controller's capacity to process personal data. Examples of measures that might facilitate the right to restriction include inter alia (Recital 67): temporarily moving the selected data to another processing system, making the selected personal data unavailable to users, or temporarily removing published data from a website.

In automated filing systems such as MES-CoBraD, controllers should be able to restrict the processing of data by technical means in such a manner that the personal data are not subject to further processing operations and cannot be changed. The status of restricted data should be clearly indicated in the system.

The design of the platform is based on the de-personalisation of datasets. It is based on it that the risks on subsequent processing are mitigated.

4.11.5 THE RIGHT TO PORTABILITY

The right to data portability is observed in Article 20 of the GDPR. It grants the data subject the right to receive the personal data concerning him or her, which he or she has provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format and the right to transmit those data to another controller without hindrance from the controller to which the personal data have been provided. The right to data portability is provided to data subjects under two conditions, that the processing is based on consent or on a contract basis and that the processing is carried out by automated means.

As in the case of the right to information, insofar the datasets stored at MES-CoBraD are pseudonymised data, the right to data portability would be contentious. Implementing the right to portability in the design of the platform would force the controllers to technically contravene their commitment to not allow the re-identification from the data processed at the platform. Nevertheless, considering the exploitation objectives of the platform, the possibility from data subjects to transfer their data to another might be relevant and therefore may be a future consideration.

4.11.6 THE RIGHT TO OBJECT

The right to object states that data subjects have, at any time, the right to deny, on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, to processing of personal data concerning him or her where the legal basis of the processing relies on public interests or legitimate interests.²⁵⁵

Data subjects do not have a general right to object to the processing of their data, but when it comes to the balancing interests, the burden of proof is vested in the controller. It is the controller who will need to show “compelling and “legitimate” grounds for continuing processing the data.²⁵⁶ In the event the interests of data subject override those of the controller, the exercise of the right to object will force the controller to stop the processing of personal data.²⁵⁷

4.11.7 KEY INSIGHTS ON DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS FROM THE DPIA QUESTIONNAIRES

- › Patients that have shared personal data with a clinical partner are able withdraw their consent. MES-CoBraD partners have a protocol – prohibiting data collection, limiting access to curated data (paper and electronic), scheduling a meeting with the participant to review any result derived from the research activities either expected or accidental.
- › In the event a data subject withdraws his consent, all personal data relating to that subject is deleted from the clinical site. However, provided that datasets located at the clinical sites are the only containing identifiers enabling the re-identification, a consent withdrawal does not necessarily imply the deletion of the dataset uploaded into the platform once they have undergone de-personalisation.
- › Data subjects are granted the highest degree of autonomy possible with respect to control over their personal data with regards to the data processing at MES-CoBraD platform. They do so through the

²⁵⁵ Article 21 of the GDPR

²⁵⁶ Recital 69 of the GDPR

²⁵⁷ In the case *Cammeria de Commercio v Salvatore Manni* the CJEU considered that national courts have the responsibility to assess the individual circumstances on a case-by-case basis. CJEU, Judgment of the Court (Second Chamber) of 9 March 2017, Case C-398/15 *Camera di Commercio, Industria, Artigianato e Agricoltura di Lecce v Salvatore Manni* Request for a preliminary ruling from the Corte suprema di cassazione, ECLI:EU:C:2017:197

clinical sites and their institutional protocols for processing personal data.

4.12 INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS AND ADEQUACY DECISIONS

<p>Transfers on the basis of an adequacy decision</p> <p>Article 45 of the GDPR; Recital 103</p>	<p>1.A transfer of personal data to a third country or an international organisation may take place where the Commission has decided that the third country, a territory or one or more specified sectors within that third country, or the international organisation in question ensures an adequate level of protection. Such a transfer shall not require any specific authorisation.</p> <p>(...)</p>
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The GDPR does not provide for a legal definition of the notion “transfer of personal data to a third country or to an international organisation”. The EDPB has identified **the three following cumulative criteria** that qualify a processing as a transfer: 1) A controller or a processor is subject to the GDPR; 2) a controller or processor discloses the data to a recipient who imports the data; 3) The recipient of the data is from a third country.

The first requirement is that the controller or a processor is bound by the GDPR. It is worth underlining those controllers and processors, which are not established in the EU, may be subject to the GDPR pursuant to Article 3(2) for a given processing and, thus, will have to comply with Chapter V when transferring personal data to a third country or to an international organisation. This is the case of the two partners in MES-CoBraD with regards to the personal data they are or may eventually process which is made available or shared to them by EU members.

Second, the controller or processor ('exporter') must disclose personal data by transmission or otherwise make personal data available to another controller, joint controller, or processor ('recipient'). In order to qualify as a transfer, there must be a controller or processor disclosing the data (the exporter) and a different controller or processor receiving or being given access to the data (the importer).

The importer is in a third country or is an international organisation, regardless of whether or not this importer is subject to the GDPR in respect of the given processing in accordance with Article 3. The third criterion requires that the importer is geographically in a third country or is an international organisation, but regardless of whether the processing at hand falls within the scope of the GDPR. In other words, under the GDPR, international data transfers exist when personal data is shared to an entity or body from a non-EU country. (Article 44 of the GDPR).

The GDPR foresees three grounds based on which a data transfer of data might take place:

- Article 45 Subject to adequacy decision
- Article 46 Subject to appropriate safeguards
- Article 47 Based on Binding corporate Rules.

4.12.1 ADEQUACY DECISION

Transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organisation may take place where the Commission has decided that the third country, a territory or one or more specified sectors within that third country, or the international organisation in question ensures an adequate level of protection. Such a transfer shall not require any specific authorisation (Article 45 of the GDPR).

Article 45 of the GDPR regulates the most convenient mechanism for transfer of data to third countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA). Where the European Commission, by means of an implementing decision on data adequacy, recognises that a foreign country's level of data protection is essentially equivalent to that of the EU, economic operators may conveniently transfer data to the

importing entity located in a third country.

Adequacy decisions are implementing acts issued by the European Commission based on an assessment of the formal level of protection of personal data in another country. In other words, they do not involve the European Council (ministers of member states) or the European Parliament, but the Commission has to consult the EDPB²⁵⁸.

We acknowledge that from a legal perspective an adequacy assessment only covers whether personal data can leave the EU, which raises the question whether adequacy decisions actually have extraterritorial effect. European Commission, 2021c).

The EDPB adopted guidelines for international data transfers between public bodies in application of Articles 46 paragraph 2a and 46 paragraph 3b GDPR on 15 December 2020 (European Data Protection Board, 2020b).

In its recent judgment C-311/18 (Schrems II) the CJEU reminds that the protection granted to personal data in the European Economic Area (EEA) must travel with the data wherever it goes. Transferring personal data to third countries cannot be a means to undermine or water down the protection it is afforded in the EEA.

The Court clarified that the level of protection in third countries does not need to be identical to that guaranteed within the EEA, but essentially equivalent. The Court also upholds the validity of standard contractual clauses, as a transfer tool that may serve to ensure contractually an essentially equivalent level of protection for data transferred to third countries. (EDPB, recommendation, 2020)

4.12.2 ARE THERE DATA TRANSFERS IN MES-COBRAD?

As indicated in the first version of the Data Management Plan (see Section 2.5.3), the project has kept track and mapped the existence of data transfers and ensured that the research conducted outside the EU does not contravene the legal standards set by the EU.

During the project, we have examined whether transfers to personal data to non-EU countries, namely Israel and the United Kingdom, took place in MES-CoBraD. From the information provided by the partners, we can conclude that both countries export but do not import data from the MES-CoBraD platform. As a result, no international transfer of data takes place during MES-CoBraD (See section 3 of the DMP).

Furthermore, even in the case that such transfer of data takes place, those transfers would still not qualify as international data transfers as per the GDPR insofar the two third countries present in the consortium, Israel, and the United Kingdom, have both been granted an adequacy decision by the European Commission. EDPB 03/2020 p. 9. See also reference to See the Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article-29 Working-Party (2018), WP260 rev.01, 17/EN, page 29 (endorsed by the EDPB).

²⁵⁸ Graham Greenleaf, (2012) 'The Influence of European Data Privacy Standards Outside Europe: Implications for Globalisation of Convention 108', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 19 October 2011),..p. 23; See also Christopher Kuner et al., *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary*, First edition (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020). p. 785

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present deliverable concludes the MES-CoBraD ethical and regulatory Framework. This updated version has reflected the interest and willingness of the consortium to not only comply with a number of requirements but to scientifically contribute to the fields of ethics and law.

As it has been herein reported and explained, the MES-CoBraD platform represents a technically complex endeavour, one that can potentially give rise to no less complex challenges from an ethical and legal perspective. Technical and Scientific partners have been aware of this circumstance when carrying out their tasks. This document, and its first instance, have aimed to go beyond capturing a framework it has sought to influence and embed ethical and legal principles and requirements in the development of the MES-CoBraD platform.

A crucial element in the assessment has relied on the concept of personal data. A discussion that, since April 2021 when the project began, has been ongoing among stakeholders, with new opinions, and case law emerging, and which through time, has shed new light on the interpretation of personal data within the project. It is based on the follow up of these discussions, and on the technical and organisational safeguards adopted by the project, that D2.9 can state, with as much confidence as a risk approach allow, that depersonalised data uploaded by clinical partners to the MES-CoBRaD platform is not personal data to other users of the platform, and that as a result, no processing of personal data takes place at the MES-CoBRaD platform.

This said, and as it has been repeatedly expressed, the validity of this statement will need to be periodically re-assessed, insofar the circumstances around the processing activities performed at or through the platform change or evolve. At the same time, the legal and ethical assessments need to be responsive to changes in law or interpretation of law, reassessing the implications for MES-CoBraD as needed.

The MES-CoBRaD methodology for data protection impact assessment is precisely an attempt to incorporate that principle of cyclic and continuous monitoring into the platform. Frameworks may become outdated with changing laws, regulations, or legal opinions, as this deliverable demonstrates. Since its first iteration - published in March 2022 - and more specifically in the last six months of this project, a new generation of EU Data Laws have been adopted, and the first attempt to regulate Artificial intelligence has been approved by the EU Legislator. While we have aimed to offer a preliminary insight through this updated framework, the interplay between the different pieces of legislation remains uncharted and MES-CoBraD will need to keep up to date.

The following table presents an executive summary on the assessments made in this document organised by topic.

A)	PERSONAL DATA AND HEALTH DATA
1.	The project MES-CoBraD uses retrospective and prospective RWD concerning health to populate the MES-CoBraD platform and train the predictive algorithms.
2.	Four medical partners: NIA, UU, KCL RMC-C&E, are the partners who collect RWD and share RWD to the project.
3.	The datasets collected and used in MES-CoBraD for research purposes, are exhaustively curated and described in the MES-CoBraD D3.2 Project Manual.
4.	Personal data obtained and processed by the clinical sites at their premises are

	governed by their own laws, regulations and procedure which are independent to MES-CoBraD.
5.	In addition, the RWD used for research purposes is bound by the data management policy of the consortium. It follows that personal data is not included in any disseminated material.
B)	DATA PROCESSING
6.	The MES-CoBraD platform incorporates a de-personalisation module configurable according to each type of RWD.
7.	Only after undergoing de-personalisation through the edge module, data is uploaded to the MES-CoBraD platform.
8.	The data outcome obtained from the module might be either fully anonymised data or pseudonymised data.
9.	The processing of personal data pre-anonymisation only occurs at the clinical site, so the only processing activity that takes place on the datasets in the edge module, is the de-personalisation itself (pseudonymisation/anonymisation)
10.	The restriction of the personal data availability only within the clinical Local Area Network ensures that clinical partners are not enabled to process personal data at a platform level.
11.	Processing activities performed at the clinical site are carried out on the original dataset, while processing activities performed at a platform level, solely involves depersonalised datasets.
C)	CONTROLLERS PROCESSORS AND RECIPIENTS
12.	There are three separate groups of entities participating in the MES-CoBraD joint research project. According to their role, they can be separated in 1. Medical Partners; 2. Technical Partners; and 3. Supporting Partners.
13.	While all partners decide jointly to undertake and participate in the scientific research, not all partners are equally responsible for all data processing activities taking place during the project.
14.	Clinical Partners processing datasets in MES-CoBraD are solely responsible for the collection and further processing of the datasets they decide to share with the consortium.
15.	With regard to depersonalized data stored at a platform level, only the clinical partner who possesses the pseudonym key is capable of, and allowed to, identify the data subject, and therefore remains the sole controller of the data.
D)	DE-PERSONALISATION OF PERSONAL DATA
16.	The de-personalisation module has been developed and installed at each clinical site, to ensure that the processing at the MES-CoBraD platform by partners other than the controller of the original dataset is performed exclusively on de-personalised data.
17.	De-personalisation in MES-CoBraD operates in five steps, combining both automatic and manual processes.
18.	Whether the module will render the personal data anonymous or pseudonymous cannot be concluded beforehand, and it depends on the result obtained after the adequate execution of each of the five depersonalisation steps.

19.	Once the data is uploaded to the data lake, only the medical partner uploading the data can re-identify the data uploaded with the original dataset stored at the clinical site.
20.	Datasets are removed of identifiers and do not enable the re-identification of individuals to any partner, except the controller of the original dataset.
21.	Data are anonymised instantly, which means that the edge module only retains temporary memory of the data pre-anonymisation. This data can only be accessed by authorised users within the clinical sites who are bound by the clinical site's responsibility, protocols and policies
22.	If, after the depersonalization processing, the depersonalization module successfully renders the dataset anonymous for the potential recipients of the dataset, the data uploaded is no longer personal data, and therefore those recipients do not process personal data at the MES-CoBraD platform.
23.	Alternatively, if it is considered “reasonably likely” for the potential recipients to re-identify the individuals from whom the depersonalized datasets come from, then the data remain personal data and the GDPR will continue to apply to those processing activities performed on the dataset uploaded into the platform.
24.	The risk of reidentification of the data has been assessed by means of “test of reasonable likelihood of identification” recital 26 of the GDPR.
25.	For the assessment of depersonalization in MES-CoBraD, five objective criteria have been identified to motivate the “reasonable likelihood of reidentification”: 1) The recipient; 2) the data uploaded; 3) the legal means of reidentification; 4) the technical means of reidentification for the motivated intruder; 5) the effectiveness of the depersonalization module.
26.	An individual assessment has been performed on each type of dataset of RWD processed in MES-CoBraD taking into account its applicable “depersonalization” technique.
27.	Based on the technical insights provided by the partners, it has been considered that technical safeguards have been put in place to prevent the identification of the uploaded datasets.
28.	It is observed that partners do not have the legal means to access the controllers' pseudonymized database.
29.	All partners have explicitly committed to not attempt the re-identification pursuant to the MES-CoBraD data processing policy.
30.	To conclude, considering the information examined in this deliverable and that reported in the MES-CoBraD DMP, it can be confirmed that uploaded datasets are depersonalised in a manner that ensures that, during the project, no recipient of datasets processes personal data at the MES- CoBraD platform
E)	DATA PROTECTION PRINCIPLES IN MES-COBRAD
31.	The processing personal data for research in MES-CoBraD is based on the approvals obtained from the Ethics Boards/Committees of the clinical partners.
32.	The lawfulness of the processing of personal data obtained by the clinical sites and other clinical settings are governed by their own laws, regulations and procedure.
33.	As part of their obligations as controllers, partners in MES-CoBraD need to choose a legal basis for the processing of datasets performed during the project.
34.	Information concerning the processing of a dataset is provided in the relevant Research

	dataset template (RDT) in the D2.2 Data management plan. This includes details on the Data collection, documentation and curation, analysis, training of AI algorithms, disclosure to partners, destruction.
35.	For the duration of the EC Grant agreement, the purpose of the datasets uploaded into the MES-CoBraD platform is solely to carry out scientific research.
36.	A test of accuracy is envisaged at the different steps of the MES-CoBraD processing lifecycle. This is part of the scientific process with the aim to prove the project's accuracy through hypothesis testing and other statistical analysis tools.
37.	At the current stage of the development, data is not necessarily updated during MES-CoBraD because uploaded datasets are de-personalised and not meant to re-identify individuals. As such, testing the accuracy of depersonalised data is not necessary, unless they introduce errors in the analyses.
38.	The following organisational measures have been adopted to promote the project's culture toward accountability. ²⁵⁹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opinions and approvals by ethics committees - Data processing records - Data processing policy - Data subject request protocols - Data breach protocols
39.	The project's compliance with its data protection obligations relies greatly on the design of the MES-CoBraD platform itself. The separation between edge module at each clinical site and the cloud platform mitigates the chance of risks to personal data processed during the project.
F)	STORAGE, INTEGRITY, CONFIDENTIALITY AND SECURITY
40.	Processing taking place on the MES-CoBraD platform must comply with the obligations provided by the GDPR, including observing the security of obligations.
41.	Considering that the assessment of MES-CoBraD processing activities is strongly dependant on its capacity to minimise risks towards re-identification, the obligation to ensure security is of utmost importance.
42.	Following the recommendation in D2.3, the project has adopted a data breach notification protocol. This has been included in the D2.2 MES-CoBraD data management plan.
43.	Clinical sites participating in MES-CoBraD are certified under ISO 27001 and ISO 27799 and have operative means of managing policies and procedures for information security. Based on their obligations from GDPR, the NIS Directive, and several national laws and regulations, clinical sites implement several controls, policies and procedures from the ISO 27001 standard. At the same time, the platform is deployed in organisations that are certified under ISO 27001.
44.	The processing that takes place within the MES-CoBraD platform is robust and can withstand changes in terms of regulatory demands, incidents and cyberattacks.
45.	The compartmentalisation of types of datasets resulting from the edge module depersonalisation, ensures that data stored at a platform level cannot be used on its own to re-identify data subjects.

²⁵⁹ MES-CoBraD D2.2 Data Mangament Plan- v2 section3.

46.	With regards to the data stored at clinical sites, this remains under the clinical sites' scope, thus the responsibility for any identifiable personal data resides with the clinical site, its technical and organisational measures.
47.	Security is being addressed using multiple controls in the platform, including VPN connections, cryptography, access control.
48.	The platform has been designed to incorporate data processing records as per Article 30 of the GDPR.
49.	The DMP and the research dataset templates have facilitated the record keeping of the data being processed during the project.
50.	The metadata manager explains where the metadata catalogue of the MES-CoBraD datasets is described.
51.	Verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the AI system's reliability and reproducibility, have been developed as part of the validation of the training of AI algorithms and are being deployed per case as part of the workflow component.
52.	The re-purposing of processing activities is not possible during the MES-CoBraD project (i.e from research to healthcare, commercial exploitation, etc). There is an express commitment by the partners included in the project Data Processing policy to only process personal data in the context of MES-CoBraD solely for the research purposes identified, including data analysis, training of AI algorithms, scientific research, etc. It covers all possible uses of open research data. See Section 3 of the D2.2 Data Management Plan
53.	The design of the platform is based on the de-personalisation of datasets. It is based on this design feature that the risks on subsequent processing are mitigated.
G)	DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS
54.	Patients that have shared personal data with a clinical partner are able to withdraw their consent.
55.	In the event a data subject withdraws their consent, all personal data relating to that subject is deleted from the clinical site.
56.	Provided that datasets located at the clinical sites are the only ones containing identifiers enabling re-identification, a consent withdrawal does not necessarily imply the deletion of the dataset uploaded into the platform once they have undergone de-personalisation.
57.	Data subjects are granted the highest degree of autonomy possible with respect to control over their personal data with regards to the data processing at the MES-CoBraD platform.
H)	INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS
58.	During the project, we have examined whether transfers of personal data to non-EU countries, namely Israel and the United Kingdom, took place in MES-CoBraD.
59.	From the information provided by the partners, we can conclude that both countries export but do not import, data from the MES-CoBraD platform. As a result, no international transfer of data takes place during MES-CoBraD (See section 3 of the DMP).

60.	Even in the case that such transfer of data takes place, that would still not qualify as an international data transfer as per the GDPR, insofar the two third countries present in the consortium, Israel, and the United Kingdom, have both been granted an adequacy decision by the European Commission.
I)	DEPLOYMENT CONSIDERATIONS
61.	The possibility that the MES-CoBraD Platform could be used for discriminating purposes (i.e job applications, insurance policy, financial products) has been taken into consideration. Indeed, it is recognised that from a technical point of view the tools developed in MES-CoBraD could be used for discriminatory purposes. During MES-CoBraD the controllers of the datasets remain clinical partners, who have agreed to sign a declaration of compliance with their institutional and national laws.
62.	In a hypothetical scenario of deployment, the technical and organisational measures adopted during the Project would need to be revisited and adjusted to reflect the new level of risks. Particularly the nature of its stakeholders and its commercial relations. Another especially important aspect concerns cybersecurity and the adjustment of the platform to the NIS2 Directive as well as relevant industry standards.
63.	The validity of the assessments performed in this document will need to be re-assessed, insofar the circumstances around the processing activities performed at or through the platform change or evolve. At the same time, the legal and ethical assessments need to be responsive to changes in law or interpretation of law, reassessing the implications for MES-CoBraD as needed.

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